

Experimental Quantum Memory Applications and Demonstration of an Elementary Quantum Repeater Link with Entangled Light-Matter Interfaces

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Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	Concept of the quantum repeater	7
2.1	Point-to-point quantum communication	7
2.2	Connection of elementary pairs	8
2.3	The DLCZ protocol	13
2.4	Robust long-distance atom-atom entanglement	14
2.5	Review of quantum memories	16
3	Experimental demonstration of an elementary quantum repeater link	39
3.1	Deterministic sub- μ s readout of a single-atom quantum memory	39
3.2	A light-matter quantum interface	45
3.3	Heralded entanglement between widely separated quantum memories . . .	55
3.3.1	Bell-State Measurement via Two-Photon Interference	55
3.3.2	Atom-Atom Entanglement via Entanglement Swapping	58
4	Remote preparation of an atomic quantum memory	69
5	Conclusion and Outlook	75
6	Publication List	85

1 Introduction

Quantum communication is the art of transferring quantum information from one location to another, taking advantage of the essential features of quantum mechanics like the uncertainty principle, randomness, and entanglement. For example, in quantum key distribution (QKD) [1, 2, 3, 4, 5] – the most advanced application in quantum communication – these features are utilized to exchange between two distant parties a shared random secret key, which is then used to encrypt and decrypt classical messages. The maximum distance, however, over which quantum information can reliably be communicated, respectively a secret key can be exchanged on basis of a simple point-to-point link, is fundamentally limited due to transmission losses in optical communication channels to about few 100 km. In order to overcome this problem, straightforward amplification of the signal at intermediate repeater stations as in classical optical telecommunication cannot be directly adopted. This is due to the fact that unknown quantum states cannot be perfectly cloned [6] or amplified. Any attempt to amplify a quantum signal would add additional noise to the quantum channel. The only approach to extend quantum communication distances beyond the fundamental limit of ordinary point-to-point devices is the “*quantum repeater*” [7, 8]. The central idea of a quantum repeater is to establish highly entangled pairs of qubits over a large distance and to use these pairs to transmit, e.g., arbitrary quantum information via quantum teleportation [9]. Here, the distribution of long-distance entanglement is achieved by dividing the quantum channel into a sequence of shorter segments (see Fig. 1.1) and then connecting these segments with a nested sequence of entanglement connection (i.e. entanglement swapping [10]) and entanglement purification [7, 11] steps. As a central result and in contrast to point-to-point quantum communication the quantum repeater provides a way to avoid exponential scaling of the resources with the communication distance.

Any physical implementation of a quantum repeater requires three major ingredients. (i) The ability to generate entanglement between stationary qubits over short distances via local CNOT operations. In turn, this requires the possibility to store and coherently manipulate quantum information in quantum memories (QM). (ii) One has to be able to connect two widely separated repeater stations such, that both stations share common pairs of entangled qubits. While the establishment of entanglement between distant nodes can be achieved with the help of photons, storage of quantum information is realized best with stationary matter-based quantum memories. This implies (iii), mandatory interfaces between flying qubits (e.g., photons) and stationary qubits (e.g., trapped atoms).

Figure 1.1: Principle of quantum repeaters. (a) Creation of entanglement between intermediate links. (b) Entanglement swapping between neighboring links creates entanglement over larger distances. Successive nested entanglement swapping and entanglement purification operations (for the sake of simplicity not shown here) are performed until (c) sender A and receiver B share a highly entangled pair of stationary qubits.

After the pioneering theoretical work by *Briegel et al.* [7] in 1998, *Duan et al.* [12] proposed in 2001 an alternative concept on the basis of atomic ensembles and linear optics. This work inspired a sequence of first experiments. Cold atomic ensembles were employed demonstrating first proof-of-principle realizations of elementary segments for quantum repeaters, i.e. the storage of single photonic qubits up to few ms with a maximum efficiency of 1.18 % [13, 14, 15, 16, 17], reconversion of stored quantum information onto single photons in the NIR as well as conversion to the telecom band with the help of entangled light-matter interfaces [18, 19, 20], quantum teleportation with atomic and photonic qubits [21], and most important the entanglement between separated ensembles [22, 23, 24, 25, 26]. With mesoscopic solid-state quantum memories (rare-earth doped crystals) a multi-mode light-matter interface at the single photon level has been realized [27], however, with low storage efficiency ($< 1\%$) and short memory time ($< 1\mu\text{s}$). Quite recently the heralded entanglement between two crystals was reported [28]. In turn, these experimental demonstrations inspired again the development of new protocols. Amongst others, fault-tolerant quantum communication based on nitrogen vacancy (NV) centers in diamond [29], a hybrid quantum repeater using bright coherent light [30, 31], a multiplexed memory-insensitive quantum repeater [32], and an efficient quantum repeater based on deterministic Rydberg gates [33] were proposed.

A promising alternative approach following much closer the original proposal by *Briegel et al.* [7, 8] relies on single trapped ions, atoms, quantum-dots, and NV-color centers in diamond. In contrast to mesoscopic systems this approach is ideally suited

Figure 1.2: (a) Generation of atom-photon entanglement in Rb-87 via spontaneous decay. Each atom in (b) is excited with a short optical laser pulse to the $5^2P_{3/2}, F' = 0$ hyperfine level. In the following spontaneous emission processes each atom spontaneously decays to the ground level $5^2S_{1/2}, F = 1$ with the magnetic sub-levels $m_F = -1, 0, +1$ by emitting a σ^+, π, σ^- polarized photon, respectively. Provided these decay channels are indistinguishable in all other degrees of freedom and the π -decay is suppressed by spatial filtering a maximally entangled state between the photonic qubit $\{|\sigma^+\rangle, |\sigma^-\rangle\}$ and the atomic spin-qubit $\{|m_F = -1\rangle, |m_F = +1\rangle\}$ is formed. (b) Generation of entanglement between two remote atoms via entanglement swapping. Two photons – each entangled with a single atom – interfere on a 50:50 beam splitter (BS). A coincident detection of the photons in the two output ports of the BS projects them onto a maximally entangled $|\Psi^-\rangle$ Bell-state (Bell-state measurement), thereby swapping the entanglement onto the remote atoms.

for the implementation of several quantum memories within few μm^3 amount of space, enabling scalability to a large number of stationary qubits. With trapped ions/atoms and individual NV-centers in diamond the deterministic preparation of short-range entanglement of two [34, 35, 36, 37] and more than two qubits [38, 39, 40, 41] is realized almost routinely nowadays. In the context of long-distance quantum communication entanglement between matter qubits and single photons [42, 43, 44, 45] at distances up to 300 m and coherence times of several 100 μs [46, 47] has been demonstrated. This avenue recently culminated in the demonstration of heralded entanglement between two single trapped ions at a distance of 1 m [48, 49]. However, heralded entanglement between independent remote atomic systems at large distances, so far, was an open experimental problem [50, 51, 52].

The objective of our research within the last 7 years was to develop new experimental methods needed for long-distance quantum communication with single trapped atoms and single photons. *The central idea of our activities was the first experimental demonstration of heralded entanglement between two independently trapped atoms at remote*

locations via entanglement swapping [10]. This is achieved by employing two entangled atom-photon pairs as light-matter interfaces (see Fig. 1.2(a)) and by performing an interferometric Bell-state measurement on the photons [53, 54] (see Fig. 1.2(b)). Within this context we demonstrated for the first time:

- The highly efficient state-selective sub- μs detection of single atoms [55]*.
- The storage and analysis of photonic quantum information in the Zeeman levels of a single optically trapped atom [46, 47]*.
- The generation and analysis of entanglement between a single photon and a single trapped atom, including a first full quantum state tomography of the atom-photon qubit pair [43]*.
- The remote preparation of a single-atom quantum memory, applying a quantum teleportation protocol [56]*.
- The reliable distribution of atom-photon entanglement via an actively stabilized optical fiber link of 300 m length [46]*.
- The high-fidelity Bell-state measurement of photons emitted by two independently trapped Rb-87 atoms (to be submitted).
- The generation and analysis of heralded entanglement between two single trapped atoms at a distance of 20 m (submitted to Science 2012)*.

I would like to emphasize that our recently achieved heralded entanglement between widely separated atoms is a significant step towards scalable long-distance quantum communication with single neutral atoms.

Overview

This work is organized as follows. In the first chapter the concept of quantum repeaters is introduced on the example of the proposals by *Briegel et al.* [7] and *Duan-Lukin-Cirac-Zoller* (DLCZ) [12]. Then our specific approach on the basis of single trapped atoms, single photons, and entangled atom-photon pairs is sketched and an overview about diverse quantum memories is given. The third chapter introduces a new experimental technique allowing the fast and highly efficient state detection of single optically trapped atoms. Furthermore, it presents our central building block for long-distance quantum communication, i.e. the experimental demonstration of an entangled light-matter interface. The third chapter closes with our recent experimental achievements, the heralded entanglement between two remote quantum memories. Chapter four highlights the application of a first quantum communication protocol, which allowed us to prepare an atomic quantum memory at a remote location via a quantum teleportation

protocol. Finally, chapter five summarizes our major achievements and gives a short outlook towards the solution of so far unanswered physical questions.

2 Concept of the quantum repeater

The central problem of quantum communication is the creation of high-fidelity entanglement between distant qubits. In this introductory chapter I will give a short overview why simple point-to-point transmission of qubits over noisy quantum channels is not sufficient to overcome the problem of transmission losses and decoherence. Then, the concept of the quantum repeater is introduced on the example of the theoretical proposal by *Briegel et al.* [7], including all necessary building blocks like nested entanglement swapping and purification. Based on atomic ensembles and linear optics a first possible implementation of a quantum repeater link is reviewed on the example of the DLCZ protocol [12]. Major advantages and drawbacks are discussed. Finally, a robust alternative experimental implementation with single trapped atoms, single photons, entangled light-matter interfaces, and entanglement swapping on the basis of Hong-Ou-Mandel interference of indistinguishable photons on a beam-splitter is introduced, forming the basis of our research activities within the last seven years.

2.1 Point-to-point quantum communication

Figure 2.1: Simple and concatenated transmission of qubits (single photons) between two remote locations A and B. To transmit single qubits over long distances, the quantum channel is split into several segments [57].

Lets assume we want to send a qubit (photon) from location A to location B (see Fig. 2.1(a) [57]). Sender (A) and receiver (B) are connected via a lossy communication channel (e.g. optical fiber) of length l . The probability for a successful transmission of a qubit is $p(l) = e^{-l/l_0}$, where l_0 defines the fiber attenuation length. The corresponding

average number $n(l)$ of required repetitions for one successful transmission is then

$$n(l) = e^{l/l_0}. \quad (2.1)$$

Hence, in point-to-point quantum communication via lossy channels, the error probability scales exponentially with the length of the channel and so does the average number of trials needed for a successful transmission [7]. This effect severely limits the distance between two directly connected communication nodes (typical attenuation lengths l_0 of optical fibers at a wavelength λ are: 62 m at $\lambda = 350$ nm; 1.44 km at $\lambda = 780$ nm; 22 km at $\lambda = 1.55$ μm).

To overcome the problem of losses due to absorption consider the following alternative situation [57]. Instead of directly sending the qubit from A to B, we divide the quantum channel in N segments (see Fig. 2.1(b)). The probability for a successful transmission on each segment is $p(l/N) = e^{-l/l_0 N}$ and the corresponding average number of repetitions $n(l/N) = e^{l/l_0 N}$. The total number of transmissions n_{comp} required for successfully sending a qubit across the concatenated channel is

$$n_{comp} = \frac{N}{p(l/N)} = N e^{l/N l_0}. \quad (2.2)$$

If $N e^{l/N l_0} < e^{l/l_0}$, the concatenated quantum channel is preferable to a simple point-to-point channel. Then the corresponding minimum number of transmission trials n_{min} along the concatenated quantum channel is obtained if all segments have the length l_0 , i.e.

$$n_{min} = N_{min} e^{l/N_{min} l_0} = \frac{l}{l_0} e, \quad (2.3)$$

with $N_{min} = l/l_0$. Although the concatenated link is scalable with the help of quantum memories this approach has a major problem. Any attempt to amplify or clone the qubit (which is generally unknown) from segment to segment will introduce additional noise to the communication process [6] and thus additional methods are required to allow efficient long-distance quantum communication.

2.2 Connection of elementary pairs

To further clarify the problem of noise, consider the following equivalent problem [57], which is the central idea of the *quantum repeater* [7]. Instead of sending single qubits repeatedly over successive segments $A \& C_1$, $C_1 \& C_2$, ..., $C_{N-1} \& B$ lets create N elementary pairs of entangled stationary particles (e.g. quantum memories) of fidelity F_1 (see Fig. 2.4(a)). By connecting all these pairs at the nodes C_i via entanglement swapping [10] and by classically communicating the measurement results between the nodes as in quantum teleportation [9], this will result in a single pair of entangled particles shared between $A \& B$. Even for perfect operations involved in the connection process,

Figure 2.2: Principle of entanglement swapping. Two sources produce two pairs of entangled particles, pair $A - B$ and pair $C - D$. One particle from each pair (particles B and C) is subjected to a common Bell-state measurement. This results in a projection of particles A and D onto an entangled state.

the overall fidelity F_N decreases exponentially. Connecting, e.g., N pairs of fidelity F_1 one obtains a final pair with reduced fidelity [7]

$$F_N = \frac{1}{4} \left[1 + 3 \left(\frac{4F_1 - 1}{3} \right)^N \right]. \quad (2.4)$$

If the final value of F_N drops below a threshold value of $F_{min} = 0.5$ the resulting quantum state does not contain any entanglement and consequently also entanglement based quantum communication will not work any more. By splitting the quantum channel into shorter segments, it seems that one has eliminated the effect of an exponentially increasing number of required transmission trials, however, at the cost of an exponentially decreasing fidelity [57]. To overcome this problem one has to connect a smaller number $L < N$ of pairs via entanglement swapping, such that $F_L > F_{min}$ and entanglement purification becomes possible [58, 59, 57].

Entanglement Swapping

In order to concatenate successive entangled pairs of stationary qubits entanglement swapping [10] is of paramount importance. The entanglement swapping protocol starts with the preparation of two maximally entangled pairs of particles $A - B$ and $C - D$ (see Fig. 2.2), each in a spin singlet state $|\Psi^-\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow\rangle|\downarrow\rangle - |\downarrow\rangle|\uparrow\rangle)$. The overall state $|\Psi\rangle_{ABCD}$ of this composite system is then given by a tensor product

$$|\Psi\rangle_{ABCD} = |\Psi^-\rangle_{AB} \otimes |\Psi^-\rangle_{CD} = \frac{1}{2} \left(|\uparrow\rangle_A |\downarrow\rangle_B - |\downarrow\rangle_A |\uparrow\rangle_B \right) \otimes \left(|\uparrow\rangle_C |\downarrow\rangle_D - |\downarrow\rangle_C |\uparrow\rangle_D \right). \quad (2.5)$$

This state can be also written as

$$|\Psi\rangle_{ABCD} = \frac{1}{2} \left(|\Psi^+\rangle_{AD} |\Psi^+\rangle_{BC} - |\Psi^-\rangle_{AD} |\Psi^-\rangle_{BC} \right)$$

$$- |\Phi^+\rangle_{AD}|\Phi^+\rangle_{BC} + |\Phi^-\rangle_{AD}|\Phi^-\rangle_{BC}), \quad (2.6)$$

which is a sum of tensor products of the four maximally entangled Bell states

$$|\Psi^+\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow\rangle|\downarrow\rangle + |\downarrow\rangle|\uparrow\rangle), \quad (2.7)$$

$$|\Psi^-\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow\rangle|\downarrow\rangle - |\downarrow\rangle|\uparrow\rangle), \quad (2.8)$$

$$|\Phi^+\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow\rangle|\uparrow\rangle + |\downarrow\rangle|\downarrow\rangle), \quad (2.9)$$

$$|\Phi^-\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow\rangle|\uparrow\rangle - |\downarrow\rangle|\downarrow\rangle). \quad (2.10)$$

In a next step, particles B and C are projected onto a maximally entangled Bell-state. This joint Bell-state measurement on the pair $B - C$ in turn prepares the remaining particles A and D in an entangled state, although the particles have been produced by two independent sources and hence have never interacted in their common past.

Entanglement purification

A second requirement of a quantum repeater is entanglement purification. The idea of entanglement purification protocols is to increase the degree of entanglement of a non-maximally entangled quantum state [60, 61, 11]. To this aim, one needs to gain some information about the considered state by performing suitable measurements. However, because any local measurement on an entangled pair will destroy the original state, there is no direct way to purify the original state. To overcome this problem the central idea of entanglement purification is to use a number of copies of non-maximally entangled pairs shared between two distant parties A and B with fidelity $F_1 > 0.5$. Using the example of two distributed pairs (see Fig. 2.3(a)), after local manipulations (bilateral CNOT gates) one of the copies is measured and depending on the outcome of the correlation measurement the other copy is kept or discarded [11] (see Fig. 2.3(b)). In the case of a successful purification step the fidelity of the remaining pair is increased. The procedure is iterated, whereby states resulting from a successful purification round are used as input for the next step [11] (see Fig. 2.3(b)). Ideally, this kind of purification protocol converges to a maximally entangled Bell-state.

Nested swapping and purification loops

We are now in the situation to introduce the central operation principle of quantum repeaters, i.e. the distribution of high-fidelity entanglement between distant quantum memories via a nested sequence of entanglement swapping [10] and entanglement purification [58, 7, 11] (see Fig. 2.4), such that the number of required resources does not grow exponentially with the number N of segments [7, 57, 62].

Figure 2.3: (a) Schematic representation of bipartite entanglement purification via bilateral local CNOT operations and two-particle correlation measurements (black arrows) [58]. (b) Schematic of iterative bipartite entanglement purification [11]. States from a successful purification round ($F_{i+1} > F_i$) serve as inputs for the next round.

As already described we divide the quantum channel of length l into N smaller segments of length $l_0 = l/N$ and distribute over each segment of length l_0 in parallel several entangled pairs of fidelity $F_1 > 0.5$ (see Fig. 2.4). For each segment, M of these pairs are purified in a first step constituting new entangled pairs of fidelity $F_2 > F_1$, respectively (see Fig. 2.4(a); here $M = 3$). In a next step L successive entangled pairs of fidelity F_2 are connected via entanglement swapping (local CNOT operations) resulting in new entangled pairs of length Ll_0 with a fidelity larger or equal to F_1 , respectively (see Fig. 2.4(a→b); here $L = 2$). These steps are repeated until M pairs of length Ll_0 are available. After application of this entanglement purification and connection procedure one has an equivalent situation as at the beginning, but now the length of elementary pairs is Ll_0 . At this nesting level, the total number of elementary pairs is LM , as L pairs are connected and M copies are required for purification. Performing again an entanglement connection and purification loop with these pairs one ends up with pairs of distance L^2l_0 and fidelity F_1 (at nesting level 2). Proceeding in the same way (after n nesting levels the distance of the pairs is L^n) only a logarithmic number $n = \log_L N$ of nesting levels is required to cover the distance $l = l_0 N$.

A detailed theoretical analysis of this quantum communication protocol shows that the total number of elementary entangled pairs R will be $(LM)^n$, which can be expressed

Figure 2.4: Principle of quantum repeaters: Nested entanglement purification and swapping ($L = 2$; $M = 3$). (a) Creation of entanglement between intermediate links via entanglement swapping and entanglement purification. After purifying on each short segment $M = 3$ pairs to one new pair, respectively, two successive repeater segments ($L = 2$) are connected via local CNOT operations creating new entangled pairs over larger distances. These steps are repeated with new initial entangled pairs until M entangled pairs are available at all longer segments. (b) At nesting level $n = 2$, entanglement purification over each of these M new pairs is performed until a highly entangled pair of stationary qubits is generated for the next entanglement swapping operation. This iterative sequence is repeated at each nesting level until (c) sender A and receiver B share a widely separated, highly entangled pair of stationary qubits.

in the form [7]

$$R = N^{\log_L M + 1}. \quad (2.11)$$

This result highlights that in contrast to ordinary point-to-point quantum communication where the resources grow exponentially with the distance N , the quantum repeater allows quantum communication with only *polynomially* growing resources [7, 57].

2.3 The DLCZ protocol

After *Briegel et al.* [7] introduced the theoretical concept of quantum repeaters in a pure mathematical language, in 2001 *Duan, Lukin, Cirac, and Zoller* (DLCZ) proposed a first experimental implementation with atomic ensembles and linear optics [12]. Although this protocol is not of central relevance for our experimental implementation a significant amount of experimental demonstrations up to date rely on this protocol.

The central idea of the DLCZ protocol is to generate entanglement between two remote atomic ensembles via Raman scattering and single photon detection (see Fig. 2.5). In detail, the two atomic ensembles – located at positions A and B – are initially prepared via, e.g., optical pumping into the atomic ground states $|g_1\rangle$. Then the two ensembles are excited with short off-resonant optical laser pulses simultaneously such that a single Stokes photon on the atomic transition $|e\rangle \rightarrow |g_2\rangle$ is emitted in either of the two spatial modes a or b . These two modes are combined on a beam splitter (BS) at an intermediate station between A and B . The detection of a single photon behind the beam splitter (detector D or \bar{D}) projects the overall state of the atomic ensembles onto

$$|\psi_{ab}\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|1_a\rangle|0_b\rangle + e^{i\theta_{ab}}|0_a\rangle|1_b\rangle), \quad (2.12)$$

where $|1_{a(b)}\rangle$ denotes the storage of a single atomic excitation in ensemble A , respectively B , and $|0_{a(b)}\rangle$ respective empty ensembles. The interferometric phase $\theta_{ab} = \phi_a - \phi_b + \xi_a - \xi_b$ is given by the phase difference $\phi_a - \phi_b$ of the exciting lasers at ensemble A and B respectively, and the phase difference $\xi_a - \xi_b$ is acquired by the Stokes photon on its way from the ensembles to the beam splitter. The overall success probability P_{DLCZ} of this process is given by $P_{DLCZ} = p\eta e^{-\frac{l}{2l_0}}$, where p denotes the overall generation, collection and coupling efficiency of a single Stokes photon into the optical fiber, η the quantum efficiency of the single photon detectors, l_0 the fiber attenuation length, and l the overall length of the repeater segment.

This brings us already to the two major challenges of the DLCZ protocol. (i) In order to generate a measurable entangled state, the interferometric phase θ_{ab} has to be stable during operation of the experiment. In [23] it was actively stabilized over a distance of 2.8 m using additional lasers. Extending the interferometrically sensitive DLCZ protocol to distances of several km may be challenging with current experimental techniques. (ii) An additional problem is that the number state entanglement of Eq.

Figure 2.5: Entanglement generation between two remote atomic ensembles at locations A and B according to Duan, Lukin, Cirac, and Zoller [12].

2.12 is not easy to verify because single qubit rotations in the number basis are difficult to implement. To overcome this problem DLCZ proposed to entangle two chains of entangled number states in parallel. In this way it is possible to create an effective two-excitation entangled state by post selection [12, 14, 63]. With this extended scheme the phase of the quantum channel has to be constant only during the time interval between the entanglement generation in the two parallel chains (typically few $10 \mu\text{s}$) [14, 63].

2.4 Robust long-distance atom-atom entanglement

In order to avoid the necessity of interferometric stability of the quantum channel on a length scale of the optical wavelength as well as number state entanglement, alternatively entangled light-matter interfaces and entanglement swapping on the basis of two-photon detections can be used for the robust generation of entanglement between remote quantum memories [64, 65].

In our approach quantum memories are implemented by single optically trapped ^{87}Rb atoms [66, 55]. The memory qubit is stored in the Zeeman sublevels $m_F = \pm 1$ of the $5^2S_{1/2}, F = 1$ hyperfine ground level [43, 46], whereas the communication qubit is encoded in the polarization degree of freedom of a single photon emitted on the lambda-type atomic transition $5^2P_{3/2}, F' = 0 \rightarrow 5^2S_{1/2}, F = 1$ at a wavelength of 780 nm [43].

In order to reliably entangle two atoms at remote locations via entanglement swapping and two-photon detections, in a first step each atom is excited with a short optical laser pulse to the $5^2P_{3/2}, F' = 0$ hyperfine level. In the following spontaneous emission pro-

Figure 2.6: (a) Generation of atom-photon entanglement in Rb-87. (b) Generation of long-distance atom-atom entanglement via entanglement swapping.

cesses (see Fig. 2.6(a)) each atom spontaneously decays to the ground level $5^2S_{1/2}$, $F = 1$ with the magnetic sub-levels $m_F = -1, 0, +1$ by emitting a σ^+ , π , σ^- polarized photon, respectively. Provided these decay channels are indistinguishable in all other degrees of freedom and the π -decay is suppressed by spatial filtering of the photon a maximally entangled state $|\psi\rangle_{AP}$ between the photonic qubit $\{|\sigma^+\rangle, |\sigma^-\rangle\}$ and the atomic spin-qubit $\{|m_F = -1\rangle = |\downarrow\rangle_z, |m_F = +1\rangle = |\uparrow\rangle_z\}$ is formed, resulting in

$$|\psi\rangle_{AP} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\downarrow\rangle_z|\sigma^+\rangle + |\uparrow\rangle_z|\sigma^-\rangle). \quad (2.13)$$

Each of the two photons is collected via a large numerical aperture objective, coupled into a single mode optical fiber, and guided to an intermediate location, where the photons interfere on a 50:50 beam splitter (BS). Finally, a coincident detection of the photons in the two output ports of the BS projects them onto a maximally entangled $|\Psi^-\rangle$ Bell-state (Bell-state measurement), thereby swapping the entanglement onto the remote atoms:

$$|\psi^-\rangle_{At-At} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow\rangle_x|\downarrow\rangle_x - |\downarrow\rangle_x|\uparrow\rangle_x). \quad (2.14)$$

The overall success probability of this protocol is given by

$$P_{At-At} = \frac{1}{4}(p\eta)^2 e^{-(L_1+L_2)/l_0}, \quad (2.15)$$

where p denotes the overall generation, collection, and coupling efficiency of a photon into the optical fiber, η the quantum efficiency of the single photon detectors, and $e^{-(L_1+L_2)/l_0}$ the photon attenuation in the optical fiber links with communication distances L_1 and L_2 and the fiber attenuation length l_0 . The factor $1/4$ accounts for the fact that only one out of four photonic Bell-states is detected. Typically $p\eta \approx 10^{-3}$. Provided the photon attenuation in the fibers is neglected we expect an overall success probability of 2×10^{-7} .

In comparison with the DLCZ-protocol this scheme excels in two major features. On the one hand it avoids number state entanglement by exploiting internal degrees of freedom of the atoms and the photons. On the other hand our entanglement swapping procedure relies on second-order quantum interference of photon pairs on a beam splitter (Hong-Ou-Mandel effect) [53]. By avoiding first-order interference this significantly relaxes the conditions on the optical path length stability (synchronization) of fiber communication channels [65].

2.5 Review of quantum memories

Central element of a quantum repeater [7, 12] are quantum memories (QM). Recently, various reviews gave a compact overview over different memory protocols with ensemble-based memories [67, 68, 63], photon-echo based memories in solid-state atomic ensembles [69], and QM based on electromagnetically induced transparency [70].

The aim of the following colloquium paper “*Quantum memories*” (C. Simon et al., *Eur. Phys. J. D* 58, 1-22 (2010)) was a review of various approaches to the implementation of quantum memories, with in the EU project Qubit Applications (QAP). The approaches to quantum memories represented in this project were quite diverse, including solid-state atomic ensembles in rare-earth doped crystals, NV centers in diamond, semiconductor quantum dots, single trapped atoms, room-temperature and cold atomic gases, and optical phonons in bulk diamond. Specific goal of the following review was to develop a common language, in order to allow a meaningful comparison of these approaches. The review begins by discussing different applications for quantum memories followed by a brief overview of the different meanings that the term quantum memory can have. In section 4, the most important criteria for assessing the performance of quantum memories are given. Section 5 discusses two physical requirements that are important for good quantum memory performance in a range of different approaches. Section 6 is devoted to an overview of the different physical approaches represented in QAP. Finally, section 7 summarizes findings including a comparative table positioning the different approaches with respect to a number of relevant criteria.

Quantum memories

A review based on the European integrated project “Qubit Applications (QAP)”

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Abstract. We perform a review of various approaches to the implementation of quantum memories, with an emphasis on activities within the quantum memory sub-project of the EU integrated project “Qubit Applications”. We begin with a brief overview over different applications for quantum memories and different types of quantum memories. We discuss the most important criteria for assessing quantum memory performance and the most important physical requirements. Then we review the different approaches represented in “Qubit Applications” in some detail. They include solid-state atomic ensembles, NV centers, quantum dots, single atoms, atomic gases and optical phonons in diamond. We compare the different approaches using the discussed criteria.

1 Introduction

Quantum memories are important elements for quantum information processing applications such as quantum networks [1], quantum repeaters [2,3] and linear optics quantum computing [4,5]. The field of quantum memories has recently been very active. Recent reviews include reference [6], which gives a compact overview over different memory protocols with atomic ensembles, reference [7], which deals with ensemble-based memories with a detailed focus on atomic gases, and reference [8], which deals with photon-echo based quantum memories, in particular in solid-state atomic ensembles, as well as reference [9], which is focused on quantum memories based on electromagnetically induced transparency. Quantum memories were also discussed in the Strategic Report on quantum information processing and communication in Europe [10]. The high activity of the field was also reflected in the European integrated project “Qubit Applications (QAP)”, which had

a sub-project involving seven research groups devoted to the development of quantum memories. As members of this sub-project we made a sustained effort over the course of the project to compare our various approaches. This included the definition of appropriate criteria for such comparisons. The present paper has grown out of this effort. We hope that it will be useful for a wider audience.

The approaches to quantum memories represented in the project are quite diverse, including solid-state atomic ensembles in rare-earth doped crystals, NV centers in diamond, semiconductor quantum dots, single trapped atoms, room-temperature and cold atomic gases, and optical phonons in bulk diamond. It was therefore an interesting challenge to develop a common language, in order to be able to perform a meaningful comparison. We will begin this review by discussing different applications for quantum memories in Section 2, followed by a brief overview of the different meanings that the term “quantum memory” can have in Section 3. We will then review the most important criteria for assessing the performance of quantum

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memories in Section 4. Section 5 discusses two physical requirements that are important for good quantum memory performance in a range of different approaches, namely good light-matter coupling and good coherence. Section 6, which is divided in seven sub-sections, is devoted to an overview of the different physical approaches that were represented in “Qubit Applications”. In Section 7 we summarize our findings. This section includes a comparative table that positions the different approaches with respect to a number of relevant criteria.

2 Applications of quantum memories

Quantum memories are important in a number of contexts, including the implementation of single-photon sources, quantum repeaters, loophole-free Bell inequality tests, communication complexity protocols and precision measurements.

2.1 Deterministic single photon sources

One simple, but potentially very important application of a quantum memory is the implementation of a single-photon source. Given a non-deterministic source of photon pairs such as parametric down-conversion, one can realize a deterministic source of single photons by detecting one photon of a pair (when it is emitted), while storing the other one in a memory. Detection of the first photon signals that the memory has been “charged” and can now be used as a single-photon source. In order to implement a close to ideal single-photon source the memory has to be highly efficient. Deterministic single photon sources are important ingredients for linear optics quantum computing [4,5]. They are also useful for certain quantum repeater protocols [3,11].

2.2 Quantum repeaters

Another area where quantum memories are absolutely essential is for the implementation of long-distance quantum communication via quantum repeaters. The direct distribution of quantum states is limited by unavoidable transmission losses in combination with the no-cloning theorem. The quantum repeater approach [2] overcomes this difficulty by combining quantum teleportation and quantum state storage. The idea is to divide a given long distance into shorter elementary links, create and store entanglement independently for each link, then extend it to the whole distance via entanglement swapping (i.e. quantum teleportation of entanglement). This approach is possible only if quantum memories are available. Requirements for quantum memories in this context include long coherence times, efficient interfacing with photons (which serve as long-distance carriers of quantum information) and the possibility of performing entanglement swapping operations [3]. However, it is not absolutely necessary for

the memories to be able to both absorb and emit photons as we assumed in our previous example for realizing a single-photon source. There are different possible approaches, cf. the next section.

2.3 Loophole-free Bell test

A more fundamental application for quantum memories is the realization of a loophole-free test of Bell’s inequality. A loophole-free test requires both creating entanglement over a long distance in order to enforce the locality condition and detecting the entangled systems with high efficiency in order to close the efficiency loophole. One attractive approach towards achieving this goal is to create entanglement between distant atoms or ions via the detection of photons [12,13]. These atoms or ions can be seen as quantum memories. Their interest in the present context lies in the fact that they can be detected with high (essentially unit) efficiency. At the same time such a setup can also be seen as an elementary link of a quantum repeater.

2.4 Communication complexity and protocols requiring local operations and classical communication (LOCC)

Communication complexity, i.e. the number of qubits needed for achieving a certain communication task, has recently been shown to be tightly linked to the violation of Bell-type inequalities [14]. It may be useful to store quantum states transmitted by light in memories in order to achieve loophole free violations of this kind. Communication protocols which require LOCC use memories to perform local operations and store the results while classical communication is going on. Examples of such protocols for continuous variables include iterative continuous variable entanglement distillation [15], continuous variable cluster state quantum computation [16], communication/cryptography protocols involving several rounds [17], and quantum illumination [18].

2.5 Precision measurements

A good quantum memory is capable of storing long-lived entanglement. As such, it can be used as a resource for entanglement enhanced sensing and precision metrology applications. A standard technique to enhance the weak coupling between light and matter is to use ensembles of many atoms. This approach does not only promise efficient quantum memories [19–21], but it can also increase the precision when detecting external disturbances on the state of such a system with quantum mechanically limited resolution. By preparing a collective entangled state of the atomic ensemble (e.g. by storing a squeezed state of light in the memory [22,23] or by squeezing a collective atomic observable via a quantum-non-demolition (QND) measurement [24]), the projection noise can be reduced. Due to the non-classical correlations between the atoms a

measurement precision beyond the classical limit is possible. Already, spin squeezing on the cesium clock transition has been demonstrated, which potentially can improve the precision of optical lattice clocks [25]. Also, an ultra-sensitive RF-magnetometer employing entanglement in a room-temperature Cs vapour cell has been successfully developed [26]. In NMR systems NOON states of 10 entangled spins have been employed to improve upon magnetic field sensing almost tenfold compared to standard measuring strategies [27].

3 Different types of quantum memories

It is useful to distinguish different ways of using quantum memories and of characterizing their performance. This includes the use of quantum memories for storing single photons, for general states of light, and memories that are charged through the emission of photons.

3.1 Memories for single photons

For applications such as the implementation of a single photon source, or quantum repeaters, one often knows that the desired output state of the memory is a single-photon state. For example, a quantum repeater protocol might involve memories that are designed to absorb and reemit photons that are emitted by other sources [11,28] (e.g. photon-pair sources based on parametric down-conversion, or more ideal single-photon or photon-pair sources based on single atoms or quantum dots). In such a situation, it is natural to verify the performance of the memory using photon counting. The memory can then fail in two distinct ways: it can fail to re-emit a photon at all, or it can re-emit a photon whose quantum state has imperfect overlap with the photon that was to be stored. This motivates the distinction between efficiency (probability to emit a photon) and fidelity (overlap of the emitted photon with the original one). The latter is sometimes more precisely denoted conditional fidelity, since it is conditional on a photon having been emitted by the memory. For quantum repeater applications, for example, both efficiency and fidelity should typically be high [3], however the requirements on the efficiency tend to be somewhat less demanding than those on the fidelity. It is interesting to note that for certain ensemble-based implementations of quantum memories decoherence can affect only the efficiency without degrading the fidelity [29]. The memory performance can also be characterized by quantum tomography of the state of the emitted photon. The tomography performed via a homodyne measurement is a deterministic process which produces a full characterization of the memory, from which efficiency and fidelity can be extracted.

3.2 Memories for general states of light

One may also have the goal of storing general states of light independently produced by a third party. Possible

applications range from linear optics quantum computing to complex quantum communication protocols. Following the storage of the state, the memory can either be measured in some basis, or for other applications retrieved onto another light pulse. Various types of states can be useful here, such as coherent states, squeezed states, Schrödinger cat states, single photon, or Fock states. The characterization of the memory performance can then be done either by quantum tomography of the atomic state or by quantum tomography of the retrieved state of light [31]. Here again homodyne measurements on light are used and thus one important concept is the (unconditional) fidelity [30].

3.3 Memories that emit photons and whose state can be measured directly

A different approach to quantum repeaters, but also to the implementation of a loophole-free Bell test, cf. previous section, involves memories (for example, single trapped atoms) that emit photons which are entangled with the memory, and where the atomic state is detected directly [32–35]. The atomic state detection is typically a deterministic process, so the distinction between efficiency and fidelity does not apply in this case, the appropriate concept is (unconditional) fidelity.

3.4 Memories that emit photons and that are measured via retrieval

Even though they were not represented in QAP, we would like to mention ensemble-based memories of the DLCZ (Duan-Lukin-Cirac-Zoller) type [21] where memory excitations are created through the emission of a photon, but where the final readout of the memory is done via conversion of the memory excitation into a single photon. Memory performance can then be characterized in analogy with Section 3.1 [3,7].

4 Criteria for assessing quantum memory performance

We now discuss a number of evaluation criteria (figures of merit) and their relevance for different applications and implementations.

4.1 Fidelity

In general terms, fidelity is related to the overlap between the quantum state that is written into the memory and the state that is read out. It should be noted that the definition of fidelity that is typically used in the context of quantum memories is different from the fidelity used in quantum information theory, e.g. in the context of unambiguous state discrimination, Uhlmann's theorem etc. [36].

For two pure states, the latter corresponds to the modulus of their overlap, whereas the former is the square of that modulus.

The precise operational meaning of the fidelity depends on the specific approach. For memories that store and re-emit single photons, the fidelity is defined as the overlap between the single-photon wave packet that was sent in and the one that is recovered from the memory. This is also denoted *conditional fidelity*, because it is conditional on the re-emission a photon. The probability to actually recover a photon is denoted *efficiency*, cf. the next subsection. For memories that are meant to store general states of light, the conditional fidelity is not an appropriate concept, and one has to consider *unconditional* fidelities.

Note that for some applications, the purity of the output state (for a pure input) can be a better criterion than the fidelity. If the output state is related to the input state by a unitary transformation, this may do no harm. For example, a Bell measurement involving two photon wave packets [37] that have both been stored in quantum memories can be performed with high accuracy if both wave packets have been subject to the same unitary transformation (distortion). However, it seems that impurity of the output state would be a problem for most conceivable applications in quantum information. Such impurity could have different forms, depending on the implementation (e.g. timing jitter, depolarization).

It is clearly important to study which processes will limit the fidelity (purity) of a given implementation. It is also interesting to study which encodings of quantum information are the most advantageous in a given physical system (are there “decoherence-free subspaces”? [38]).

4.2 Efficiency

We already introduced the concept of memory efficiency in the previous section. It is most clearly defined for the case of memories that are meant to store and emit single photons, where it is the probability to re-emit a photon that has been stored. In atomic ensembles the efficiency can in principle be close to one thanks to collective interference effects. For single atomic systems (including quantum dots and NV centers), the efficiency with which a single emitted photon can be recovered is typically small, but it can be enhanced through the use of optical cavities. Efficiency is not a well-defined concept for memories that are meant to store general states of light, the use of (unconditional) fidelity is usually more appropriate.

It is interesting to note that, while high recall efficiency is clearly desirable, it is not always necessary to be very close to 100% for the memory to be useful, for example for proof-of-principle demonstrations of quantum repeaters. However, some applications, such as teleportation of an unknown state, require that the storage of a light state in the memory has unconditional high fidelity. In other words, the combined fidelity times efficiency must be higher than the classical limit. It is important to study the efficiency required for different applications, see e.g. reference [3] for quantum repeater requirements.

4.3 Storage time

This is clearly very important for long-distance quantum communication applications, where the communication time between distant nodes imposes a lower bound on the required storage time. Storage times have to be at least as long as the average entanglement creation times, which are at least in the second range for realistic repeater protocols and relevant distances [3]. A quantitative study of the effect of storage time limitations was recently performed in reference [39]. Long storage times are less important for other applications such as single-photon sources or loophole-free Bell tests.

4.4 Bandwidth

This will influence the practical usefulness of a given memory for most applications, because it determines the achievable repetition rates, and also the multiplexing potential, cf. below. Bandwidth considerations can also be important for matching sources (e.g. parametric down-conversion) and memories. Of course the required numerical value will depend on the desired application.

4.5 Capacity to store multiple photons and dimensionality

The capacity to store several modes is a natural capability for certain ensemble implementations, which can allow a multiplication of the repetition rate, e.g. in quantum communication [28,40]. It is then of interest to quantify the maximum number of photons (modes) that can be stored. The criterion does not apply to single-atom approaches in the same way. The ability to store multiple spatial modes, i.e. to generate quantum holograms, which is inherent to atomic ensembles is one exciting perspective [41]. For a single-mode memory, it can be interesting to quantify its dimensionality, i.e. how many excitations (photons) can be stored.

4.6 Wavelength

As mentioned above, for long-distance quantum communication applications it is important that the wavelength of the photons that propagate over long distances is within the region of small absorption in optical fibers (unless one considers free-space transmission, e.g. to satellites). Depending on the protocol under consideration, this may constrain the operating wavelength of the respective quantum memory.

5 Physical requirements

In this section we want to focus on the physical requirements for implementing good memories, where “good” is defined with respect to the figures of merit discussed in

the previous section. We will focus on figures of merit that seem particularly important, and that are relevant for all approaches, namely efficiency and/or fidelity, and storage time. The described criteria are generally not independent. For example, the longer the desired storage time, the harder it may become to achieve high efficiency and/or high fidelity.

We suggest that for any memory protocol there are at least two requirements in order to achieve high efficiency/fidelity and significant storage time, namely good coupling between traveling and stationary excitations, and good coherence.

5.1 Light-matter coupling

The notion of light-matter coupling is most easily defined for memories that operate by absorbing and re-emitting states of light (cases 2.1 and 2.2 above). In this case, the notion of coupling is directly related to the probability of absorbing the light. In the case of atomic ensembles (whether in gaseous form or in solids), good coupling is achieved by having high optical depth. If such a memory is realized by a single quantum system inside a high-finesse cavity, for example, then the finesse of the cavity will play a role that is analogous to the optical depth. For memories where the memory excitation is created via the emission of a photon (cases 2.3 and 2.4), a critical point is the probability to emit this photon into a well-defined mode. It is at this point that the notion of good coupling intervenes in such systems. For case 2.4, it is also important in the readout process.

Optical depths that are sufficient for excellent memory performance have already been achieved in atomic gas cells (both hot and cold), and are in the process of being achieved for rare-earth doped crystals, using multi-pass configurations and/or particularly strongly absorbing materials. High unconditional fidelity furthermore requires good coherence and high detection efficiency (for the homodyne detection), which have both been achieved in experiments in Copenhagen (see Sect. 6.5). For individual systems such as trapped atoms and NV centers efficient collection of the emitted photons could be achieved with high-Q cavities. It is also worth noting that the possibility of storing multiple modes (temporal, spatial, directional) is being investigated in several ensemble-based approaches. These points will be discussed in detail in Section 6.

5.2 Coherence

We also discuss decoherence. Its effects can be different for different approaches. For example, for memory protocols based on collective effects, such as controlled reversible inhomogeneous broadening (CRIB), decoherence affects the efficiency, but not the conditional fidelity. On the other hand, for single atoms decoherence primarily affects the fidelity, but not the readout or recall efficiency. Nevertheless, decoherence is an important consideration for all implementations. In most systems the coherence is limited

by fluctuating magnetic fields. These can be externally applied fields (for trapped atoms) or fields generated by the solid-state environment, in particular nuclear spins in the host material (NV centers, quantum dots, rare-earth ion ensembles). Coherence properties can then be greatly improved by optimizing the choice of host material (e.g. isotopically purified crystals that have very low concentration of nuclear spins). The following section develops the described topics in more detail for the different experimental approaches within QAP.

6 Implementations

6.1 Rare-earth ions in solids (Lund/Geneva)

We now discuss the possible realizations of quantum memories using ensembles of rare-earth ions in solids. The optical $4f-4f$ transitions in rare-earth ions are known for their long optical coherence times ($100\ \mu\text{s}-1\ \text{ms}$) [42,43] at cryogenic temperatures and it is also possible to find spin transitions with extremely long coherence time ($>1\ \text{s}$) [44–46]. This makes them very suitable for transferring photonic quantum states onto collective atomic coherences, which can be optical as well as spin. Doped into solids the optical transitions have inhomogeneous broadening [47] much larger than the homogeneous broadening given by the optical coherence time. This causes inhomogeneous dephasing of the induced optical coherence that needs to be compensated for. We mention already that the inhomogeneous broadening offers the possibility of a large-bandwidth light-matter interface.

In order to control the inhomogeneous dephasing the considered storage protocols are based on absorption and re-emission of photons using photon-echo effects. It has been shown, however, that traditional two-pulse photon echoes are not suitable for the storage of quantum light [48,49]. This is due to intrinsic spontaneous-emission noise induced by the strong π -pulse used for rephasing of dipole moments. We are going to describe two modified photon echo protocols that can in principle store single photons with efficiency and fidelity up to unity. The first protocol is based on the controlled and reversible inhomogeneous broadening (CRIB) [50–58] of a single absorption line (for a recent review see [8]). The second protocol is based on the reversible absorption by a periodic structure of narrow absorption peaks, a so called atomic frequency comb (AFC) [59–63]. Potential areas of application for this type of quantum memories are for long-distance quantum communication (quantum repeaters) and the realization of quasi-deterministic single-photon sources.

6.1.1 Controlled reversible inhomogeneous broadening

We now describe the first scheme, controlled reversible inhomogeneous broadening (CRIB) [8]. This involves broadening an initially narrow absorption line using the linear Stark effect and an applied external electric field gradient [51,52,54,57]. The width of the broadened line should

match the spectral width of the light that is to be absorbed. Re-emission of the light is triggered by changing the sign of the field, which inverts the atomic transition frequencies around the central frequency. The rephasing mechanism can be understood by the following argument. Atoms at detuning Δ with respect to the carrier frequency of the light accumulates a phase $\exp(-i\Delta\tau)$ between absorption ($t = 0$) and the polarity inversion of the electric field ($t = \tau$). By inverting the polarity, the atoms invert their detunings $\Delta \rightarrow -\Delta$. After a time $t = 2\tau$ the atoms will have accumulated an opposite phase factor $\exp(i\Delta\tau)$ which results in a rephasing of all atomic dipoles.

The following formula can be derived for the memory efficiency η_{CRIB} [54,64]:

$$\eta_{CRIB}(t) = \left(1 - e^{-\tilde{d}}\right)^2 \text{sinc}^2(\gamma_0 t), \quad (1)$$

where $\tilde{d} = d\gamma_0/\gamma$. Here γ_0 is the width of the initial narrow line, γ is the width of the broadened line, d is the optical depth of the initial line, and t is the storage time in the excited state. Note that the initial absorption depth is decreased by the broadening factor γ/γ_0 . Thus the more broadening that is added, the less efficient the storage efficiency becomes. The storage of a single pulse (one mode) can be chosen to be essentially equal to the pulse duration (and thus inversely proportional to γ). Once the pulse has been absorbed, the created atomic excitation can be transferred to a lower-lying state [51,52], e.g. a state that lies in the same hyperfine multiplet as the ground state. The storage time in such a hyperfine state is limited only by (hyperfine) decoherence, cf. below.

One can see that the total efficiency is the product of two factors. The first one is related to the absorption of the light. In fact, it is precisely the square of the absorption probability in the broadened ensemble, since is the optical depth of the broadened line. The square intervenes because in the CRIB protocol, the re-emission process is the exact time reversal of the absorption, so the probability is the same for both processes. The second factor (the squared sinc function) describes the dephasing which is due to the fact that the initial narrow line has a finite width γ_0 . The exact form of the last factor depend on the shape of initial line (which we here assume to be a square function), it being related to its Fourier transform.

In reference [28] an analysis of the performance of CRIB was performed, particularly in terms of multimode storage. It was found that an optical depth of about 30 is required to achieve an efficiency of 0.9 for the storage of a single pulse (one mode). If larger optical depths are available, one can store multiple temporal modes (trains of pulses), which can be very attractive for certain applications, e.g. quantum repeaters. The number of modes that can be stored with a certain fixed efficiency grows linearly with the optical depth [28,65].

6.1.2 Atomic frequency combs

In order to fully exploit temporal multiplexing in quantum repeater architectures, the memory should be able to store

Fig. 1. The AFC quantum memory scheme. Figure from reference [59].

many temporal modes with high efficiency [28]. For EIT based quantum memories, this requires extremely high and currently unrealistic value of optical depth [59,65]. The scaling is better for CRIB based quantum memories but the required optical depth are still very high (e.g. 3000 for 100 modes with 90% efficiency) [28,65]. Recently, a new scheme was proposed [59] for inhomogeneously broadened materials, where the number of stored modes does not depend on the initial optical depth d . The scheme is based on atomic frequency combs (AFC).

The idea of AFC is to tailor the absorption profile of an inhomogeneously broadened solid state atomic medium with a series of periodic and narrow absorbing peaks of width γ_0 , height d and separated by Δ (see Fig. 1). The single photon to be stored is then collectively absorbed by all the atoms in the comb, and the state of the light is transferred to collective atomic excitations at the optical transition. After absorption, the atoms at different frequencies will dephase, but thanks to the periodic structure of the absorption profile, a rephasing occurs after a time $2\pi/\Delta$ which depends on the comb spacing. When the atoms are all in phase again, the light is re-emitted in the forward direction as a result of a collective interference between all the emitters.

In order to achieve longer storage times and on-demand retrieval of the stored photons, the optical collective excitation can be transferred to a long lived ground state before the re-emission of the light. This transfer freezes the evolution of the atomic dipoles, and the excitation is stored as a collective spin wave for a programmable time. The read out is achieved by transferring back the excitation to the excited state where the rephasing of the atomic dipoles takes place. If the two control fields are applied in a counterpropagating way, the photon is re-emitted backward. In that case, it has been shown that the re-absorption of the light can be suppressed thanks to a

collective quantum interference. In that configuration, the theoretical storage and retrieval efficiency, assuming that the decoherence in the long lived ground state is negligible and a perfect transfer, is given by [59]:

$$\eta_{AFC} \approx \left(1 - e^{-\tilde{d}}\right)^2 e^{-\frac{\tau}{F^2}} \quad (2)$$

where $\tilde{d} \approx d/F$ is the effective optical depth and $F = \Delta/\gamma_0$ is the finesse of the AFC. Note that this formula applied to a series of Gaussian peaks. In reference [61] a formula for Lorentzian line shapes is also given. In the equation above we see that η_{AFC} tends towards unity for sufficiently large d and F . Note that the interpretation of the efficiency formula for AFC is identical to the one for CRIB discussed above. The difference lies in the origin of the effective absorption depth \tilde{d} , which for CRIB is due to the applied broadening while for AFC it is due to the removal of atoms when creating the comb structure.

The number of temporal modes N_m that can be stored in an AFC quantum memory is proportional to the ratio between the storage time in the excited state $2\pi/\Delta$ and the duration of the stored photons, which is inversely proportional to the total AFC bandwidth $\Gamma = N_p\Delta$, where N_p is the total number of peaks in the AFC. Hence, we see that N_m is proportional to N_p and is independent of the optical depth. See [59] for a more detailed discussion on the multimode capacity.

6.1.3 Crystal properties

The optical depth of a given rare-earth doped crystal is proportional to the dopant concentration (for low concentrations) and to the transition dipole moment. Above a certain dopant concentration, however, adding more ions does not increase the optical depth any further [66], because ion-ion interactions lead to increased inhomogeneous broadening without changing the spectral density of absorbers at any given frequency. Furthermore the optical coherence time may decrease for higher concentrations [67], equally due to ion-ion interactions. Of course, the optical depth can also be increased by using longer crystals, or, more significantly, by using multi-pass configurations or optical cavities.

At low temperature ($T = 1-4$ K) the optical and hyperfine coherence times are limited by the spin-spin interaction of the ions between themselves, and with spins in the host crystal [42,43]. This has led to the use of crystal hosts with low nuclear spin density, most notably Y_2SiO_5 . The commonly used ions praseodymium (606 nm), europium (580 nm) and thulium (793 nm) have quenched electronic spins, resulting in weak spin interaction in general. For erbium (1530 nm) and neodymium (880 nm) doped crystals, however, one has to take the (much larger) electronic spins of Er and Nd into account, which will interact both with nuclear spins in the host and among themselves. Nevertheless, optical coherence times of a few ms have been demonstrated for Er-doped [68] and Eu-doped Y_2SiO_5 [66] (hundreds of microseconds for

Nd and Pr in the same host [68]), while for Pr: Y_2SiO_5 hyperfine spin coherence times as long as 1 s have been reported [44,46].

In order to perform the spectral shaping of the inhomogeneous absorption profile, which is necessary for both CRIB and AFC, one uses optical pumping [69–72]. The optically pumped ions are stored in a ground state, normally a spin level with a long population lifetime. Both the CRIB and AFC protocols also use another spin-level for storing the excitation on long time scales ($>10 \mu s$) [50–52,59,63]. In the preparation of the memory this level must be emptied of population, also via optical pumping. Thus, the material must have at least 3 spin levels for implementation of the complete schemes. In materials with only 2 spin levels one uses a level for population storage in the spectral shaping process, and the light is only stored in the optically excited state.

6.1.4 Experimental state of the art

The first proof of principle demonstration of the CRIB scheme with bright coherent states was realized in a europium doped solid [53]. The europium ions doped in the solid state matrix have an optical transition at 580 nm, and a level structure with three hyperfine states in the ground and excited states. The authors used optical pumping techniques to create a narrow absorption peak with a width of 25 kHz, within a 3 MHz wide transparency window. The absorption of the peak was approximately 40%. This peak was then broadened with a gradient of electric field implemented with four electrodes in a quadrupole configuration, thanks to the linear Stark effect. An incoming optical pulse of 1 μs was partly absorbed by the broadened spectral feature. To read-out the memory the polarity of the electric field was reversed after a time τ . After an additional delay τ , two-level Stark echoes were observed, with a decay time of about 20 μs . In another experiment, the same authors stored and recalled a train of 4 pulses [55]. They also showed that the phase information of the input pulses was preserved during the storage. In these experiments, only a very small part of the incident pulses were re-emitted in the Stark echo (between 10^{-5} and 10^{-6}). This low efficiency can be partly explained by the small absorption of the broadened peak (about 1%). In a more recent experiment, the same group demonstrated a greatly improved storage and retrieval efficiency of 15% using a praseodymium doped crystal, which features an optical transition with larger oscillator strength and consequently larger absorption [56]. Using a longer crystal they could achieve an efficiency as high as 45%. Very recently, a CRIB experiment has been demonstrated at the single photon level, using an erbium doped crystal absorbing at the telecommunication wavelength of 1536 nm [58].

Storage schemes combining off-resonant Raman interaction and photon-echo rephasing mechanisms have been proposed [73–75]. The experiments reported in [74,76] use a Raman interaction to transfer the optical input

Fig. 2. Phase preservation during the storage of a time-bin qubit by an atomic frequency comb [60]. Time-bin qubits with different phases Φ , are stored and analyzed using the light-matter interface. The analysis is performed by projecting the time-bin qubit on a fixed superposition basis, which here is achieved by two partial read-outs (see text for details). The inset shows the histogram of arrival times, where there is constructive interference for $\Phi = 2\pi$ and destructive interference for $\Phi = \pi$ in the middle time bin. For this particular interference fringe, a raw visibility of 82% and a visibility of 95% when subtracting detector dark counts are obtained. Figure from reference [60].

pulse onto a spin excitation. The spin transition is artificially broadened by an external magnetic field gradient, which allows rephasing of the spin coherence using the CRIB scheme. These experiments were realized in atomic vapours of Rb and in [76] an efficiency of 41% was reached. Moreover, it was shown that using this approach multiple pulses could be stored and later retrieved in any time order.

Phase preservation properties of photon echo techniques have also been investigated for the storage of multiple temporal modes using conventional photon echoes in Er doped LiNbO₃ [29,77]. This realizes a (relatively low-efficiency) memory in the classical regime. However, the results concerning the phase coherence generalize to the case of CRIB memories. The phase coherence of the memories was also studied performing an interference experiment between two spatially separated crystals [29]. The results showed very good visibility (of order 90%), which suggests that very high fidelities should be achievable with CRIB and AFC based memories in the same system. An interesting feature of these results is that the decoherence only affects the efficiency of the memory, but not its fidelity [29] (as long as background fluorescence is negligible). This is because atoms that are decohered simply do not efficiently contribute to the collective interference that produces the echo. The same principle also applies to CRIB and AFC.

The first proof of principle demonstration of the AFC protocol has been realized with a neodymium doped crystal (Nd:YVO₄) [60]. This experiment was the first demonstration of a solid light matter interface at the single photon level. The authors demonstrated the coherent and reversible mapping of weak light fields with less than one photon per pulse on average onto the ensemble of neodymium ions. This experiment showed that the quantum coherence of the incident weak light field was almost perfectly conserved during the storage, as demonstrated by performing an interference experiment with a stored time-bin qubit (see Fig. 2). Finally, they also demonstrated experimentally that the interface makes it possible

to store light in multiple temporal modes (4 modes). The storage and retrieval efficiency was low (about 0.5%) in this experiment, mainly limited by the imperfect preparation of the atomic frequency comb due to the difficulty to perform good optical pumping in Nd:YVO₄. In a more recent experiment, [61] demonstrated improved performance in terms of efficiency (9%) using a thulium doped YAG crystal, also at the single photon level. The efficiency could be further improved (to 17%) by optimization of the creation of the AFC, particularly by optimizing the shape of the teeth in the AFC [78]. The efficiency has been further improved in reference [62], in the bright pulse regime, reaching 34% in a Pr-doped Y₂SiO₅ crystal. In the weak pulse regime (average photon number <1), a storage efficiency of 25% was achieved [79]. This improvement was possible due to the ability to make narrow (100–200 kHz) peaks with high absorption depth ($d \sim 10$). The multi-mode capacity has also been increased by almost one order of magnitude compared to [60] in a Nd-doped Y₂SiO₅ crystal, where up to 64 modes were stored for 1.5 μ s [80].

In the AFC experiments cited above, only the first part of the proposed AFC protocol was demonstrated (i.e. the coherent mapping onto collective excitation at the optical transition and collective re-emission at a predetermined time). Hence these experiments did not allow for on demand-read out. Very recently, a proof of principle demonstration of the full AFC protocol including the transfer to a long lived ground state has been demonstrated in a praseodymium doped Y₂SiO₅ crystal [63]. True on-demand storage up to 20 μ s was achieved, limited by inhomogeneous spin dephasing. Spin echo techniques should allow to extend the storage time up to the spin coherence time (about 1 s) [46], even at the single excitation regime.

6.1.5 Performances

We now evaluate the expected performances of quantum storage in rare-earth doped solids with respect to the parameters proposed in the introduction.

Fidelity: Very high fidelities have been shown possible since the dominant decoherence processes affect the recall efficiency, but not the fidelity of the output state. This is a virtue of ensemble-based quantum memories. Experiments at the single photon level has shown conditional fidelities up to 95%.

Efficiency: In theory efficiencies up to 100% are possible with the CRIB and AFC protocols. In practice, the maximal efficiency reached so far is 45% for the CRIB protocol, and 34% for the AFC protocol, both in Pr-doped Y_2SiO_5 crystals. The challenge is to design systems with sufficiently high absorption. Another promising route towards higher efficiencies is the use of multi-pass arrangements or cavity enhanced light-matter interactions.

Storage time: Rare-earth doped solids usually feature optical transitions homogeneous linewidths of order of 1–10 kHz. Optical coherence times up to several ms have even been observed in certain rare-earth doped materials (see above). However, the storage time in the excited state is mostly limited by the width of the absorption peak γ_0 . While the theoretical ultimate limit for the width of absorption peak is given by the homogeneous linewidth, in practice the narrowest peak realized so far are of order of tens to hundreds of kHz. This leads to storage times of tens of microseconds. Significantly longer storage times can be achieved if the excitation is transferred to a long lived ground state. In particular Pr doped solids have extremely long spin coherence times. Even longer spin coherence time are expected for Eu doped solids [81]. Long storage times should thus be possible.

Bandwidth: Bandwidths up to several hundreds of MHz are realistic using the atomic frequency comb protocol. The challenge is thus to find systems with sufficiently high initial absorption to achieve acceptable efficiencies. The limitation in bandwidth will in general depend on the spacing between hyperfine transitions, either in the excited or ground state. Excitation of several levels will cause quantum beat phenomena in the recall efficiency.

Multiple-photon and multiple-mode storage capacity: In principle, large numbers of photons could be stored in the same memory. Trains of wave packets can be stored. The AFC protocol is particularly promising for that aspect, since the number of temporal modes that can be stored does not depend on the available optical depth. In addition there is potential for frequency multiplexing. Limits are imposed by the storage time and the frequency bandwidth of the material. In particular, the number of modes that can be stored with the AFC protocol is proportional to the number of peaks in the AFC.

Wavelength: Rare-earth doped solids optical transitions cover a wide range of wavelengths, from 580 nm (Eu) to 1530 nm (Er). It should be noted that there is considerable flexibility concerning the operating wavelength of the photon memory in quantum repeater protocols involving non-degenerate sources of entangled photon pairs, since then photons at one wavelength can be stored in the memory, while photons at another wavelength can be sent into optical fibers. Some efficient quantum repeaters

proposals however require quantum storage at telecommunication wavelengths. Erbium doped solids is the only proposed system that meets the requirements to implement a quantum memory at this wavelengths.

Read-out: For the CRIB scheme, the read-out delay for a single stored photon can be chosen at will by controlling the electric field that causes the Stark shifts used in CRIB. For the storage of multiple temporal modes, pulses stored at different times will be re-emitted at different times, thus allowing to distinguish between the modes. The order of the pulse sequence is however reversed during the storage. For the AFC scheme, the storage time in the excited state is pre-determined by the comb structure. On demand-read out can be achieved by a reversible transfer of the stored excitations to ground state level. Contrary to the CRIB scheme, the order of the pulse sequence is preserved with the AFC scheme.

Complexity: The proposed implementations uses standard lasers and fiber-optic components. The lasers are frequency stabilized to a reference for increased coherence length, which is important when shaping the absorption profile via optical pumping. The experiments also require a cryostat, operating temperatures being in the region 1–4 K.

6.2 NV centers in diamond (Stuttgart)

Defect centers in diamond share many similarities with the above mentioned rare earth system. Diamond defects typically comprise single or few impurity atoms in a diamond host with allowed optical transitions with absorption wavelength ranging from the UV to the infrared. Those defects may be electron paramagnetic such that one can use the superior relaxation and decoherence properties of electron and nuclear spins for information storage, retrieval and processing. In contrast to rare earth systems up to now mainly defects have been studied in the context of quantum information processing that do show strongly allowed optical transitions (absorption cross section: 10^{-17} cm^2 at $T = 300 \text{ K}$) such that single color centers can be observed. The popularity diamond defects have gained in quantum information over the past years is based on two aspects: on the one hand color centers in diamond usually are point defects deep within the bandgap of diamond which results in narrow and stable room temperature optical emission and excitation lines. In most cases excitation and emission without lattice phonons being involved is visible even at room temperature. On the other hand the stiff and diamagnetic diamond lattice eventually leads to very long electron and nuclear spin dephasing times, which for example can reach ms for electron spins at $T = 300 \text{ K}$. The currently most studied defect center in diamond is the nitrogen vacancy (NV) defect (see Fig. 3).

Due to the fact that it is an electron paramagnetic system, the NV does show a set of paramagnetic electronic and hyperfine split ground and excited state levels. It thus allows for the observation of photon-spin coupling used in e.g. lambda-type optical transitions with the

Fig. 3. In (a) a schematic picture of the NV-center embedded in the diamond lattice is shown. (b) Sketches the NVs levels scheme with its possible microwave transitions and hyperfine structure as an inlay.

potential to use CRISP and AFC type of techniques for storage. Long term storage can be realized by electron and nuclear sub spin levels with very long (ms-s) coherence times. The NV center has a strongly allowed optical transition with a corresponding optical excitation and emission linewidth of around 10 MHz at low temperature. This enables strong defect cavity coupling to enhance the spin photon interface [82]. The project started with exploring the fundamental applicability of the NV center as a quantum storage element. Basically two lines of research were explored namely an ensemble based approach for memory based on EIT-like two-photon resonance. Secondly coupling of single photon states to single NV centers which requires efficient (strong) coupling to cavities is explored. An important requirement prior to memory application is a detailed understanding of the involved energy levels as well as the excitation dynamics and photon properties of the NV center. Figure 3 shows the energy levels of the defect important for photon absorption and emission as well as for electron spin physics. The optical excitation path from the electron spin triplet ground state to the excited state orbital doublet allows for electron spin state conserving as well as spin flip transitions. If a transition is of lambda type (spin flip transition) or not can be determined by an external control parameter, e.g. transition wavelength or an external electric field. The existence of lambda transitions has been proven in electromagnetic induced transparency type of experiments [83]. These experiments also demonstrate that optical excitation can be used to generate long lived ground state spin coherence, an important prerequisite for quantum mem-

Fig. 4. Second-order fluorescence intensity autocorrelation function for the NV center at low temperature under resonant excitation of $m_s = 0$ spin state. The Rabi frequency of the excitation laser was varied for different curves and equals to 0.44, 0.59, 0.67, and 1.00 GHz (increase from bottom to top).

ory applications. A slightly different but key observation connected to quantum repeater application as well as light source of linear optical quantum information processing is the fact that single NV defects do emit transform limited photons [84] (see Fig. 4). To enhance spin-photon coupling single defect centers have been coupled to plasmonic structures [85]. Besides mere storage of photons via spin state coherence, single defects in diamond also do possess the capability to process the information stored. This particularly useful property allows for e.g. entanglement purification in quantum repeater applications. Information processing uses ^{13}C or nitrogen nuclei coupled to the electron spin of the NV center. Coherence swapping between electron and nuclear spins, entanglement among spins and basic quantum gates have been demonstrated [86]. It has been estimated that 5 qubits are sufficient for a full quantum repeater functionality [87]. This proposed spin cluster comprises one electron spin for spin-photon interaction and 4 nuclear spins for storage and entanglement pumping. First experiments on clusters of such size have been demonstrated in the meantime [88]. Spin-photon entanglement has also recently been achieved.

Fidelity: Fidelities for single or multiple photon storage in defect centers have not been determined up to now. However, subparts of the memory have been investigated towards their fidelity of state storage. This is particularly true for the spin memory part, i.e. swapping of coherences between electron and nuclear spin. Here fidelities as defined in the introductory part of this paper of up to 85% have been achieved [89].

Storage time: Storage time of the defect center memory is limited by the NV center T_1 or for arbitrary state storage T_2 . In purified crystals T_2 for the electron spin has been measured to be ms. Ultimately information will be stored in nuclear spins with dephasing times on the order of tens of ms.

Bandwidth: Here the NV center can be used in a similar way than the rare earth systems in CRISP and AFC methods. A crucial part of these schemes is the

possibility to create and reverse inhomogeneous broadening. In the case of the NV center this can be done by inverting a magnetic field or more importantly by the recently demonstrated Stark-shift frequency tuning [90] allowing frequency multiplexing.

Wavelength: The NV center emission wavelength is centered around 700 nm and hence not in the telecommunication range. Nevertheless free space quantum communication was demonstrated with NV defects (637 nm) [91]. Emission at longer wavelength is achieved with different defect centers. Other defects in diamond like NE8 (emission wavelength 800 nm) might be more suitable for fiber-based systems [92]. In addition to this defect, 90% of oscillator strength is concentrated in zero-phonon transition of NE8 defect (compared with 10% for NV defect). Currently however, little is known about the spin states of this defect and their coherence properties.

Complexity: For storage of single photons in defect center cavity systems first steps have been taken. As mentioned in the introductory part strong coupling between single defect in diamond and the whispering gallery mode of silica micro resonator was shown. The development of other cavity system is in its beginnings. However progress was reported on NV center photonic band gap cavity coupling as well as NV center-plasmon coupling. Owing to the low electron phonon coupling diamond-based photonic memory can be operated at relatively high temperatures (up to 20 K).

6.3 Semiconductor nanotechnology (Toshiba/Bristol)

Semiconductor quantum dots could potentially be used to produce fast and efficient quantum memories to be utilised in future quantum networks or as quantum repeaters. Semiconductor based systems are compact, robust and easy to integrate with existing technology. The energy structure of the quantum dots can be engineered by manipulating the material, size, and strain. Furthermore, the well established techniques to produce high-Q cavities in semiconductor material makes it possible to achieve a high efficiency [93].

In our approach we are using a single InAs quantum dot embedded in GaAs to store and deterministically re-emit a single-photon state. The operation of the device as described in [94] is illustrated in Figure 5a. The quantum dot is placed in the intrinsic region of a diode structure and biased so that the heavy-hole tunnelling rate is higher than the radiative recombination rate. On the negative side of the diode an AlGaAs barrier prevents the electron from leaving the dot. The polarisation of an incoming circularly polarised photon is transcribed to a pure spin state of an exciton confined in the quantum dot. The hole immediately tunnels out while the electron remains, thus storing the spin state. At a later time a pair of heavy-holes is returned by applying an ac voltage pulse. The positively charged exciton that is formed subsequently recombines, recreating a photon with a polarisation defined by the spin-state of the stored electron. Figure 5b shows the delayed emission for storage times up to 1 μ s. The storage

Fig. 5. (a) Schematic diagram of the quantum dot band structure and the memory scheme for pure spin storage. Write mode: a circularly polarised photon is absorbed and creates an exciton, the device is biased to remove holes (open circles), the polarisation is stored in the spin-state of the confined electron (filled circles). Read mode: the device is biased to return a pair of holes, radiative recombination results in a photon with a polarisation dictated by the stored electron's spin state. (b) Time-resolved emission from the quantum dot for readout delay times between 0.2 and 1 μ s (as labeled).

time is limited by the voltage pulse pattern generator and not the device, no decrease (other than statistical fluctuations) in the readout intensity can be observed on this time scale.

Fidelity: The fidelity for the pure spin storage described above was $80 \pm 10\%$ and constant within the delay times. This is consistent with the spin relaxation time for similar spin memories which has been shown to be in the ms range [95]. Figure 6a shows the spectrum of the delayed emission after 1 μ s storage of a right-hand circularly polarised photon. The spectrum is measured both in the right- (R) and left-hand (L) polarisation basis to illustrate the high fidelity of the readout. Figure 6b shows the same measurement for storage of a left-hand circularly polarised photon.

In order to store a superposition state both the electron and hole must be retained (as their spin states are entangled), this can be done in separate reservoirs. In this case the fidelity is limited by the hyperfine interaction between the stored electron and the nuclei of the atoms which form the quantum dot (and those in the material surrounding the dot, depending on the extent of the electron's wavefunction). For the hole, which has a p -like orbital with almost no overlap with the nuclei, the hyperfine

Fig. 6. (a) and (b) The spectrum of the delayed emission after $1 \mu\text{s}$ storage of a right- and left-hand circularly polarised photon respectively. The spectrum is measured in the right- (R) and left-hand (L) polarisation basis. (c) Coherent time-evolution of the fidelity, f^+ , for the exciton-photon state with the symmetric Bell state. Bands denote measurement errors dominated by Poissonian counting noise.

coupling is very small. The nuclear spins give rise to a randomly fluctuating magnetic field which causes the electron spin to pick up a random phase and thus the electron spin-coherence decays with time. For III-V semiconductor material (such as the InAs-GaAs system discussed here) the decoherence time can be expected to be of the order of 10 ns.

To demonstrate coherent storage we have created an entangled exciton-photon state in a quantum dot, and observed the coherent evolution of the spin-superposed state in a dot for up to 2 ns, with a single qubit fidelity of up to 94% [96]. The entangled exciton-photon state was prepared through the radiative decay of a biexciton in a single quantum dot. Polarisation selection rules dictate that radiative decay will project the system into the entangled exciton-photon state $|\Psi\rangle \propto (|H_{XX}X_H\rangle + e^{iS\tau/\hbar}|V_{XX}X_V\rangle)$ where H_{XX} and V_{XX} are the vertically and horizontally polarised photon states and X_H and X_V are the exciton spin states coupling to the horizontally and vertically polarised photons respectively. S is the spin splitting of the stored exciton state. Figure 6c shows the measured fidelity, f^+ , of the exciton-photon state to the symmetric Bell state $|\Psi^+\rangle = (|H_{XX}X_H\rangle + |V_{XX}X_V\rangle)/\sqrt{2}$, as a function of the storage time. Strong oscillations are observed as a function of the storage time with a period of h/S . The increasing phase acquired by the stationary qubit causes the final entangled photon pair state to pe-

riodically overlap with the symmetric Bell state. No loss of coherence is resolved for the longest recorded storage time of 2 ns which is limited by the radiative lifetime of the exciton. We stress that when the qubit pair fidelity is low, entanglement still exists in the system but with high fidelity to other Bell states.

Although the spin dephasing time is in the 10 ns range for III-V semiconductors, where the naturally occurring isotopes of the constituent materials all have non-zero nuclear spin [97], the nuclear field fluctuates on a much slower time scale, on the order of $100 \mu\text{s}$. This means that a spin echo technique could be employed to extend the coherence time to this range [98]. Another alternative is to polarise the nuclear spins by optical pumping to keep the nuclear field fixed in time. Thereby any uncertainty in the phase evolution of the electron spin would be removed [99,100]. It should also be mentioned that other material systems exist where most of the nuclei are zero spin isotopes. An example of such a material system is CdSe QDs embedded in ZnSe [101].

Efficiency: For this memory scheme the input and output coupling efficiency for the photon to dot-confined exciton are similar and they predominantly determine the efficiency of the memory as a whole. Strong coupling between optical and exciton modes has been demonstrated by integrating quantum dots into optical cavities. To achieve strong coupling, the exciton-photon coupling parameter g must meet the criteria: $g^2 > (\gamma_c - \gamma_x)^2/16$ [102], where γ_c and γ_x are the full width at half maxima of the cavity and exciton modes respectively; thus to reach the strong coupling limit it is necessary to fabricate cavities with very high quality factors (Q) to make the width of the cavity mode comparable to the exciton's mode. Pillar microcavities formed by etching through distributed Bragg reflectors, two-dimensional photonic crystals and microdisks have all been used to show strong exciton-photon coupling [102–104]. Such systems should be capable of providing near deterministic single photon absorption and emission which is required for a useful quantum memory. Our best output coupling efficiency for microcavities is 20%, a similar input coupling efficiency should in principle be achievable. To our knowledge the best quantum efficiency achieved for exciton-cavity mode coupling between excitons in quantum dots and a microcavity is 97% [105]. We have been working to extend strong coupling schemes to show the possibility of a deterministic photon-spin quantum interface using charged dots [106–108]. A singly charged quantum dot, when spin polarised will interact differently to different circular polarisation states of light due to Pauli blocking. When this occurs in a strongly coupled QD-cavity system the spin state of the charged dot induces giant circular birefringence and giant optical Faraday rotation. This enables non-demolition measurement of single spins, entanglement between a spin and a single photon and the development of various photon-spin, photon-photon and spin-spin entangling gates. As a result this could provide an efficient read-in, read-out quantum memory and quantum relay. As yet no experimental demonstration has been reported.

Storage time: The limiting factor here will be the decoherence time of the electron spin stored in the quantum dot (which could be $> 100 \mu\text{s}$).

Bandwidth: The bandwidth will be limited by the speed at which the gates controlling the device can be operated, hole tunnelling times, and the exciton's radiative lifetime. The latter is usually around 1 ns for an isolated quantum dot but can be greatly reduced for a quantum dot in a cavity by the Purcell effect. Operation at 1 GHz has been demonstrated for single photon emission from quantum dots in diodes [109].

Multiple-photon and multiple-mode storage capacity: Frequency multiplexing is possible with multiple dots of different size. Multiple photon storage in the single quantum dot scheme is not likely.

Wavelength: Initial experiments exploit the benefits of silicon detectors and work in the near-IR, around 900 nm. We have developed some quantum dot based devices at telecom wavelengths [110]. In principle the emission wavelength can be tuned arbitrarily by using appropriate materials and manipulating the quantum dot size and strain.

Complexity: Production of the quantum memories only involves standard semiconductor fabrication techniques. The operation of the quantum memory however requires liquid helium temperatures. As the temperature is increased confinement of the electron in the dot reduces as thermal activation becomes possible. This limits operation to < 50 K for typical InAs quantum dots which are optically active at 900 nm. Confinement can be increased to allow higher temperature operation by altering the growth of the dots or changing the dot and/or barrier materials.

In summary, we have developed a spin memory based on semiconductor quantum dots. This was done by creating devices which provide preferential tunnelling of holes to allow a spin encoded exciton to be decomposed and the pure spin state stored by the electron confined in the dot. With this device we have demonstrated storage of pure spin states for 1 μs with a fidelity of 80%. Furthermore, we have demonstrated that the coherence of a photon entangled with a stored exciton does not decay within the exciton radiative lifetime. We also present possible routes to improve a semiconductor quantum memory.

6.4 Single optically trapped ^{87}Rb atoms (LMU Munich)

Brief description of approach and potential applications: This approach aims at the generation of entanglement between remote atomic quantum memories useful for future applications in long-distance quantum communication like quantum networks or the quantum repeater [2]. Such applications can be realized on basis of our recently demonstrated entanglement between a single optically trapped ^{87}Rb atom and a single emitted photon [32,116] by applying robust probabilistic quantum gates like entanglement swapping [111], based on

the quantum interference of photon pairs on a beam splitter [33,113,119]. The memory qubit is stored in the Zeeman sub-levels $m_F = \pm 1$ of the $5^2\text{S}_{1/2}$, $F = 1$ hyperfine ground level of a single ^{87}Rb atom (localized in an optical dipole trap [112]), whereas the photonic communication qubit is encoded in the polarization state of a single photon. Transfer of quantum information from the photon onto the quantum memory can be realized for example by quantum teleportation or similarly by remote state preparation [35]. Efficient readout with high fidelity can be performed in two ways: the memory qubit can be determined by a destructive spin measurement using a fluorescence-based shelving technique [32] or by state-selective laser ionization and subsequent detection of the charged ionization fragments. Both techniques are investigated by our group [118]. Alternatively, stored quantum information can be coherently transferred back onto a photonic qubit by optically exciting the atom on a suitable dipole transition, leading to the emission of a single photon in the same spin state as the atom. The latter technique was recently demonstrated for the first time by Wilk et al., where a single ^{87}Rb atom emits a single photon into the well defined spatial mode of an high-Q optical cavity [114,115].

For future applications of long-distance quantum communication like quantum networks, the quantum repeater [2], or quantum teleportation between distant matter qubits it is mandatory to achieve entanglement between separated quantum processors. In order to entangle two ^{87}Rb atoms at remote locations, we intend to apply the entanglement swapping protocol [111]. For this purpose, both atoms are entangled in a first step via spontaneous Raman scattering with a single photon [32] (see Fig. 7a). Each of the two photons is collected via a large numerical aperture objective, coupled into a single mode optical fiber, and guided to an intermediate location. There the photons are overlapped on a 50:50 beam-splitter (BS). In case the photons are detected in coincidence in both output ports of the BS the remaining atom-atom pair is projected onto the maximally entangled spin-singlet state (see Fig. 7b). First successful experimental steps into this direction – namely the demonstration of entanglement [33,119] and quantum teleportation [34] between single-ion quantum bits at a distance of 1 m – were reported recently by Chris Monroe's group.

In this contribution we focus on figures of merit which are particularly important for the generation of entangled ^{87}Rb atoms connected via optical fiber links of several 100 m length.

Efficiency: The overall success probability of the entanglement swapping protocol is given by

$$P_{At-At} = \frac{1}{4}(p\eta)^2 e^{-\alpha(L_1+L_2)}, \quad (3)$$

where p denotes the overall collection and coupling efficiency into the optical fiber, η the quantum efficiency of the single photon detectors, and $e^{-\alpha(L_1+L_2)}$ the photon attenuation in the optical fiber links with communication distances L_1 and L_2 and absorption α . The factor 4 accounts for the fact that only one out of four photonic

Fig. 7. (a) Preparation of atom-photon entanglement in ^{87}Rb via spontaneous Raman scattering. The atoms are excited first with short optical laser pulses to the $5^2\text{P}_{3/2}$, $F' = 0$ hyperfine level. In the following spontaneous emission process they decay to the ground states with the magnetic quantum numbers $m_F = -1, 0$, or $+1$ by emitting a σ^+ , π , or σ^- -polarized photon, respectively. Provided these decay channels are indistinguishable in all other degrees of freedom and the π -decay is filtered out spatially a maximally entangled state is formed between the photonic qubit $\{|\sigma^+\rangle, |\sigma^-\rangle\}$ and the atomic spin-qubit $\{|m_F = -1\rangle, |m_F = 1\rangle\}$. (b) Preparation of a pair of entangled atoms from two entangled atom-photon pairs via entanglement swapping. The photons interfere on a 50:50 beam-splitter (BS). A coincident detection of the photons in both output ports projects the atoms onto an entangled state.

Bell-states is detected. Typically $p\eta \approx 10^{-3}$, provided the photon attenuation is neglected. In practice we expect to achieve an overall success probability of 2×10^{-7} for the entanglement swapping process [117] via a 300 m optical fiber link. This value could be enhanced by the use of improved detection optics [121,122] or optical cavities [114,115], thereby allowing entanglement swapping at a higher rate.

Fidelity: When talking about fidelities (accuracies) of this scheme we distinguish in general three cases. (i) The fidelity F_{At-Ph} we are able to generate an entangled atom-photon state, (ii) the accuracy a_{det} to read out the atomic spin-state via a projective measurement, and (iii) the fidelity F_{At-At} to generate a pair of entangled atoms at remote locations via entanglement swapping. In theory atom-photon entanglement fidelities F_{At-Ph} of up to 100% are possible. However in practice due to errors in the preparation of the excited atomic state $5^2\text{P}_{3/2}$, $F' = 0$ the best achievable fidelity is limited to $F_{At-Ph} = 99.6\%$. To estimate now the expected atom-atom entanglement fidelity F_{At-At} after one photon has traveled e.g. an optical fiber link of 300 m length, one has to account for additional errors which are mainly due to polarization imperfections in the optical fiber [116], dephasing of the entangled atom-photon state (caused by fluctuating magnetic fields [116]), and spatio-temporal mismatch in the two-photon interference. In addition, dark counts in the single photon detectors of the Bell-state analyzer will further reduce the achievable fidelity. Applying a careful error analysis we estimate a fidelity of $F_{At-At} = 94.4\%$ to generate an entangled pair of atoms [117]. Here we emphasize that this value yet does not include the limited accuracy $a_{det} = 95\%$ to distinguish orthogonal atomic spin states via fluorescence-based shelving. Including this additional experimental error we finally estimate an observable entanglement fidelity of $F_{At-At}^* = 81\%$ [117].

Storage time: If we scale this scenario to larger distances (several km), dephasing of the atomic spin due to fluctuating magnetic fields – respectively the resulting dephasing of the entangled atom-photon interface –

will reduce the reachable atom-atom entanglement fidelity F_{At-At} . By implementing an active magnetic field stabilization and without application of any magnetic guiding field we demonstrated transverse and longitudinal spin-dephasing times of $T_2^* = 75 \dots 150 \mu\text{s}$ and $T_1 \geq 0.5 \text{ ms}$, respectively, limited mainly by the residual state-dependence of the optical trapping potential and the thermal energy of the trapped atom [116]. This value is in good agreement with state-of-the-art coherence times of Zeeman qubits stored in single trapped ions. In order to achieve storage times up to several seconds one could use e.g. magnetic-field-independent hyperfine qubits and encode the photonic qubit in the frequency of a single photon [33], thereby enabling e.g. quantum teleportation between matter qubits [34] at distances of several km. Nevertheless, with the already demonstrated coherence time of $T_2^* = 75 \dots 150 \mu\text{s}$ for our Zeeman qubit an entanglement swapping experiment between two atoms connected via 300 m optical fiber can be performed in the near future.

Bandwidth: The Fourier-limited bandwidth of our single atom quantum memory is determined by the natural linewidth (6 MHz) of the dipole transition $5^2\text{S}_{1/2} \rightarrow 5^2\text{P}_{3/2}$ in ^{87}Rb . This value assures a rather uncritical implementation of the entanglement swapping protocol since the interfering photon wave packets have an overall spatial extension of several meter. In addition the temporal shape of the photons could be tuned e.g. via controlled variation of the spontaneous Raman scattering process [120] while maintaining the possibility to generate a highly entangled atom-photon interface.

Wavelength: The wavelength λ of the photonic qubit is determined by the dipole transition $5^2\text{S}_{1/2} \rightarrow 5^2\text{P}_{3/2}$ in ^{87}Rb . At $\lambda = 780 \text{ nm}$ the damping in optical fibers is $\approx 5 \dots 6 \text{ dB/km}$. In combination with our single photon collection efficiency of $p = 4 \dots 5 \times 10^{-3}$ our current experimental implementation (two single atom traps) already allows the distribution of quantum information and entanglement between nodes of a primitive quantum network at a distance of 1 km.

6.5 Room temperature alkali gases with long spin polarization life time (Copenhagen)

Brief description of approach and potential applications: Room temperature atomic gases allow for the use of various approaches towards a quantum memory, such as Raman transitions [126] and electromagnetically induced transparency [19]. The approach we have been pursuing is based on off-resonant interaction followed by a measurement on light and a successive feedback onto the atoms. This approach is particularly suitable for room temperature atomic ensembles because it can achieve a high fidelity for the so-called symmetric atomic spatial mode, that is the mode in which every atom contributes in the same way irrespectively of its position in the cell. For Raman and EIT based memories, a high fidelity can be achieved only for asymmetric atomic modes. The information is stored in a spin wave that is not distributed evenly over the ensemble so that atoms in the front part of the cell contribute much more to the memory than the atoms in the rear part of the cell [127]. Obviously such a memory can only have a life time that is limited by atomic motion, which is practically limited to a few tens of microseconds.

In this project we use large ensembles of up to 10^{12} cesium atoms that are kept in glass cells which are coated from the inside with a material preventing collisional decoherence. Our approach uses a quantum non-demolition (QND) type off-resonant interaction combined with quantum feedback. This has proven to work very well for the generation of deterministic entanglement of two distant objects [125], for writing a coherent state of light into a quantum memory [20], and for teleportation of a quantum state of light onto an atomic memory [129]. Potential applications include distant teleportation of atomic states and high fidelity quantum memories for light. Since high fidelity teleportation is the essential ingredient of a quantum repeater this approach is also relevant for this application.

Fidelity: The maximum obtainable unconditional fidelity of the light-to-atoms storage increases with the resonant optical depth which for a detuning larger than Doppler width is equal to the optical depth for atoms at rest. An optical depth of the order of 50 has been realized in experiments with cesium atoms in a 25 mm long cell at a temperature close to room temperature. Fidelities of storage and teleportation up to 70% have been demonstrated experimentally for weak coherent states. For atoms initially prepared in a squeezed state the fidelity can be even higher. Such initial spin squeezing of the atoms can be achieved either by a quantum nondemolition measurement, or by preparing each atom in a coherent superposition of magnetic sublevels of the ground state. With the latter method a spin squeezing of ≈ 3 dB has been demonstrated [24].

An alternative approach to light-to-atoms state transfer is via light-to-atoms teleportation [129]. This approach has shown a fidelity of $\approx 60\%$, compared to the theoretical maximum of 72%. Again, in order to improve the fidelity beyond this bound, initial squeezing should be employed,

but this time the light which generates the entanglement should be squeezed. With 6 dB of squeezing, which has been demonstrated experimentally in our laboratory, a fidelity exceeding 90% is possible.

The factors which reduce the experimentally observed fidelity below the theoretical maximum are losses of light and decoherence of atoms. Losses of light are mainly caused by reflections on the cell windows. While on the external windows' surfaces dielectric antireflection coatings can be applied easily, the internal surfaces are difficult to coat. However, it is clear that this purely technical limitation can be overcome. The atomic decoherence which is the most serious limitation to the fidelity is dominated by the decoherence caused by the driving optical field itself. At the moment this effect is responsible for the 10–15% reduction in the fidelity compared to the theoretical optimum.

Efficiency: So far our most successful quantum memory implementations involved demonstration of unconditional state transfer from light onto atoms. The unconditional character of the memory is due to the fact that the measurement on light is a homodyne measurement on a well defined spatial mode of light which can be performed with detectors with more than 98% quantum efficiency. The given fidelity is unconditional, and therefore by definition the efficiency is 100%, i.e. the process is deterministic.

Storage time: In our experiments the memory life time is defined as the time over which the fidelity drops below the classical benchmark value of 50%. Life times of up to 4 ms have been demonstrated experimentally [20]. Such a long quantum memory life time (the longest demonstrated so far for any kind of general quantum memory for light) has been made possible by using a special coating of the inside surface of the cells. With this coating atoms can withstand tens of thousands of collisions with the cell walls without losing their coherence properties.

Bandwidth: The biggest drawback of our approach is that as of now only very narrowband light modes can be stored. The protocol relies on atoms to traverse the coupling beam many times during the write- and read-out process, so that atom position effects average out. If vapour cells of a few cm^3 are used this limits the bandwidth to ≈ 1 kHz. In order to construct a photon-qubit memory using this approach, ways to design a memory which can handle a bandwidth of about 1 MHz or higher should be developed. This could be achieved with smaller cells, or with hollow fibers.

Multiple-photon and multiple-mode storage capacity: The memory can store continuous variable observables with up to a few hundred photons and therefore the dimensionality of the stored state is high. In principle, several temporal modes could be stored in the same memory using different atomic sublevels. Limits are imposed by the number of levels available.

Wavelength: The wavelength should be close to resonant frequencies of alkali atoms, i.e., 852 nm or 895 nm for Cs and 780 nm or 795 nm for Rb, to take two most popular examples. Those wavelengths are suitable for free space

propagation. In order to apply this memory approach to telecom wavelengths for long distance fiber communications, the same approach can be, in principle, generalized to other systems or dual-color sources of entangled light states could be used.

Read-out delay: The limit of the read-out delay time is set by the quantum memory life time, which is up to 4 ms at the moment.

Complexity: The implementation uses room temperature atoms and therefore is simple and scalable. As for all approaches that use a great number N_a of individual physical systems to enhance the coupling between light and matter, if fields are used to perform local operations on states stored within the memory they have to be controlled precisely to $1/\sqrt{N}$. Very good magnetic shielding and low noise lasers and detectors are required to avoid technical noise.

6.6 Cold trapped atomic ensembles (Copenhagen)

Brief description of approach and potential applications: To some degree this approach is an extension of the room temperature experiments with alkali atoms: an optically dense cloud (optical depth of ~ 15) of 10^5 cesium atoms is prepared in one of the magnetically insensitive clock-levels by first cooling the atoms in a magneto-optical trap and successively transferring them into a far off-resonant dipole trap, which is overlapped with one arm of a Mach-Zehnder interferometer [130]. By measuring the the state-dependent phase shift that the atoms induce on probe light in the interferometer a QND interaction between light and atoms can be realized with a shot-noise and projection-noise limited precision [25].

The advantage of using a dense ensemble of cold atoms is that the sample is much smaller, light can be focused tighter and the same strong coupling can be achieved with much less photons and much shorter pulses compared to room temperature ensembles. Additionally the spontaneous scattering channels are closed, so that for similar interaction strengths QND measurements are much less destructive compared to the room-temperature vapor cell setup.

Higher optical depth can be achieved with even colder or quantum degenerate atomic samples. Utilizing condensed samples containing 10^6 rubidium atoms stored in magnetic traps or optical dipole traps a considerable increase in coupling strength (optical depth of ~ 1000), albeit at the cost of higher system complexity, is anticipated [124]. The most promising applications for cold atom based systems are in entanglement enhanced sensing and metrology and in quantum repeaters.

Fidelity: Fidelities similar to those already obtained with atomic vapors can be expected.

Efficiency: Like in the vapor-cell experiment the efficiency of the approaches we use is 100%, i.e. the process is deterministic.

Storage time: Quantum memory life times up to tens of milliseconds can be expected with ultracold atoms and

T_2 times in this range are routinely observed for the collective coherence on the microwave clock transition. Recent investigations indicate that transversal motion of the atoms within the inhomogeneous probe beam [128] might reduce the life time of stored spin-waves, so that it might be necessary to employ an optical 3d-lattice instead of a simple linear dipole trap.

Bandwidth: Pulses of up to a few MHz bandwidth can be used. An upper limit is in principle given by the collective linewidth of the optical transition involved in the coupling scheme, so that for condensed samples also a bandwidth in the GHz range is possible.

Multiple-photon and multiple-mode storage capacity: Ensembles of 3d-trapped ultracold atoms are suitable for storage of multiple spatial modes. In principle, several temporal modes could be stored in the same memory using different atomic sublevels. Limits are imposed by the number of levels available and the level of control/compensation of external fields that cause decoherence between the different hyperfine states. For spatial multimode operation ensembles with a sample Fresnel number above 1 need to be used. To prevent mode-mixing by atomic motion, strong localization in an optical lattice is advantageous.

Wavelength: The wavelength requirements are identical to those of room-temperature atomic ensembles and determined by the atomic species used.

Read-out delay: As in the room-temperature atomic vapors the limit of the read-out delay time is set by the quantum memory life time.

Complexity: The complexity is comparatively high: the implementation uses ultracold atoms trapped in a dipole trap and requires a very low phase noise microwave source to perform LOCC operations on the stored quantum state, as explained in Section 6.5.

6.7 Raman memory in atomic gases and solids (Oxford)

Off-resonant Raman interactions provide a natural way to access long-lived material coherences optically, utilizing the strong light-matter coupling of an intermediate dipole transition, while avoiding fluorescent losses. Spontaneous Raman scattering has already been used to entangle separated atomic ensembles [131,132], which operation forms the basis of the DLCZ quantum repeater architecture [21]. Running the interaction in reverse offers the possibility to coherently store propagating photons as stationary excitations of a Raman coherence.

Our experiments have focussed on the manipulation of temporally short, broadband wavepackets. We implemented a Raman memory for sub-nanosecond pulses in cesium vapour, and we probed the optical phonon modes of diamond via ultrafast Stokes and anti-Stokes scattering. In both cases coupling over a wide spectral bandwidth is possible because the narrowband atomic states are dressed by the application of a bright, short control pulse, producing a broad virtual state that mediates the interaction.

Fig. 8. (a) A Raman memory. The signal is directed into the memory along with a bright write pulse and is stored. If the storage is partial, any unstored signal is transmitted through the memory. A subsequent read pulse extracts the stored excitation, which emerges along with the transmitted read pulse. (b) The Λ -level structure of the atoms in the memory. The atoms are prepared in the ground state $|1\rangle$ by optical pumping. The signal is tuned into two-photon resonance with the control field; both are detuned from the excited state $|2\rangle$. Absorption of a signal photon transfers an atom from $|1\rangle$ into the storage state $|3\rangle$ via Raman scattering stimulated by the control. Upon retrieval the interaction is reversed.

Fig. 9. Storage and retrieval of a sub-nanosecond signal pulse. (a) Solid line: transmission of incident signal field without the presence of control field – there is no storage and no retrieval. Dashed line: in the presence of control fields (not visible) we observe 30% storage and 50% retrieval, yielding a total memory efficiency of 15%. (b) Zoom of retrieved signal field showing the measured full width at half maximum (FWHM) temporal duration of 1 ns, limited by the detector response time. This shows that the bandwidth of the retrieved signal exceeds 1 GHz.

6.7.1 GHz optical memory in cesium vapour

Although Raman storage is well-known theoretically [126, 133–135], it has not previously been realized experimentally. Superficially it resembles EIT-based storage, except that the optical fields are detuned away from the excited state resonance (see part (b) of Fig. 8). Qualitatively, they operate on quite different principles: in EIT the strong dispersion associated with the quantum interference of two absorption pathways – direct or via the control field – is employed to bring a signal pulse to a halt inside an atomic ensemble. In a Raman memory the large detuning destroys this interference, and instead the signal is coherently absorbed into the virtual state created by the control pulse, with no reduction in group velocity.

In the experiment [136], a bright control pulse and an orthogonally polarized weak signal pulse, both of ~ 300 ps duration, are spatially and temporally overlapped and directed into a glass cell containing warm cesium vapour,

where around 30% of the signal field is converted into a *spin wave* – a stationary excitation of the ground state hyperfine coherence. 12.5 ns later, a second control pulse extracts the stored excitation with $\sim 50\%$ efficiency, which emerges as a retrieved signal pulse. Figure 9 shows a typical time-trace of the intensity of the transmitted signal field detected by a fast avalanche photodiode placed downstream from the cell, after removal of the transmitted control field by polarization and spectral filtering. It is clear from part (b) that the bandwidth of the retrieved signal field is at least 1 GHz, but this measurement is limited by the response time of the detector, which is 1 ns. Theoretically the Raman memory operates at the full bandwidth of the control pulse of around 1.5 GHz.

Decoherence of the spin wave over the short storage time shown here is negligible; recently we observed retrieval after $\sim 2 \mu\text{s}$, although some technical adjustments are required to test longer storage times. The efficiency of our memory is limited by the strength of the Raman coupling attainable, and by the quality of the overlap between the write control pulse and the incident signal. Appropriate pulse shaping (which may be technically challenging), and increasing the control pulse energy (which should not be), could raise the total efficiency to around 60% [133]. Phasematched retrieval in the backward direction allows efficiencies above 90% to be reached [137].

The memory performs reasonably well when evaluated against the criteria introduced in Section 4. The **fidelity** of the memory is (up to a possible unitary re-shaping of the retrieved pulse profile [138]) the same as the **efficiency**, which is $\sim 15\%$. As discussed above, much higher efficiencies are feasible. A proxy for the **conditional fidelity** is given by the visibility of interference between the retrieved pulse and an appropriately attenuated replica of the stored pulse. The short storage time of 12.5 ns makes this measurement relatively straightforward, and we obtained a visibility of $\sim 85\%$, after correcting for imperfections in the interferometer. Theory suggests further improvement may be possible if the Stark shift on the retrieved signal due to the strong control can be compensated.

The limiting **storage time** of the current memory is probably on the order of 100 μs ; a typical coherence time in warm atomic vapours set by the diffusion of atoms out of the interaction region [139]. Longer times are of course possible if the atoms can be confined, for example by the walls of the vapour cell, although special care should be taken that the optical fields address the full cell diameter, and that collisions of atoms with the cell wall do not dephase the Raman coherence. Coherence times in warm cesium vapour on the order of 10 ms have been achieved with such a set-up by the Copenhagen group [125], with only residual magnetic fields and Cs–Cs spin exchange preventing longer coherence times. Other possibilities for extending the memory lifetime include trapping the atoms in an optical lattice [140] or most appealing of all as dopants in a solid-state host (see the discussion of CRIB and AFC memories in Sect. 6.1).

The **bandwidth** of the current memory exceeds 1 GHz, which compares favourably with the clock rates of modern classical computers. Time bandwidth products of the order of 10^5 are feasible if the full storage time is exploited. The bandwidth is limited by the ground state hyperfine splitting of 9.2 GHz in cesium, since larger bandwidth pulses will address both control and signal transitions simultaneously (this is known as the impulsive regime in the Raman literature [141]). Other media with larger splittings, or appropriate selection rules, could allow the storage of shorter pulses; the diamond memory introduced in the next section is an example.

The **multimode capacity** is not generally large – it scales poorly with the density of the ensemble, as indeed does the capacity of EIT storage [142] – although off-axis beam geometries do allow for angular multiplexing [137,143,144]. Finally, the **wavelength** is tunable in principle, although the present memory is operated sufficiently close to resonance that significant wavelength variations away from 852 nm would rapidly erode the efficiency: the tunability is currently limited to a few GHz. Again, alternative media with sufficiently large Raman cross-sections – such as the diamond memory discussed below – can be operated far from resonance, where the Raman coupling varies slowly with frequency, allowing for near-arbitrary wavelength tunability.

Solid state memory in diamond: Diamond has a very large Raman cross-section. Although its bandgap lies in the ultraviolet, optical pulses will readily scatter from the ‘deformation potential’, producing correlated pairs of Stokes photons and optical phonons. These phonons are non-propagating vibrational excitations associated with the ‘ringing’ of the crystal basis. They survive for approximately 5 ps before decaying into pairs of short wavelength acoustic phonons – sound waves – due to high order anharmonic couplings in the diamond lattice. Although this lifetime is extremely short, the optical phonons are interesting because they are very energetic, with a Stokes shift of 1332 cm^{-1} (0.16 eV, or expressed as an optical wavelength, $7.5\ \mu\text{m}$). This is much larger than the energy scale associated with thermal fluctuations at room temperature, so these excitations are naturally isolated

from noise. Additionally, the large splitting allows Stokes photons to be spectrally distinguished from the control field used to initiate the interaction, even if their spectra span 10 s of nanometers. Therefore, ultrashort, femtosecond timescale pulses can be used to address the phonons: on such timescales the coherence time of the phonons appears long!

The optical phonons in bulk diamond represent a unique testbed for the ultrafast control of macroscopic coherence in solid state systems at room temperature. As an extension of previous work [1,145] in atomic vapours to such systems, we adopted the goal of generating, and then verifying, entanglement between the phonon modes of two separated diamond crystals. We have successfully taken the first step in this direction, namely demonstration of the ability to create and detect phonons.

Figure 10 shows the experimental arrangement used, along with the structure of the interactions involved. In Figure 11 the Stokes/anti-Stokes coincidence rate is plotted as a function of an electronically introduced time-delay between the two detection events. The surge in correlations around zero delay is attributed to the survival of phonons over the (unresolved) period separating the control pulses.

The next stage of these experiments is to interfere the Stokes modes from a pair of diamond crystals, so as to erase the *welcher weg* information about the origin of a detected Stokes photon. Such a detection then entangles the phonon modes of the crystals; subsequent application of read pulses to the crystals transfers this entanglement back to the optical domain, where it can be witnessed by interfering the anti-Stokes modes. The scheme is identical to that implemented in [131,145,146], except that the entanglement is created in a solid, a technical challenge being that it survives for a time that is too short to be resolved electronically.

Although the current experiments with diamond are not focussed on the realization of an absorptive optical memory, the planned entanglement generation set-up can be adapted to function as a post-selected memory [145], which is prepared by the Stokes detection that heralds entanglement. From this perspective, it is interesting to evaluate the performance of diamond as a memory by the criteria introduced in Section 4.

For storage of a polarization qubit, the **fidelity** can be high in principle, being limited only by the stability of the set-up and the coherence time of the memory. The retrieval probability is generally low, which translates into low **efficiency**, although this could be mitigated by boosting the energy of the read pulse. The **storage time** of 5 ps is extremely short – far too short to find applications in any quantum communication protocols. It is possible, however, that it could be of use as a solid-state register, as part of a miniaturized integrated quantum processor.

The **bandwidth** is extremely large, being on the order of tens of THz. This allows the storage of ultrafast pulses, a million times shorter than any other memory has so far demonstrated. The time bandwidth product for the

Fig. 10. Creation and detection of phonon excitations in diamond. A pair of 50 fs control pulses are focused into a crystal of diamond. When the ‘write’ pulse generates a Stokes photon, a phonon is created. The ‘read’ pulse can then scatter from this excitation, producing an anti-Stokes photon that returns the crystal to its ground state. Coincidence measurements reveal the resulting statistical correlations arising between Stokes and anti-Stokes detection events.

Fig. 11. Read out of phonons in diamond, as revealed by examining the correlation between Stokes and anti-Stokes detection events. The green curve shows the coincidence rate associated with the ‘wrong’ detection order (A,S), in which an anti-Stokes photon is scattered from the write pulse and a Stokes photon scatters from the read pulse. Photons scattered from the write and read pulses are distinguished by their polarizations. The blue curve describes the correlations for the ‘correct’ ordering (S,A). No significant correlations are observed for the incorrect ordering (although the polarization selection rules in diamond are not perfect, so there is a residual contribution from the correct ordering). The correct ordering exhibits a pronounced peak around zero delay. This peak is a signature that phonons are created by the write pulse and read out by the read pulse from the same control pulse sequence – the 5 ps delay between the read and write control pulses is not resolvable. Subsidiary maxima occur for delays that are multiples of 12.5 ns, which is the laser repetition rate. These are spurious, being a symptom of the increased accidental coincidence rates associated with a pair of independent control pulse sequences (dashed red line, calculated for a 3 ns coincidence gate, with reasonable technical noise).

memory is accordingly on the order of 1000, despite its short coherence lifetime.

The **multimode capacity** of the memory is probably small, for the same reasons as discussed above in the case of an absorptive Raman memory. Nonetheless, as with all ensemble memories, spatial or angular multiplexing could be used. Finally the **wavelength** is extremely tunable, since diamond is transparent to all optical frequencies, with a Raman cross-section that varies little over the visible or telecoms spectra. Essentially any choice of wavelength is viable.

7 Summary and outlook

Table 1 summarizes where the different approaches position themselves with respect to the applications discussed in Section 2 and to the criteria discussed in Section 4.

The experimental projects in this review are in different stages in their development. Some have already demonstrated quantum features such as entanglement with light or realized quantum protocols such as teleportation. Others are in an earlier stage. All approaches appear to be suitable in principle for high-fidelity and

Approach	Potential Applications	Efficiency	Measurement	Fidelity	Entanglement with light	Band width	Storage Time	MM capacity	Dim.
RE AFC	SPS, QRep LOC4	0.34 ~1	retrieval	0.97 cond.	not yet Yes with PDC	100 MHz 1 GHz	15 μ s 30 s	64 high	high
NV	QRep, SPS	not yet ~1 with cavity	direct	0.85	done	not yet 10 MHz	>100 μ s >10 ms	moderate	moderate
QD	SPS, QRep	~0.04 ~1	retrieval	0.94	done	>GHz	2 ns 100 μ s	high	low
Single atoms Free space	LHF, QRep	low ~1 with cavity	direct	0.94 cond.	done	6 MHz	150 μ s >ms	moderate	moderate
Room-temp. gas	LOC4, Prec.msmt.	1	direct	0.7 uncond.	done	kHz 100 kHz	4 ms 200 ms	low	high
Cold gas	Prec.msmt., LOC4, QRep	1	direct	0.75 uncond.	not yet yes	1 MHz 0.5 GHz	not yet 100 ms	moderate (spatial)	high
Raman gas	SPS, QRep	0.15 ~1	retrieval	0.85 cond.	not yet yes	1 GHz GHz	2 μ s >100 μ s	moderate	high

Table 1. Overview of different approaches to quantum memories represented in the integrated project “Qubit Applications”. The numbers shown are the best values that have been achieved by members of the project. **Approach:** RE AFC – atomic frequency comb with rare-earth doped crystals (Geneva/Lund); NV – NV centers in diamond (Stuttgart); QD – quantum dots (Toshiba); single atoms in free space (Munich); room-temperature gas (Copenhagen); cold gas (Copenhagen); Raman gas – Raman memory in a hot cesium gas (Oxford). **Potential applications:** see Section 2 for a discussion of potential applications. SPS – single-photon source; QRep – quantum repeaters; LOC4 – protocols that allow a reduction in communication complexity using memories and local operations and classical communication; LHF – loophole-free Bell experiment; Prec.msmt. – precision measurement. **Efficiency:** see Sections 4.2 and 6 for the concept of efficiency. Above the diagonal is the current experimental value, below the diagonal the value that appears in principle achievable with the respective approach. The same applies to the following columns. **Measurement:** in some approaches it is possible to measure the stored state in a way that is different from retrieving the stored light. In other approaches state measurements are done via retrieval. **Fidelity:** see Sections 4.1 and 6 for the definition of fidelity. The given fidelities are conditional on detection of a photon, or unconditional as indicated. **Entanglement with light:** entanglement between an excitation stored in the memory and light has already been demonstrated in some approaches. **Bandwidth:** bandwidth of the light that can be stored and retrieved (or that is emitted, cf. Sect. 3.3). **Storage time:** maximal memory storage time. **MM capacity:** capacity to store signals in multiple modes. **Dim.:** capacity to store signals that live in a high-dimensional Hilbert space (for a single mode).

high-efficiency operation. The technological challenges that have to be overcome to this end vary between the different approaches. Most implementations aim for bandwidths in the range 100 MHz to 1 GHz and for storage times in the ms to s range. Concerning complexity, most solid-state implementations require cryostats and some micro- or nanofabrication, while atomic approaches tend to require laser cooling and trapping.

In the future it will be interesting to investigate various ways of combining the different approaches discussed here. Recent examples for this trend include the combination of continuous-variable and single-photon concepts in the context of quantum repeaters [147], and a proposal for creating entanglement between a trapped ion and a quantum dot [148].

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3 Experimental demonstration of an elementary quantum repeater link

Central goal of our research activities was the experimental demonstration of an elementary quantum repeater link, i.e. the generation and analysis of heralded entanglement between widely separated quantum memories. As already mentioned, we implement stationary quantum memories by storing qubits in the internal spin-degree of freedom of single optically trapped ^{87}Rb atoms [66, 46, 55]. Communication qubits are encoded in the polarization degree of freedom of single photons (see Fig. 2.6). In order to enable the reliable generation and analysis of heralded entanglement between two atomic spins at remote locations several experimental demands have to be met. (i) Atomic spin states have to be read out fast, efficient, and with high fidelity. (ii) The atomic memory qubit should show long coherence times. (iii) Entangled atom-photon pairs are required for interfacing photonic and atomic qubits. (iv) Atom-photon entanglement has to be distributed over large distances. (v) Two photons have to be subjected to a high-fidelity Bell state measurement in order to enable entanglement swapping. The following experiments demonstrate all relevant building blocks of a quantum repeater link, culminating finally in the demonstration of heralded entanglement between two atoms at a distance of 20 m.

3.1 Deterministic sub- μs readout of a single-atom quantum memory

One central requirement for scalable quantum repeaters is the highly efficient and fast measurement of stationary qubit states. For single atomic qubits, the most frequently used fluorescence method allows measuring with a detection efficiency of almost unity, however, at the cost of comparably long detection times ($> 100\mu\text{s}$). In order to reduce the measurement duration for such systems one can either increase the numerical aperture of the collection optics [71, 72, 73] or, alternatively, enhance fluorescence by means of optical cavities [74, 75, 76]. Yet, if one intends to apply these approaches for state analysis of many atoms, e.g., required for entanglement purification in optical lattices, difficulties arise. Even with fluorescence collection pushed to the limit [71, 72, 73] the detection times can hardly be reduced below 10 μs per atom. Alternatively, optical cavities allow detection times below 1 μs [77]. However, due to the typically small mode

Figure 3.1: (a) Atomic level structure of Rb-87 used for photoionization. (b) Experimental arrangement of two opposing channel electron multiplier for efficient detection of ionization fragments.

volume and reduced optical access, scalability to a large number of atoms is challenging with current state of the art technologies. In order to obtain both scalability and speed, a completely different approach is required.

In the following work “*Highly efficient state-selective sub-microsecond photoionization detection of single atoms*” (F. Henkel et al., *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 105, 253001 (2010)) we have demonstrated a highly efficient, state selective, and fast detection system for optically trapped neutral atoms, allowing deterministic state analysis at the single-atom level. The method is based on hyperfine-state-selective photoionization (see Fig. 3.1(a)) and subsequent registration of the correlated ion-electron pairs by coincidence counting using two opposing channel electron multipliers (see Fig. 3.1(b))[78]. On the example of single Rb-87 atoms, we reach a readout fidelity of $F = 99.2\%$, an overall detection time below $1 \mu\text{s}$, and an overall detection efficiency η exceeding 98% . In comparison with the frequently used fluorescence method this new technique combines a 100 fold enhancement in speed with scalability to a large number of atoms. Though the detection process removes the analyzed atom from the trap, the system has a number of possible applications, e.g. together with stimulated Raman adiabatic passage (STIRAP) techniques the state analysis of Zeeman qubits [79, 43]. In the future it might also be applied e.g. for imaging [80, 81, 82, 83, 84] and site-specific readout of atoms in optical lattices [85, 86], for *in situ* real-time probing of ultra-cold atomic ensembles with sub-Poissonian accuracy [87], or as a detector for a loophole-free test of Bell’s inequality [88, 89].

Highly Efficient State-Selective Submicrosecond Photoionization Detection of Single Atoms

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We experimentally demonstrate a detection scheme suitable for state analysis of single optically trapped atoms in less than $1 \mu\text{s}$ with an overall detection efficiency η exceeding 98%. The method is based on hyperfine-state-selective photoionization and subsequent registration of the correlated photoion-electron pairs by coincidence counting via two opposing channel electron multipliers. The scheme enables the calibration of absolute detection efficiencies and might be a key ingredient for future quantum information applications or precision spectroscopy of ultracold atoms.

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One crucial requirement for quantum computation, quantum communication, and quantum metrology is the highly efficient measurement of qubit states. For atomic qubits, the most frequently used fluorescence method allows measuring with a detection efficiency of almost unity, however, at the cost of comparably long detection times ($>100 \mu\text{s}$). In order to reduce the measurement duration for such systems one can either increase the numerical aperture of the collection optics [1] or, alternatively, enhance fluorescence by means of optical cavities [2].

Yet, if one intends to apply these approaches for state analysis of many atoms, e.g., for one-way quantum computation in optical lattices [3], difficulties arise. Even with fluorescence collection pushed to the limit [1] the detection times can hardly be reduced below $10 \mu\text{s}$ per atom. Alternatively, optical cavities allow detection times below $1 \mu\text{s}$ [4]. However, due to the typically small mode volume and reduced optical access, scalability to a large number of atoms may be challenging with current state of the art technologies. Therefore, in order to obtain both scalability and speed, a completely different approach is required.

In this Letter, we experimentally demonstrate how hyperfine-state-selective photoionization and subsequent detection of the generated photoion-electron pairs enable fast and efficient state analysis. On the example of single ^{87}Rb atoms, we reach a readout fidelity of $\mathcal{F} = 99.2\%$, an overall detection time below $1 \mu\text{s}$, and an overall detection efficiency η exceeding 98%.

In a first experiment, efficiency, speed, and hyperfine-state selectivity of the photoionization procedure are studied [5]. For this purpose, a single ^{87}Rb atom is loaded into a far off resonance optical dipole trap in an UHV glass cell setup, similar to [6] [Fig. 1(a)]. State selectivity is achieved by a two-step, two-color photoionization scheme using the $5^2P_{3/2}$, $F^I = 3$ level as resonant, intermediate state [Fig. 1(b), $\lambda_{12} = 780 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{2i} = 473 \text{ nm}$]. For that purpose two perpendicular, focused laser beams ($w_{12} = 54 \mu\text{m}$, $P_{12} = 6 \mu\text{W}$; $w_{2i} = 1.13 \mu\text{m}$, $P_{2i} = 32.8 \text{ mW}$) are overlapped with the optical dipole trap into one common focus [Fig. 1(a)]. The polarizations of both laser fields

are linear and parallel to the y axis. During measurements no electric field is applied and only small magnetic fields ($< 50 \text{ mG}$) are present.

To evaluate the photoionization process, we investigate the ionization probability of the trapped atom for different excitation pulse lengths (Fig. 2). By optical pumping, the atom is initially prepared either in the $5^2S_{1/2}$, $F = 1$ or $F = 2$ hyperfine ground state, respectively [Fig. 1(b)]. Then, pulses of the excitation and ionization light are simultaneously applied. While the ionization pulse length is fixed to $2.12 \mu\text{s}$ for all measurements, the excitation

FIG. 1 (color online). (a) Setup for single-atom ionization: Single atoms are trapped in an optical dipole trap, prepared into selected hyperfine states and subsequently ionized. (b) Photoionization level scheme: Single ion- e^- pairs are generated by hyperfine-state-selective, resonant two-step, two-color photoionization. (c) Joint channel electron multiplier (CEM) detector: two opposing CEMs and compensation electrodes against stray fields are built into a glass cell identical to (a). (d) Detector geometry in section view (laser beam waist not to scale).

FIG. 2 (color online). Hyperfine-state-selective, single-atom ionization probability for different laser pulse lengths. Atoms in the trap are initially prepared either in the $5^2S_{1/2}$ $F = 2$ (\square) or the $F = 1$ (\circ) hyperfine state, respectively. Only atoms in $F = 2$ driven by both laser fields (λ_{12} , λ_{2i}) are ionized. Inset: Scheme showing the timing of the excitation and ionization pulses.

pulse length t_p is varied between 36 ns and 2.0 μs (Fig. 2, inset). The excitation pulse operates at a multiple of the saturation intensity of the cycling transition, yielding the $5^2P_{3/2}$ state population approaching one-half after a few lifetimes of the excited state ($\tau_{\text{exc}} = 26.2$ ns).

Figure 2 shows the ionization probability after application of a single excitation-ionization sequence. As the ionization process removes the atom out of the trap, the ionization probability is derived from atom loss, analyzed by subsequent fluorescence detection. For atoms initially prepared in $F = 2$, the dynamics of the resonant two-step, two-color photoionization is described by a rate equation model [7], valid for t_p longer than the lifetime of the intermediate $5^2P_{3/2}$ level. The ionization probability is

$$p_{\text{ion},F=2}(t_p) = p_{\infty}(1 - \exp[-\rho_{ee}\sigma_{2i}\Phi_{2i}t_p]), \quad (1)$$

with p_{∞} being the probability to ionize the atom for $t_p \rightarrow \infty$, $\rho_{ee} \approx \frac{1}{2}$ the steady-state population of the $5^2P_{3/2}$ level, σ_{2i} the ionization cross section [8], and Φ_{2i} the photonic flux of the ionizing laser. For the evaluation of $p_{\text{ion},F=2}$, the parameters ρ_{ee} , σ_{2i} and Φ_{2i} are combined into a characteristic $\frac{1}{e}$ -ionization time $\tau = (\rho_{ee}\sigma_{2i}\Phi_{2i})^{-1}$. To determine τ , a least-square fit according to (1) is applied for pulse lengths t_p up to 475 ns (red line, Fig. 2). With $p_{\infty} = 0.993 \pm 0.001$ deduced by averaging the measured ionization probabilities for $t_p > 475$ ns, we obtain $\tau = 64.4 \pm 2.8$ ns. Thus, after an ionization time $t_{\text{ion}} \equiv 6\tau = 386$ ns ($F = 2$, Fig. 2), an ionization probability of $p_{\text{ion},F=2}(t_{\text{ion}}) = 0.9905 \pm 0.0010$ is achieved. Other loss mechanisms, as, e.g., possible single-color, multiphoton ionization processes or heating are considered. For that purpose each of the beams is switched on separately, showing negligible ionization probabilities. In order to demonstrate the hyperfine-state selectivity of the ionization scheme, we compare this result with measurements for the atom initially prepared in the $5^2S_{1/2}$, $F = 1$ state.

Here, we observe a probability $p_{\text{ion},F=1}$ of 0.0068 ± 0.0001 for all excitation pulse lengths t_p ($F = 1$, Fig. 2).

From these measurements, a readout fidelity $\mathcal{F} = \frac{1}{2}[p_{\text{ion},F=2} + (1 - p_{\text{ion},F=1})]$, defined as the average probability to correctly identify the hyperfine state, can be deduced, resulting in a value of $\mathcal{F}(t_{\text{ion}}) = 99.19 \pm 0.05\%$ [9]. Note, this value also includes preparation errors, atom loss out of the trap, and errors of the fluorescence detection and since the observed $p_{\text{ion},F=1}$ is indistinguishable from measurements without any ionizing light the actual readout fidelity of the ionization process is even closer to unity.

In a second experiment, the efficiency and time required for detecting the generated photoion-electron pairs, as well as the sensitive volume of the detection system are investigated. To detect both ionization fragments, this system consists of two channel electron multipliers (CEMs, [10]) whose cone entrances are separated by $d = 15.7$ mm. To protect the CEM cones against stray light and to tailor the electric fields inside the cones, the entrances are covered by copper plates with an open aperture of 2 mm. Additional electrodes next to the CEMs compensate for electric stray fields [Fig. 1(c)]. This system is mounted in a separate UHV glass cell setup, where in between both detectors at $z = d/2$, ^{87}Rb atoms from the thermal background vapor are photoionized within the overlap of two mutually perpendicular laser beams. The overlap region can be moved in all three dimensions in order to investigate the spatial dependence of the detection efficiency (the sensitive volume). Uniform ionization conditions over the scan region are provided by only weakly focusing the beams ($w_{12} = 26$ μm , $P_{12} = 155$ μW ; $w_{2i} = 43$ μm , $P_{2i} = 164$ mW). To separate the oppositely charged photoionization fragments into their corresponding CEM, the CEMs are held at different electric potentials defining the total acceleration voltage U_{acc} [Fig. 1(d)] which in turn determines the kinetic energy E_{kin} of the fragments at the cone entrance [11]. The particular arrangement of the CEMs and the compensation electrodes ensures that no additional electron or ion optics is required, thus, allowing a large solid angle for optical access.

In order to determine the duration t_{det} of the detection process, the time from the ionization event to the detection of the macroscopic pulses at the anodes of the CEMs is investigated [12]. It is composed of the respective flight times (t_e , t_i) of the two ionization fragments until the primary particle hit in the corresponding detector [Fig. 1(d)] and the transit time of the electron avalanche inside the CEM channels. In the experiment only the time-of-flight difference $\Delta t = t_i - t_e$ is accessible [Fig. 3(a)]. It is deduced from a Gaussian fit of the detection time differences [Fig. 3(a), inset]. The temporal spread of the correlation peak [indicated by the error bars in Fig. 3(a)] remains narrow for a wide range of acceleration voltages (1.6–3.8 kV) with $\text{FWHM} \leq 8.5$ ns. The measured time-of-flight differences can be modeled assuming acceleration of the ion or electron in a homogeneous field E_{acc} up to the

FIG. 3 (color online). (a) Time-of-flight difference Δt of generated ^{87}Rb ions to their corresponding photoelectrons for different acceleration voltages U_{acc} . Inset: Sample histogram of time differences between ^{87}Rb -ion and electron detections for $U_{\text{acc}} = 3.8$ kV. (b) Absolute detection efficiency for ^{87}Rb -ions (\square , black), electrons (\circ , red) for different acceleration voltages and the calculated, total detection efficiency (\triangle , blue). Inset: Zoom for acceleration voltages from 3.2 to 3.8 kV.

CEM entrance and further deceleration (acceleration) within the respective CEM. The model holds for U_{acc} above 1.6 kV [red line, Fig. 3(a)], below this value the actual field configurations between and inside the CEMs have to be taken into account in more detail. At $U_{\text{acc}} = 3.8$ kV, we observe a time-of-flight difference of $\Delta t = 388.81 \pm 0.01$ ns. According to the model we obtain a photoelectron flight time of $t_e = 0.95$ ns for this acceleration voltage, which together with the CEM transit time of 26 ns [10] sums up to a detection time of $t_{\text{det}} = \Delta t + t_e + t_{\text{transit}} = 415.8$ ns.

For many applications the crucial parameter is a high detection efficiency [13,14], i.e., in our case the total efficiency of collecting the respective fragment into the CEM and converting it into an observable electron avalanche. In order to optimize the efficiency for our detection system, the positions of the primary particle hit inside the CEMs are designed to be under grazing incidence at the channel walls [Fig. 1(d)] and not in the CEM cones [15,16]. Absolute detection efficiencies can be determined by coincident detection of the oppositely charged ionization fragments with two particle detectors [17]. Such a calibration is in perfect conceptual correspondence to $4\pi\beta\gamma$ -coincidence counting [18] or absolute photodetector calibration via photon pairs [19]. Accordingly, the CEM ion and e^- -detection efficiencies η_i , η_e are given by

$$\eta_i = \frac{N_c}{N'_i}, \quad \eta_e = \frac{N_c}{N'_e}, \quad (2)$$

where $N'_i = N_i - N_{bi}$ and $N'_e = N_e - N_{be}$ are the background corrected ion and e^- single counts and N_c is the number of coincidences. The latter is obtained from the detection time difference histograms [Fig. 3(a), inset] with a coincidence time window starting 20 ns before the correlation peak and ending 80 ns after it. This choice results from the presence of a few late ion detections. Accidental coincidences can be neglected, as the fraction of accidental to true coincidences is smaller than 10^{-4} . The background events N_{bi} , N_{be} are measured with the excitation laser turned off, leaving only the ionization laser switched on. Figure 3(b) shows the absolute detection efficiencies for ions and electrons for different acceleration voltages U_{acc} . For values up to 3.8 kV, the ion detection efficiency η_i increases in qualitative agreement with previous studies for different ion species [16,20]. In contrast to this, the measured electron detection efficiency η_e remains almost constant. At $U_{\text{acc}} = 3.8$ kV, for a measurement time of 60 s we observe $N_i = 53\,762$, $N_{bi} = 2235$, $N_e = 196\,547$, $N_{be} = 147\,845$ and $N_c = 45\,099$ (including ion and electron dark counts $N_{di} \sim 2100$ and $N_{de} \sim 15\,000$, respectively), resulting in an absolute CEM detection efficiency of $\eta_i = 0.926 \pm 0.010$ and $\eta_e = 0.875 \pm 0.002$ [21]. From these efficiencies, a total efficiency for the detection of a photoionized neutral atom can be determined. As it is sufficient to detect the photoion *or* the photoelectron, the total detection efficiency η_{det} is

$$\eta_{\text{det}} = 1 - (1 - \eta_i)(1 - \eta_e) = \eta_e + \eta_i - \eta_i\eta_e. \quad (3)$$

Using the above values at 3.8 kV, a total detection efficiency of $\eta_{\text{det}} = 0.991 \pm 0.002$ is derived.

Finally, we analyze the spatial dependence of the detection efficiency, i.e., the sensitive volume of the detection system. Figure 4(a) shows the spatial distribution of the efficiency determined by a 2D scan in the x - y plane at $d/2$ in between both CEMs. Here, for both detectors, a roughly circular distribution is observed. A scan along the x direction through the center of the area is depicted in Fig. 4(b) for different CEM gain voltages at $U_{\text{acc}} = 3.8$ kV. Uniform efficiencies over the full area [see e^- CEM, Fig. 4(b)] are achieved for high gain voltages [22], similar to previous experiments with electron and ion beams [16]. From these measurements we obtain a sensitive area with a diameter of $d_o = 0.84$ mm where η_{det} exceeds 98.8%. Corresponding measurements at different z positions display a similar spatial behavior, indicating that the sensitive volume has a longitudinal extension of at least 5 mm. By moving the ionization region closer to the ion CEM and adapting U_{acc} , even shorter ion flight times can be achieved, retaining high detection efficiencies.

Combining all measurement results, an overall efficiency $\eta = p_{\text{ion},F=2}\eta_{\text{det}}$ for state-selective detection of a single, neutral atom stored in an optical dipole trap and its corresponding detection time $t_{\text{tot}} = t_{\text{ion}} + t_{\text{det}}$ can be estimated. At an acceleration voltage of $U_{\text{acc}} = 3.8$ kV, an

FIG. 4 (color online). (a) 2D scans of the sensitive areas at a gain voltage of 2.8 kV for the e^- CEM (top) and ion CEM (bottom) for an acceleration voltage of 3.8 kV. Dashed lines indicate respective line scans in (b). (b) Line scans through the center at $y = -0.4$ mm. Electron detection efficiencies (top) at different gain voltages ($\diamond = 2.4$ kV (brown); $\triangleleft = 2.5$ kV (green); $\star = 2.6$ kV (blue); $\nabla = 2.8$ kV (red); $\triangle = 3.2$ kV (black)). ^{87}Rb -ion detection efficiency (bottom) for a gain voltage of 2.7 kV (\square). The acceleration voltage is the same as in (a).

overall detection efficiency of $\eta = 0.982 \pm 0.002$ with an overall detection time $t_{\text{tot}} = 802 \pm 17$ ns is determined.

In this Letter, we have shown a highly efficient, state selective, and fast ionization detection system for optically trapped neutral atoms which allows deterministic state analysis at the single-atom level. Though the detection process removes the analyzed atom from the trap, the system has a number of possible applications, for example, combined with single-atom traps it allows us to determine partial and total photoionization cross sections free from ensemble averages [8] or together with coherent stimulated Raman adiabatic passage techniques the state analysis of Zeeman qubits [13]. Contrary to other approaches for single-atom state analysis, the geometry of the detection system provides a comparably large sensitive volume and high optical access. In the future it might thus be applied, e.g., for imaging [23] and site-specific readout of atoms in optical lattices where pulsed, scanning excitation schemes operating at high powers can enable readout times below 100 ns per atom. Furthermore, it could also be used for *in situ*, real-time probing of ultracold ensembles with sub-Poissonian accuracy [14] or as detector for a loophole-free test of Bell's inequality with a pair of trapped atoms at remote locations [13].

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3.2 A light-matter quantum interface

A second crucial building block for quantum repeaters are light-matter quantum interfaces [42, 18, 43, 90]. In our approach entanglement between a single atom and a single photon is used to interface stationary memory and mobile photonic qubits. The relevance of light-matter entanglement arises from the fact that it establishes non-classical correlations between a localized matter-based quantum memory and an optical carrier of quantum information which can easily be sent to a distant location. In this context, decoherence of the photonic quantum channel, as well as, decoherence of the matter-based quantum memory are important figures of merit setting a limit how far quantum information can be distributed or how long this information can be stored, respectively. Therefore, the ability to generate and preserve light-matter entanglement over large distances opens the possibility for long-distance distribution of quantum information.

In the following contribution “*Observation of Entanglement of a Single Photon with a Trapped Atom*”, (J. Volz et al., *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 96, 030404 (2006)) we report the *first* observation of entanglement between the polarization state of a single photon and the internal spin-state of a single optically trapped Rb-87 atom. The atom-photon entanglement is generated in the spontaneous emission process in a lambda-type atomic transition. For full characterization of the entanglement we introduced a new state-analysis method, enabling state tomography of the atomic qubit. This technique allowed us for the first time to reconstruct the density matrix of an entangled light-matter hybrid system. In a second work “*Towards Long-Distance Atom-Photon Entanglement*”, (W. Rosenfeld et al., *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 101, 260403 (2008)) we describe a further significant step towards a long-distance quantum repeater link. We successfully demonstrated the generation and verification of atom-photon entanglement, after communicating the photon via an actively stabilized optical fiber link of 300 m length. This implementation includes also an active stabilization of ambient magnetic fields, resulting in a T_2^* dephasing time of the atomic memory qubit of 150 μ s. This achievement already demonstrates that our entangled light-matter interface can be reliably operated up to distances of several km, limited only by transmission losses of the photon in optical fibers.

Observation of Entanglement of a Single Photon with a Trapped Atom

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We report the observation of entanglement between a single trapped atom and a single photon at a wavelength suitable for low-loss communication over large distances, thereby achieving a crucial step towards long range quantum networks. To verify the entanglement, we introduce a single atom state analysis. This technique is used for full state tomography of the atom-photon qubit pair. The detection efficiency and the entanglement fidelity are high enough to allow in a next step the generation of entangled atoms at large distances, ready for a final loophole-free Bell experiment.

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Entanglement is a key element for quantum communication and information applications [1]. Demonstrations of quantum computers with ions in linear chains nowadays almost routinely create deterministically any desired entangled state with up to eight ions [2]. The currently largest quantum processor consisting of some tens of (not yet distinguishable) qubits in a so-called cluster state was implemented with neutral atoms in an optical lattice [3]. For future applications such as quantum networks or the quantum repeater [4], it is mandatory to achieve entanglement also between separated quantum processors. For this purpose, entanglement between different quantum objects such as atoms and photons—recently demonstrated for ions and photons [5]—forms the interface between atomic quantum memories and photonic quantum communication channels [6], finally allowing the distribution of quantum information over arbitrary distances.

Atom-photon entanglement is not only crucial for many applications in long range quantum communication but is also the key element to give the final answer to Einstein's question on the real properties of nature [7]. Together with Podolsky and Rosen, he pointed out the inconsistencies between quantum mechanics and their ideal of a local and deterministic description of nature [8]. They implied that parameters of a physical system (local hidden variables), which might not—yet—be known to us, could solve the problem. Until now, the results of many experiments based on Bell's inequality [9] indicate that hidden variable theories would result in incorrect predictions and, thus, are not a valid description of nature [10–12]. But all these tests are subject to loopholes [11,13], and none so far could definitely rule out all alternative concepts.

Here we describe the observation of entanglement between the polarization of a single photon and the internal state of a single neutral atom stored in an optical dipole trap. For this purpose, we introduce a new state-analysis method enabling full state tomography of the atomic qubit. This now allows for the first time the direct analysis of the

entangled atom-photon state formed during the spontaneous emission process. Moreover, we can show that the results achieved indeed suffice to test Einstein's objections.

Atom-photon entanglement can be prepared best by exciting an atom to a state which ideally has two decay channels (Λ configuration). The hyperfine structure of ^{87}Rb offers a good approximation to such a level scheme [Fig. 1(a)]. Excited to the $5^2P_{3/2}$, $F'=0$ hyperfine level, the atom can spontaneously decay into the three magnetic sublevels $|m_F=0, \pm 1\rangle$ of the $5^2S_{1/2}$, $F=1$ hyperfine ground level by emitting a photon at a wavelength of 780 nm.

If the emitted photon is σ^+ -polarized, the atom will be in the state $|m_F=-1\rangle$. If the photon is linearly π -polarized, the atom will be in the state $|m_F=0\rangle$, and for σ^- polarization we find the state $|m_F=+1\rangle$. Since the emitted photons are collected along the quantization axis, π -polarized light (emitted into a different spatial mode) is not collected. Therefore, only spontaneous decay into the states $|m_F=\pm 1\rangle$ is observed. As long as these emission processes are indistinguishable in all other degrees of freedom, one obtains a coherent superposition of the two decay possibilities, i.e., the maximally entangled state

$$|\Psi^+\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|m_F=-1\rangle|\sigma^+\rangle + |m_F=+1\rangle|\sigma^-\rangle). \quad (1)$$

Here in each of the terms the first ket describes the state of the atom and the second one the polarization of the photon. The quantum mechanical phase of the atom-photon state is well defined and follows from the Clebsch-Gordan coefficients of the transitions.

In our experiment, atoms are cooled from a shallow magneto-optical trap (MOT) into an optical dipole trap located in the center of the MOT [14]. For the dipole trap waist size of $3.5\ \mu\text{m}$, a collisional blockade mechanism ensures that only single atoms are captured [15].

When a single atom is loaded into the trap and its fluorescence is registered, the sequence entangling the atom

FIG. 1 (color online). (a) Preparation of atom-photon entanglement in ^{87}Rb . The excited hyperfine level with $F' = 0$ can decay to three possible ground states with the magnetic quantum numbers $m_F = -1, 0$, or 1 , by spontaneously emitting a σ^+ , π , or σ^- polarized photon, respectively. If the light is collected along the quantization axis, π -polarized photons are suppressed. Thus, an effective Λ configuration is obtained which allows the preparation of a maximally entangled state between the photon polarization and the orientation of the atomic magnetic moment. (b) Scheme of the experimental setup. The dipole trap light ($\lambda = 856$ nm, $P = 30$ mW) is focused by a microscope objective (NA = 0.38) to a waist of 3.5 μm . The photon from the spontaneous decay is collected with the same objective, separated from the trapping beam by a dichroic mirror, and coupled into a single mode optical fiber guiding it to the polarization analyzer. The analyzer consists of a rotatable half- and quarter-wave plate, a polarizing beam splitter (PBS), and two avalanche photodiodes (APD) for single photon detection. Triggered by the detection of the photon in either APD₁ or APD₂, the atomic state is analyzed using a STIRAP light field whose polarization defines the atomic measurement basis.

with a photon is started by pumping it into the $F = 1$, $m_F = 0$ state. Next, a 30 ns optical π pulse excites the atom to the $F' = 0$ level, from which it will decay back to $F = 1$. Photons emitted along the quantization axis are collected and guided via a single mode optical fiber to a single photon polarization analyzer to determine the state of the photonic qubit [see Fig. 1(b)]. Because the emitted photon is detected with an overall efficiency of $\eta_{\text{ph}} \approx 5 \times 10^{-4}$, the whole process has to be repeated approximately 2000 times to observe the photon. The repetition rate of this process is 1.25×10^5 s $^{-1}$. However, in the atomic state detection, the atom is lost with a probability of 0.5 (see below). Therefore, the mean time to load an atom into the dipole trap limits the total rate for the generation of entangled atom-photon pairs to 0.2 s $^{-1}$.

Once the emitted photon is detected, the state analysis of the atom is initiated. Standard spectroscopy techniques probing only the populations of the states $|m_F = -1\rangle$ and $|m_F = +1\rangle$ are not sufficient to confirm entanglement. Instead, a projection onto general superposition states is

required. We thus apply a state selective stimulated Raman adiabatic passage (STIRAP) technique [16], which allows one to transfer an arbitrary superposition state $|\psi\rangle = \sin\theta|m_F = -1\rangle + e^{i\phi}\cos\theta|m_F = +1\rangle$ adiabatically to the $F = 2$ ground level (Fig. 2). Because of the selection rules of atomic dipole transitions, the orthogonal quantum state does not couple to the STIRAP light field Ω_1 and remains in the $F = 1$ level. The angles θ and ϕ in this process are defined by the relative amplitude and phase of the σ^+ and σ^- polarization components of the STIRAP laser Ω_1 , respectively. In essence, the polarization of the STIRAP laser defines which superposition state is transferred, thus allowing a full tomographic analysis of the atomic state without the necessity to perform any state manipulation on the atomic qubit.

After the STIRAP pulse, the atom is in a superposition of the hyperfine ground levels $F = 1$ and $F = 2$, which now can be distinguished by standard methods. We apply a detection laser pulse (resonant to the closed transition $F = 2 \rightarrow F' = 3$), removing atoms in the $F = 2$ level from the trap. Finally, to read out the atomic state, the cooling lasers of the MOT are switched on and atomic fluorescence is measured for 30 ms to decide whether the atom is still in the trap or not. Thereby, we obtain the binary result of the projective atomic state measurement on the state $|\psi\rangle$ and the orthogonal state $|\psi_{\perp}\rangle$. For the results shown in Fig. 3, we repeated the experimental cycle approximately 300 times per data point from which we obtain the probability of the atom to remain in $F = 1$ with a statistical error of $\pm 2\%$.

To verify the entanglement of the generated atom-photon state, we perform $\hat{\sigma}_x$ ($\theta = \pi/4$, $\phi = 0$) as well as $\hat{\sigma}_y$ ($\theta = \pi/4$, $\phi = \pi/2$) state analysis of the atomic qubit for different polarization measurements of the photon (Fig. 3, $\hat{\sigma}_i$ are the spin-1/2 Pauli operators). Thereby, the probability of the atom to be transferred by the STIRAP pulse sequence, or the probability to remain in the $F = 1$

FIG. 2 (color online). Experimental procedure for the atomic state detection. To analyze the atomic state, a two-photon STIRAP-process state selectively transfers a superposition of the states $|m_F = -1\rangle$ and $|m_F = +1\rangle$ to the $F = 2$ hyperfine level. To read out the atomic qubit, a hyperfine-level selective detection pulse is applied before standard fluorescence detection.

FIG. 3 (color online). Probability of detecting the atom in the ground level $F = 1$ (after the STIRAP pulse) conditioned on the detection of the photon in detector APD₁ (●) or APD₂ (○) as the linear polarization of the photonic qubit is rotated by an angle β . (a) The atomic qubit is measured in $\hat{\sigma}_x$ and (b) in $\hat{\sigma}_y$, whereas the photonic qubit is projected onto the states $1/\sqrt{2}(|\sigma^+\rangle \pm e^{2i\beta}|\sigma^-\rangle)$.

ground level, respectively, is measured, conditioned on the polarization measurement outcome of the photon. Varying the photon polarization analyzer, this probability shows the expected sinusoidal dependence for both $\hat{\sigma}_x$ and $\hat{\sigma}_y$. From the fits to the measured data, we obtain an effective visibility (peak to peak amplitude) of $V_{\text{at-ph}} = 0.85 \pm 0.01$ for analysis in $\hat{\sigma}_x$ and $V_{\text{at-ph}} = 0.87 \pm 0.01$ for analysis in $\hat{\sigma}_y$. This clearly proves entanglement of the generated atom-photon state.

For the determination of the full atom-photon state, we perform two-qubit state tomography. This involves a new set of measurements determining correlations of all combinations of the operators $\hat{\sigma}_x$, $\hat{\sigma}_y$, and $\hat{\sigma}_z$ on the atom and the photon [17]. The density matrix $\rho_{\text{at-ph}}$ determined this way clearly proves the state to be of the form of (1) [see Fig. 4(a)]. The fidelity, defined as the overlap between $|\Psi^+\rangle\langle\Psi^+|$ and $\rho_{\text{at-ph}}$, in this measurement was $\mathcal{F} = 0.87 \pm 0.01$. The limited visibility in the atom-photon correlations is caused mainly by errors in the atomic state detection (5%), accidental photon detection events due to the dark counts of the single photon detectors (3%), off-resonant excitation to the hyperfine level $5^2P_{3/2}$, $F' = 1$ (1%), and polarization errors of the STIRAP laser beams (2%). Applying the Peres-Horodecki criterion [18] to the combined density matrix proves the entanglement with a

FIG. 4 (color online). (a) Graphical representation of the real part of the measured density matrix of the entangled atom-photon state. The fidelity (overlap with the expected state $|\Psi^+\rangle$) from this measurement is $\mathcal{F} = 0.87 \pm 0.01$. Insets (b) and (c) show the single particle density matrices for the atom and photon state, respectively, indicating that the single particles when observed on their own are found in a completely mixed state.

negativity of 0.382. Figures 4(b) and 4(c) show the density matrices of the atomic and the photonic state after tracing over the partner qubit. Obviously, these states are in a complete statistical mixture. However, it becomes clear that the resulting atom-photon state is *not* a mixture of all possible contributions but is instead a well defined (ideally) pure entangled state.

In view of these results, let us now analyze the performance of a possible loophole-free Bell experiment with a pair of entangled atoms. Crucial for such a test is a highly efficient state analysis by spacelike separated observers. To generate entanglement between atoms at remote locations, they are first entangled with a photon each. The two photons are brought together and then are subject to a Bell-state measurement, which serves to swap the entanglement to the atoms [19]. If we use the average visibility observed in our experiment and extrapolate results of recent two-photon interference experiments [20–22], we derive an expected atom-atom visibility of $V_{\text{at-at}} = V_{\text{at-ph}}^2 = 0.74 \pm 0.01$. Thus, the violation of a Clauser-Horne-Shimony-Holt (CHSH)-type Bell inequality [23], which is achieved above the threshold visibility of 0.71, is feasible.

We emphasize that, triggered on the detection of a photon, every atomic state measurement yields a result. In this sense, the atomic detection efficiency is equal to

one. In certain cases, as, e.g., the loss of the atom from the trap, a wrong measurement outcome may occur, but one always obtains a result. Moreover, entanglement swapping enables a so-called event-ready scheme [11,19,24]. If measurement results are reported for every joint photon detection event, this scheme is independent of any additional assumptions and, thus, is not subject to any detection related loopholes at all. To close at the same time the locality loophole, the atoms have to be spacelike separated with respect to the measurement time of the atomic states. The minimum distance of the atoms is determined by the duration of the atomic state detection. In detail, the atomic state collapses by scattering photons from the detection laser for 350 ns. Together with the STIRAP process, this yields an overall measurement time of less than $0.5 \mu\text{s}$ and requires a separation of the atoms of 150 m. Thus, we expect the generation of one entangled atom-atom pair per minute [25]. A loophole-free violation of a CHSH-type Bell's inequality [23] by 3 standard deviations would require approximately 7000 atom pairs at the expected visibility of 0.74. This would be feasible within a total measurement time of 12 days.

In this Letter, we presented a successful implementation of a source of high-fidelity entangled atom-photon pairs. We introduced a single atom STIRAP state analysis which does not require additional atomic state manipulations and, thus, can be performed with increased fidelity. This allowed us to perform the first full state tomography of an atom-photon system and proved that the spontaneous emission of the atom results in the entangled state $|\Psi^+\rangle$. In the experiment, we achieved a state fidelity of $\mathcal{F} = 0.87 \pm 0.01$ and a mean visibility of the atom-photon correlations of $V_{\text{at-ph}} = 0.86 \pm 0.01$. These methods, possibly combined with high- Q cavities to enhance the collection efficiency [22,26], form the basic elements in future quantum information experiments for building the interface between quantum computers and a photonic quantum communication channel. In addition, these tools also help to find an answer to the long-standing question of whether local realistic extensions of quantum mechanics can describe nature at all. The experimental demonstration of high-fidelity entanglement provides the most important step towards a final, loophole-free test of Bell's inequality.

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Towards Long-Distance Atom-Photon Entanglement

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We report the observation of entanglement between a single trapped atom and a single photon at remote locations. The degree of coherence of the entangled atom-photon pair is verified via appropriate local correlation measurements, after communicating the photon via an optical fiber link of 300 m length to a receiver 3.5 m apart. In addition, we measured the temporal evolution of the atomic density matrix after projecting the atom via a state measurement of the photon onto several well-defined spin states. We find that the state of the single atom dephases on a time scale of 150 μ s, which represents an important step towards long-distance quantum networking with individual neutral atoms.

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Entanglement between light and matter [1–4] plays an outstanding role in long-distance quantum communication, allowing efficient distribution of quantum information over, in principle, arbitrary large distances. By interfacing matter-based quantum processors and photonic communication channels, light-matter entanglement is regarded as a fundamental building block for future applications such as the quantum repeater [5] and quantum networks. In addition, this new kind of entanglement would allow, e.g., quantum teleportation [6] of quantum states of light onto matter [4,7] as well as the heralded generation of entanglement between quantum memories [8] via entanglement swapping [9]. Light-matter entanglement is thus not only crucial for long range quantum communication but forms the basis for a first loophole-free test of Bell's inequality with a pair of entangled atoms at remote locations [3,10].

So far, three different approaches entangling light and matter have been pursued. The spontaneous decay in a lambda-type transition of a single trapped atom or ion enables one to entangle the internal degree of freedom of the emitted photon with the spin state of the atom [1,3]. Experiments in this direction recently achieved the observation of entanglement between two individually trapped ions [8], the remote preparation of an atomic quantum memory [11], and the realization of a single-atom single-photon quantum interface based on optical high- Q cavities [12]. Other approaches are based on entanglement between coherently scattered photons and collective spin excitations in atomic ensembles [2,7,13] and entanglement between continuous variables of light and matter [4,14].

The relevance of light-matter entanglement for quantum networking arises from the fact that it establishes non-classical correlations between a localized matter-based quantum memory and an optical carrier of quantum information which can easily be sent to a distant location. Together with appropriate quantum communication protocols like quantum teleportation, this allows to map photonic quantum information into quantum memories, to

buffer quantum information, and to reconvert it later on again to photonic quantum carriers. In this context, decoherence of the photonic quantum channel, as well as, decoherence of the matter-based quantum memory are important figures of merit setting a limit how far quantum information can be distributed or how long this information can be stored, respectively. Therefore, the ability to generate and preserve light-matter entanglement over large distances [15] opens the possibility for long-distance distribution of quantum information [16].

In this Letter, we report the first direct observation of entanglement between the internal state of a single trapped ⁸⁷Rb atom and the polarization state of a single photon which has passed 300 m optical fiber. This is achieved by actively stabilizing both the birefringence of the optical fiber link, as well as, ambient magnetic fields in order to minimize dephasing of the atomic memory qubit, stored in the atomic ground state $5^2S_{1/2}$, $F = 1$, $m_F = \pm 1$. Detailed coherence measurements of the atomic qubit show that photonic quantum information can be stored for about 150 μ s.

In our experiment, entanglement between the spin of a single optically trapped ⁸⁷Rb atom and the polarization of a photon is generated in the spontaneous emission process in a lambda-type transition [3], resulting in the maximally entangled atom-photon state

$$|\Psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|1, -1\rangle|\sigma^+\rangle + |1, +1\rangle|\sigma^-\rangle). \quad (1)$$

Here the two circular polarization states $\{|\sigma^+\rangle, |\sigma^-\rangle\}$ of the photon define the photonic qubit, and the angular momentum states $\{|F=1, m_F=-1\rangle := |\downarrow_z\rangle, |F=1, m_F=+1\rangle := |\uparrow_z\rangle\}$ the atomic qubit, respectively. While the atom is spatially localized in the optical dipole trap, the emitted photon is coupled into a single-mode optical fiber of 300 m length and guided to a separate optical breadboard at a distance of 3.5 m within the same lab where the polarization analysis is performed. To mea-

sure and compensate drifts of the fiber birefringence, reference laser pulses with two complementary polarizations (V , $+45^\circ$) are sent through the optical fiber (incorporating a fiber-based dynamic polarization controller) and the respective output polarizations are analyzed with a reference polarimeter [see Fig. 1(b)]. Based on the difference between input and output polarization, a software algorithm calculates new parameters for the dynamic polarization controller thereby optimizing the alignment. One such step takes 0.7 s, which is currently limited by the switching speed of the optomechanical shutters. These steps are repeated iteratively until input and output polarizations are identical within 99.9% [17]. Once the algorithm has compensated the fiber birefringence, typically after 10 steps, single photons from the atom are sent through the fiber. Under lab conditions, it was sufficient to repeat this algorithm every 10 min. To verify atom-photon entanglement, the internal atomic spin state is measured locally in two complementary measurement bases σ_x and σ_y with the help of a stimulated-Raman-adiabatic-passage tech-

FIG. 1 (color online). Schematic of long-distance atom-photon entanglement. (a) During the spontaneous decay of a single optically trapped ^{87}Rb atom on the transition $5^2P_{3/2}$, $F' = 0 \rightarrow 5^2S_{1/2}$, $F = 1$ the polarization of the emitted photon gets entangled with the final spin state of the atom. (b) The emitted photon is coupled into a single-mode optical fiber and communicated to a remote location where a polarization analysis is performed. To overcome thermally and mechanically induced fluctuations of the fiber birefringence, an active polarization compensation is used. Therefore reference laser pulses are sent through the optical fiber and the output polarizations are characterized in a reference polarimeter. With the help of a software algorithm and a dynamic polarization controller it is ensured that input and output polarizations are identical.

nique [3,18] and correlated with the polarization analysis of the photon. The bare photon detection efficiency typically is 1.2×10^{-3} , including coupling losses into the single-mode optical fiber and the limited quantum efficiency of the single-photon detectors. Together with transmission losses in the optical fiber and coupling losses of the dynamic polarization controller, this results in the total detection efficiency of 0.6×10^{-3} . The final event rate is 15 min^{-1} , which is mainly caused by frequent reloading of the dipole trap after 50% of the atomic state measurements [3]. For the analysis of entanglement, we determined the probability of detecting the atomic qubit in $|\downarrow\rangle_x$ and $|\downarrow\rangle_y$ conditioned on the projection of the photon onto the states $1/\sqrt{2}(|\sigma^+\rangle \pm e^{2i\beta}|\sigma^-\rangle)$ [see Figs. 2(a) and 2(b)]. For $\beta = 0^\circ$ the Si avalanche photo-diodes APD_1 and APD_2 analyze the photonic qubit in the eigenstates $|H\rangle := 1/\sqrt{2}(|\sigma^+\rangle + |\sigma^-\rangle)$ and $|V\rangle := 1/\sqrt{2}(|\sigma^+\rangle - |\sigma^-\rangle)$ of $\hat{\sigma}_x$, whereas for $\beta = 45^\circ$ APD_1 and APD_2 project onto the eigenstates $|+45^\circ\rangle := 1/\sqrt{2}(|\sigma^+\rangle - i|\sigma^-\rangle)$ and $|-45^\circ\rangle := 1/\sqrt{2}(|\sigma^+\rangle + i|\sigma^-\rangle)$ of $\hat{\sigma}_y$. As expected, if a $|V\rangle$ -polarized photon is detected, the atom is found with high probability in the corresponding state $|\downarrow\rangle_x$, whereas if a $|H\rangle$ -polarized photon is registered the atom is with low

FIG. 2 (color online). Verification of atom-photon entanglement. Probability of detecting the atomic qubit in (a) $|\downarrow\rangle_x := 1/\sqrt{2}(|\uparrow\rangle_z - |\downarrow\rangle_z)$ and (b) $|\downarrow\rangle_y := 1/\sqrt{2}(|\uparrow\rangle_z - i|\downarrow\rangle_z)$ conditioned on the detection of the photon in detector APD_1 or APD_2 , where the photonic qubit is projected onto the states $1/\sqrt{2}(|\sigma^+\rangle \pm e^{2i\beta}|\sigma^-\rangle)$. The phase β can be set with a rotatable $\lambda/2$ wave plate in front of a polarizing beam splitter (PBS). For $\beta = 0^\circ$, respectively, $\beta/2 = 22.5^\circ$ the photon is analyzed in the complementary measurement bases σ_x and σ_y .

probability in the state $|\downarrow_x\rangle$. Observing similar correlations in the complementary σ_y basis of the atom [see Fig. 2(b)] confirms that the atom-photon pair is in the entangled state $|\Psi\rangle$ [see Eq. (1)]. To determine the degree of entanglement, sinusoidal functions were fitted onto the measured atom-photon correlation data. From the fits we infer a visibility of $V_{\sigma_x} = 0.85 \pm 0.03$ for the analysis of the atomic qubit in σ_x and $V_{\sigma_y} = 0.75 \pm 0.03$ for σ_y , respectively. The limited visibility of the atom-photon correlations is caused mainly by errors in the atomic state detection (7%), accidental photon detection events due to dark counts of the single-photon detectors (3%), errors in the preparation of the initial state (1%), polarization drifts in the optical fiber during successive stabilization sequences of the dynamic polarization compensation (1%), and residual shot-to-shot dephasing of the atomic qubit due to fluctuations of the ambient magnetic field. For the significantly reduced visibility in the atomic σ_y basis we suppose residual magnetic fields along the x axis, which lead to Larmor precession into the additional Zeeman sublevel $m_F = 0$ of the $5^2S_{1/2}$, $F = 1$ hyperfine ground level [19]. To estimate the atom-photon entanglement fidelity $F_{\text{at-ph}}$, we assume that errors in the atomic and photonic state detection are isotropic in all three complementary measurement bases (white noise). Herewith, we derive a minimum fidelity $F_{\text{at-ph}}$ of 0.85 ± 0.02 .

For future applications in long-distance quantum communication, absorption losses and depolarization of the photonic qubit in optical fibers are important figures of merit, thereby limiting the distance over which quantum information can be distributed. Another crucial criterion for these applications will be the ability to store quantum information in quantum memories, which show long coherence times. So far, for quantum memories based on Zeeman qubits of neutral atoms, experimental coherence times of several $10 \mu\text{s}$ have been demonstrated [7,15]. In principle, clock-state quantum memories can have much longer coherence times [20], yet, manipulation of the corresponding light-matter entanglement is far less practical.

In order to carefully distinguish between photonic and atomic decoherence, we characterized the coherence properties of the atomic quantum memory by measuring the precession of the atomic spin in a magnetic field. This is achieved via quantum state tomography of the atomic ground level $5^2S_{1/2}$, $F = 1$, reconstruction of the respective density matrix $\rho = r|\chi\rangle\langle\chi| + (1-r)\hat{1}/3$ [19], and determination of the corresponding purity parameter r . In contrast to the fidelity, $F = \langle\Phi|\rho|\Phi\rangle$, which is the overlap between the measured density matrix ρ and a pure target state $|\Phi\rangle$, the purity parameter, here $r = \sqrt{1/2[3\text{tr}(\rho^2) - 1]}$, is related to the coherent fraction of the density matrix with respect to the *closest* pure state $|\chi\rangle$ (which is in general unknown). Therefore r is ideally suited to quantify decoherence effects of our atomic quantum memory.

In our spin-precession experiments, the 300 m optical fiber of the first experiment is replaced by a 5 m one, leading to a negligible time delay of 25 ns between the preparation of the entangled atom-photon pair and the initialization of the atomic spin state via a projective polarization measurement of the photon. The magnetic bias field is controlled via additional Helmholtz coils and an active feedback loop with an accuracy of $|B| < 2 \text{ mG}$. After the atomic spin has freely evolved in the magnetic field for defined time periods, tomography of the final atomic spin state was performed by measuring populations of the atomic eigenstates of the Pauli spin operators $\hat{\sigma}_x$, $\hat{\sigma}_y$, and $\hat{\sigma}_z$ [11]. In the case where a small magnetic guiding field of 5.5 mG is applied along the quantization axis z , we observe the expected Larmor precession of a spin-1/2 atom (see Fig. 3), with a $1/e$ dephasing time of $150 \mu\text{s}$. In the general case where a magnetic guiding field is not along the z axis or in the case where no guiding field is applied, the atom can precess out of the qubit subspace $\{|1, -1\rangle, |1, +1\rangle\}$ into the $|F = 1, m_F = 0\rangle$ Zeeman state of the $5^2S_{1/2}$, $F = 1$ hyperfine ground level. Thus, for complete characterization of decoherence effects it is necessary to reconstruct the 3×3 spin-1 density matrix ρ . This is possible with certain constraints. Coherences between the states $|1, \pm 1\rangle$ and $|1, 0\rangle$ cannot be measured with the present atomic state detection technique, as the applied stimulated-Raman-adiabatic-passage pulses analyze only the $\{|1, -1\rangle, |1, +1\rangle\}$ qubit subspace in a complete way [3,11]. However, the population in the $|1, 0\rangle$ state can be inferred as the population missing in the $\{|1, -1\rangle, |1, +1\rangle\}$ subspace. To reconstruct the density matrix ρ of the spin-1 state, we apply a worst-case assumption that there is no coherence between the $|1, 0\rangle$ state and the others, and set the corresponding components to 0. The resulting purity parameter r thus is a conservative lower bound on the effective coherence of the atomic state.

In a second measurement run, no guiding field is applied (corresponding to the situation of a magnetic zero field with an accuracy of $\pm 2 \text{ mG}$) and dephasing of the atomic

FIG. 3 (color online). Spin precession of the atomic states $\{|\uparrow_x\rangle := 1/\sqrt{2}(|\uparrow_z\rangle + |\downarrow_z\rangle), |\downarrow_x\rangle := 1/\sqrt{2}(|\uparrow_z\rangle - |\downarrow_z\rangle)\}$, as a guiding field of 5.5 mG is applied along the quantization axis z . After the temporal evolution the population P of the $|\downarrow_x\rangle$ state is measured.

FIG. 4 (color online). Temporal evolution of the lower bound of the purity parameter r as the atom is prepared initially in the states (a) $\{|\uparrow\rangle_x := 1/\sqrt{2}(|\uparrow\rangle_z + |\downarrow\rangle_z), |\downarrow\rangle_x := 1/\sqrt{2}(|\uparrow\rangle_z - |\downarrow\rangle_z)\}$, (b) $\{|\uparrow\rangle_z := |1, +1\rangle, |\downarrow\rangle_z := |1, -1\rangle\}$. Each measurement point results from a partial quantum state tomography of the spin-1 ground level $5^2S_{1/2}$, $F = 1$.

superposition states $1/\sqrt{2}(|1, -1\rangle \pm |1, +1\rangle)$ is analyzed by reconstruction of the minimal purity parameter r . Here we find transversal $1/e$ dephasing times of $T_2^* = 75..150 \mu\text{s}$; see Fig. 4(a). For the states $|1, \pm 1\rangle$, see Fig. 4(b), the longitudinal dephasing times are estimated by extrapolation to be >0.5 ms. The faster dephasing of superposition states show that fluctuations, respectively, shot-to-shot noise of the effective magnetic field, are mainly along the quantization axis z . This effect is due to a small fraction of circularly polarized dipole-trap light (below 1%), which leads in combination with a finite atomic temperature of $150 \mu\text{K}$ to a position-dependent differential light shift [19].

In this Letter, we successfully demonstrated the generation and verification of entanglement between a single trapped neutral atom and single photon separated by 300 m optical fiber. Our implementation includes an active stabilization of ambient magnetic fields with an accuracy of $|B| < 2$ mG, resulting in a dephasing time of the atomic memory level $5^2S_{1/2}$, $F = 1$ of $\approx 150 \mu\text{s}$. Longer coherence times could be reached with higher accuracy of the polarization of the dipole-trap light, lower temperature of the trapped atom, and better stability of the magnetic field. Nevertheless, together with the implemented stable optical

fiber link, also the current setup should allow to entangle two optically trapped ^{87}Rb atoms at locations spatially separated by several 100 m, ready for future applications in long-distance quantum networking with neutral atoms and a loophole-free test of Bell's inequality [3].

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3.3 Heralded entanglement between widely separated quantum memories

Entanglement between stationary qubits over large distances is the key resource of the quantum repeater [7]. Central for this application is, that the entanglement can be generated in a heralded way, i.e. one knows if an entangled pair of stationary qubits is available for further process steps such as the connection of successive repeater segments and entanglement purification via local CNOT operations.

In this section I will report on our most recent experimental achievement, i.e. the first heralded preparation and analysis of entanglement between two single Rb-87 atoms at a distance of 20 m. This is realized by entanglement swapping [10], utilizing two entangled atom-photon pairs as primary physical resource. In detail, the remote atoms are entangled in a first step in a spontaneous emission process with a single photon each [43, 46]. The photons are collected via large numerical aperture objectives, coupled into single mode optical fibers, and guided to an intermediate location (see Fig. 3.2). There the photons are overlapped on a 50 : 50 beam splitter (BS) and subject to an interferometric Bell-state measurement (BSM). A coincident detection of two orthogonally polarized photons in either the same or two different output ports of the BS allows us to project the photons onto the polarization entangled Bell-states $|\Psi^+\rangle_{Ph}$ or $|\Psi^-\rangle_{Ph}$ respectively [54], thereby swapping the corresponding entanglement onto the atoms. Beside two highly entangled atom-photon pairs [43, 46], a high-fidelity Bell-state measurement (BSM) on the interfering photons is crucial for achieving this task.

3.3.1 Bell-State Measurement via Two-Photon Interference

We employ a Bell-state measurement based on the Hong-Ou-Mandel interference of two indistinguishable photons on a beam splitter [53]. Here, photon pairs in a symmetric state of the spatial input modes of the BS lead to bunching, i.e. both photons leave the beam splitter as twins in either of the two spatial output ports, while for an anti-symmetric spatial state the photons leave the BS in two different output ports. For the polarization-entangled Bell-state $|\Psi^+\rangle_{Ph} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|H\rangle|V\rangle + |V\rangle|H\rangle)$ the respective spatial part of the wavefunction is symmetric. This results in the coincident detection of a horizontally (H) and a vertically (V) polarized photon in the same spatial output port of the beam splitter [54] (cross-correlations H_1V_1 or H_2V_2). Contrary, for the antisymmetric polarization entangled two-photon state $|\Psi^-\rangle_{Ph} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|H\rangle|V\rangle - |V\rangle|H\rangle)$ the respective spatial part of the wavefunction is also antisymmetric, i.e. the photons leave the BS in different spatial output ports leading to cross-correlations H_1V_2 or H_2V_1 [54]. The other two symmetric Bell-states $|\Phi^\pm\rangle_{Ph}$ give yet a different result but can not be distinguished from each other [54]. Thus, by detecting one of the four coincidences mentioned above, we project the incoming photons unambiguously on a Bell-state, thereby heralding the generation of entanglement between the separated atoms.

Figure 3.2: Principle of atom-atom entanglement generation via entanglement swapping. The trapped atoms are entangled with a photon each in a spontaneous emission process (lambda-type atomic transition). The photons are coupled into optical fibers and guided to an intermediate location where a Bell-state measurement is performed, thereby swapping the entanglement onto the atoms.

The fidelity of this Bell-state measurement is crucially influenced by the degree of indistinguishability of the arriving photons, requiring a high degree of spatial, temporal and spectral mode overlap. This is achieved experimentally by using a fiber BS, synchronizing the excitation procedures of the atoms to better than 500 ps (which is far below the lifetime of the excited atomic state of 26.2 ns), matching exactly the shapes of the interfering photon wave-packets, as well as by eliminating frequency differences of the emitted photons (see *W. Rosenfeld et al., Optics and Spectroscopy 111, 535 (2011)*).

In order to quantify the fidelity of the Bell-state measurement, we perform second order interference experiments with single photons emitted by and entangled with a single atom each. In this context the atoms can be considered as sources of unpolarized light, i.e. at the input of the BSM-arrangement all four photonic Bell-states $\{|\Psi^\pm\rangle_{Ph}, |\Phi^\pm\rangle_{Ph}\}$ appear with equal probability. To quantify e.g. the fidelity of a projection onto the $|\Psi^-\rangle_{Ph}$ Bell-state we measure polarization dependent cross-correlations, i.e. number of coincident detections of photons leaving the beam splitter in two different spatial output modes within a coincidence time window of 120 ns. In detail we record the number of cross-correlations H_1V_2 and V_1V_2 . For normalization these numbers are also measured for distinguishable photons originating from two different successive optical excitation trials (here $\tau = \pm 5.5 \mu\text{s}$) of the two atoms. Whereas the correlations H_1V_2 at $\tau = 0$

Figure 3.3: Polarization dependent two-photon cross-correlations during entanglement swapping. (a) H_1V_2 correlations at zero detection time-difference signal “clean” entanglement-swapping events. (b) V_1V_2 correlations at $\tau = 0$ are a measure for unwanted two-photon emissions of the atoms during a single optical excitation trial. (c) R_1L_2 correlations at $\tau = 0$ signal entanglement-swapping events contaminated by two-photon emissions. (d) The suppression of L_1L_2 correlations at $\tau = 0$ (Hong-Ou-Mandel dip) is used to ascertain the fidelity of the Bell-state measurement. The number of correlations at $\tau = \pm 5.5 \mu\text{s}$ (originating from successive excitation trials of the atoms) is used for normalization.

ns signal a successful projection onto the $|\Psi^-\rangle_{Ph}$ Bell-state, V_1V_2 correlations ideally should not show up due to destructive interference (Hong-Ou-Mandel effect). I.e., the suppression of V_1V_2 correlations is expected to be a measure for the quality of the Bell-state projection.

In our measurements however (see Fig. 3.3(b)) a significant amount of V_1V_2 correlations at $\tau = 0$ ns is observed. This large number of “unwanted” correlations results mainly from residual two-photon emissions from the same atom. Detailed experimental studies show that due to a relatively long optical excitation pulse length of 26 ns and the internal level structure of Rb-87 each atom emits with 2.5% a second photon within one excitation trial [51]. This is due to off-resonant excitation to the $5^2P_{3/2}, F' = 1$ level, which is possible if the first photon was emitted already within the duration of

Figure 3.4: Generation of polarization entangled photon-pairs via off-resonant optical excitation of a single Rb-87 atom. The entanglement is employed for suppression of unwanted two-photon events in the interferometric Bell-state projection.

the excitation pulse. After the first spontaneous decay to $5^2S_{1/2}, F = 1, m_F = \pm 1$, the second time the atom decays with 81% (this follows from the respective dipole transition matrix elements [91]) back to the $5^2S_{1/2}, F = 1, m_F = 0$ state (see Fig. 3.4, right), generating the polarization entangled two-photon state $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\sigma^- \rangle_1 |\sigma^+ \rangle_2 + |\sigma^+ \rangle_1 |\sigma^- \rangle_2) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|H \rangle_1 |H \rangle_2 + |V \rangle_1 |V \rangle_2)$. Such emitted photon pairs lead in the BSM to correlations $H_1 H_2$ and $V_1 V_2$, apparently diminishing the visibility of the Hong-Ou-Mandel dip. However, the quality of the Bell-state projection is not affected, as these correlations do not herald a Bell-state projection. In order to ascertain the fidelity of the BSM we change the analysis direction of the photons during the two-photon interference measurements. Performing the BSM in the σ_z basis (defined by $\{|R \rangle := |\sigma^- \rangle; |L \rangle := |\sigma^+ \rangle\}$) two-photon emissions accumulate in the detector combinations $R_1 L_2$ and $L_1 R_2$, but not in $R_1 R_2$ and $L_1 L_2$ (see Fig. 3.3(c) and (d)). In order to determine the visibility of the BSM we finally compare the normalized number of correlations $H_1 V_2$ (signaling a clean entanglement swapping event) with the normalized number of correlations $L_1 L_2$. For typical experimental conditions we achieve an entanglement swapping fidelity of 93..95%.

3.3.2 Atom-Atom Entanglement via Entanglement Swapping

Combining all presented methods we are now able to generate and characterize entanglement between two distant atoms. In the following article “*Heralded entanglement between widely separated atoms*” (*J. Hofmann et al., submitted to Science (2012)*) we report on the preparation and analysis of entanglement between two single Rb-87 atoms over a distance of 20 m via entanglement swapping [10]. The scheme starts with entan-

gling the spin of each of the two atoms with the polarization state of a spontaneously emitted photon [43]. The photons are guided to a Bell state measurement setup where the two-photon polarization state is projected onto an entangled state, thereby providing the heralding signal and entangling the atomic spins. In a final step we evaluate the entanglement between the atomic spins via correlation measurements in two complementary measurement bases. The experimental atom-atom entanglement fidelity was high enough to observe a clear violation of a Bell inequality. This achievement forms the starting point for new experiments in quantum information science, as well as for fundamental tests of quantum mechanics.

Heralded entanglement between widely separated atoms

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Entanglement is the essential feature of quantum mechanics. Remarkably, observers of two or more entangled particles will find correlations in their measurement results, that can not be explained by classical statistics. To make it a useful resource, particularly for scalable long-distance quantum communication, the heralded generation of entanglement between distant massive quantum systems is necessary. We report on the creation and analysis of heralded entanglement between spins of two single Rb-87 atoms trapped independently 20 meters apart. Our results illustrate the viability of an integral resource for quantum information science, as well as for fundamental tests of quantum mechanics.

Entanglement between distant stationary quantum systems will be a key resource for future applications in the field of long-distance quantum communication, like quantum repeaters (1) and quantum networks (2). At the same time, it is an essential ingredient for new experiments on the foundations of physics, in particular for a first loophole-free test of Bell's inequality (3–5). Central to all these applications is the heralded generation of entanglement, i.e., a signal is provided once an entangled pair is successfully prepared.

Up to now, (unheralded) entanglement between separated massive quantum objects has been achieved for various systems (6, 7), even over 21 m (8). Heralded entanglement has been demonstrated with cold atomic ensembles (9, 10), single trapped ions (11, 12) and diamond crystals (13), albeit over short distances in a single setup only. For the realization of heralded entanglement over long distances single neutral atoms are promising candidates. In view of future applications, several important milestones have already been demonstrated for such systems: manipulation of atomic quantum registers (14), storage of quantum-information (8, 15–17), fast

Figure 1: (A) Experimental setting: two independent single atom traps, operated in separate laboratories. Single photons emitted by the atoms interfere on a 50-50 fiber beam splitter (fiber BS) and are detected by avalanche photodiodes (APDs) behind a polarization analyzer consisting of half- and quarterwave plates ($\lambda/2$ and $\lambda/4$) and polarizing beam splitters (PBS). Simultaneous detection of two photons in particular combinations of detectors constitutes a Bell state measurement (BSM) on the photons and heralds the generation of entanglement between the separated atoms. (B) Scheme for generation of single photons whose polarization is entangled with the atomic spin. (C) Histograms of arrival times of the single photons from trap 1 (blue) and trap 2 (red). The photonic wave-packets are overlapped by synchronizing the two excitation procedures to better than 500 ps.

and highly efficient state analysis (18), deterministic quantum gates between nearby trapped atoms via Rydberg-blockade (19, 20), and distribution of light-matter entanglement over large distances (21).

We report on the preparation and analysis of heralded entanglement between two single ^{87}Rb atoms over a distance of 20 m via entanglement swapping (22). The scheme starts with entangling the spin of each of the two atoms with the polarization state of a spontaneously emitted photon (23). The photons are guided to a Bell state measurement setup (BSM) where the two-photon polarization state is projected onto an entangled state, thereby providing the heralding signal. In a final step we evaluate the entanglement between the atomic spins.

Our experimental arrangement (Fig. 1A) consists of two independently operated experiments, here called trap 1 and trap 2 (24), which are situated in two laboratories and equipped with their own laser and control systems. In each experiment we load a single ^{87}Rb atom into

an optical dipole trap (25). The typical lifetime of a single trapped atom is 5 – 10 s, limited mainly by heating during the experimental process and collisions with background gas. Photons emitted by the atoms are coupled into single-mode optical fibers and guided to the BSM-arrangement next to trap 1. The lengths of the optical fibers from trap 1 and trap 2 to the BSM are 5 m and 30 m, respectively. In order to compensate for polarization drifts induced by temperature changes and mechanical stress in the 30 m fiber, an automatic polarization stabilization (21) is used. The interferometric BSM arrangement consists of a 50-50 single-mode fiber beam splitter (BS) with polarizing beam splitters (PBS) in each of the output ports. Additional half- and quarterwave plates allow us to select the measurement basis for the BSM and the atom-photon entanglement measurements. Finally, photons are detected by 4 avalanche photodiodes (APDs).

First, we verify atom-photon entanglement in each experiment separately. The generation of an entangled atom-photon state starts by preparing the atom in the initial state $5^2S_{1/2}$, $|F = 1, m_F = 0\rangle$ (Fig. 1B) via optical pumping. Then the atom is excited to the state $5^2P_{3/2}$, $|F' = 0, m_{F'} = 0\rangle$ by a short optical pulse (FWHM pulse length 21 ns). In the following spontaneous decay the polarization of a single photon emitted into the collection optics (defining the quantization axis z) is entangled with the atomic spin (23), yielding the state

$$|\Psi\rangle_{AP} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\downarrow\rangle_z |L\rangle + |\uparrow\rangle_z |R\rangle) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\downarrow\rangle_x |V\rangle + |\uparrow\rangle_x |H\rangle),$$

where $|L\rangle$, $|R\rangle$ denote the left- and right-circular and $|H\rangle$, $|V\rangle$ the horizontal and vertical linear polarization states of the photon. The atomic qubit is defined by the Zeeman states $|m_F = +1\rangle$ and $|m_F = -1\rangle$ of the ground level $5^2S_{1/2}$, $F = 1$ which we associate with spin orientations $|\uparrow\rangle_z$ and $|\downarrow\rangle_z$, respectively. Preparation and excitation of the atom is repeated until a photon is detected. Taking into account additional cooling periods required to counteract heating of the atom, the preparation and excitation of the atom can be performed 50×10^3 times per second. The overall efficiency for detecting the photon after an excitation in trap 1 (trap 2) is $\eta_1 = 0.9 \times 10^{-3}$ ($\eta_2 = 1.25 \times 10^{-3}$). These numbers include the excitation probability, the collection and coupling efficiencies as well as losses in the optics, and also the quantum efficiency of the photodetectors. Polarization analysis of the single photons is performed with the BSM arrangement, which also serves to monitor fluorescence of the atom inside the trap.

In order to evaluate atom-photon entanglement, conditioned on the detection of the emitted photon the internal spin state of the atom is read out (23). The detection process consists of a Zeeman state-selective stimulated Raman adiabatic passage (STIRAP) (26) with subsequent hyperfine state detection. This process can be considered as a projection of the atom onto the state $\cos(\gamma) |\uparrow\rangle_x + \sin(\gamma) |\downarrow\rangle_x$, where γ is the angle of linear polarization of the STIRAP pulse defining the measurement basis (the angle of the corresponding direction of the atomic spin is 2γ). In atom-photon correlation measurements we register event numbers $N_{SS'}^{(\gamma,\delta)}$, where $S, S' \in \{|\uparrow\rangle, |\downarrow\rangle\}$ are the eigenstates of the spin of the atom and the photon along their respective measurement directions defined by γ and δ . Figure 2 shows the resulting correlations between atomic spin and photon polarization measurements for both traps separately.

Figure 2: Atom-photon correlations for trap 1 (A) and trap 2 (B). The graphs show the measured correlation probabilities $\frac{1}{N}(N_{\uparrow\uparrow}^{(\gamma,0^\circ)} + N_{\downarrow\downarrow}^{(\gamma,0^\circ)})$ (red \blacktriangle with dashed lines), $\frac{1}{N}(N_{\uparrow\uparrow}^{(\gamma,45^\circ)} + N_{\downarrow\downarrow}^{(\gamma,45^\circ)})$ (green \blacktriangledown with dot-dashed lines) and the anti-correlation probabilities $\frac{1}{N}(N_{\uparrow\downarrow}^{(\gamma,0^\circ)} + N_{\downarrow\uparrow}^{(\gamma,0^\circ)})$ (blue \blacksquare with dotted lines) $\frac{1}{N}(N_{\uparrow\downarrow}^{(\gamma,45^\circ)} + N_{\downarrow\uparrow}^{(\gamma,45^\circ)})$ (black \blacklozenge with solid lines), $\gamma \in \{\alpha, \beta\}$ as a function of the respective atomic analysis angle. Each point is deduced from $N = 1200 - 2400$ events, where N is the sum over the four possible measurement outcomes.

In these measurements the photon was detected in H/V basis ($\delta = 0^\circ$) and in $\pm 45^\circ$ basis ($\delta = 45^\circ$), while the atomic measurement angle α (trap 1) and β (trap 2) was varied between 0° and 180° . The visibilities $V^{(\delta)}$ of the correlation curves obtained by least-squares fits are $V_1^{(0^\circ)} = 0.869 \pm 0.006$, $V_1^{(45^\circ)} = 0.900 \pm 0.006$ for trap 1 and $V_2^{(0^\circ)} = 0.895 \pm 0.004$, $V_2^{(45^\circ)} = 0.901 \pm 0.005$ for trap 2, where the given errors are the expected statistical 1σ deviations. These high visibilities, limited mainly by the quality of the atomic state read-out, demonstrate that atom-photon entanglement is reliably generated and detected with high fidelity in both traps.

The second crucial condition for preparing a highly entangled state of two trapped atoms is a high-fidelity Bell-state measurement of the photons, i.e., projecting them onto maximally entangled states. We use interferometric Bell-state analysis based on the Hong-Ou-Mandel effect (27). This two-photon detection scheme does not require interferometric stability on a wavelength scale, thereby relaxing the experimental requirements for long-distance quantum communication. In general, at a beam-splitter, bunching (anti-bunching) of two photons in a symmetric (anti-symmetric) state enables one to identify Bell-states. In our case a coincidence in detectors H_1V_1 or H_2V_2 (Fig. 1A) signals projection of the photons onto the state $|\Psi^+\rangle_{Ph} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|H\rangle|V\rangle + |V\rangle|H\rangle)$, and the coincidences H_1V_2 or H_2V_1 indicate projection onto the state $|\Psi^-\rangle_{Ph} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|H\rangle|V\rangle - |V\rangle|H\rangle)$, respectively. The other two symmetric Bell-states $|\Phi^\pm\rangle_{Ph} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|H\rangle|H\rangle \pm |V\rangle|V\rangle)$ give yet a different result but can not be distinguished from each other (28–30). Thus, by detecting one of the four coincidences mentioned above, we project the incoming photons unambiguously on a Bell-state, thereby heralding the generation of entanglement between the separated atoms.

The visibility of the two-photon interference, which determines the fidelity of the Bell-state

measurement, depends crucially on temporal, spatial and spectral indistinguishability of the arriving photons. Experimentally the temporal overlap is achieved by synchronizing the two excitation procedures in trap 1 and trap 2 to better than 500 ps, which is far below the lifetime of the excited atomic state of 26.2 ns, and by exactly matching the shapes of the interfering wave-packets (Fig. 1C). The single-mode fiber beam-splitter guarantees spatial mode overlap of unity. Frequency differences of the emitted photons are minimized by zeroing all relevant fields (31). Further reduction of the fidelity of the Bell-state measurement arises from two-photon emission by a single atom due to off-resonant excitation of the atom to the $5^2P_{3/2}$, $F' = 1$ level (see Fig. 1B, fig. S1) if the first photon is emitted already within the duration of the excitation pulse. However, due to the structure of the involved atomic levels, with a probability of 78.1% a polarization-entangled state $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|H\rangle_1|H\rangle_2 + |V\rangle_1|V\rangle_2)$ of the two consecutively emitted photons is formed (32). These events are registered as coincidences H_1H_2 and V_1V_2 and do not herald projection onto a Bell state. Reduction of the fidelity is therefore due to the remaining two-photon emissions and due to dark counts of the detectors. Based on additional calibration measurements we estimate a fidelity of the Bell-state projection of at least 92% (32).

By combining all methods described above we are able to generate and characterize entanglement between two distant atoms. In each of the two experiments a single atom is captured and the atom-photon entangling sequences are repeated until two photons are detected within a time-window of 120 ns in the BSM arrangement. With a coincidence probability of 0.54×10^{-6} , a repetition rate of 50 kHz, and by taking into account the fraction of time when an atom was present in each of the traps of 0.35 we arrive at an atom-atom entanglement rate of about $1/106 \text{ s}^{-1}$. A valid twofold detection, i.e., registration of $|\Psi^\pm\rangle_{Ph}$, heralds projection of the atoms onto the state $|\Psi^\pm\rangle_{AA} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow\rangle_x|\downarrow\rangle_x \pm |\downarrow\rangle_x|\uparrow\rangle_x)$. Subsequently, measurements of the atomic states are performed $1.2 \mu\text{s}$ (trap 1) and $0.95 \mu\text{s}$ (trap 2) after the coincidence detection (fig. S2). These times are far below the coherence time of the single atomic qubit state of $\tau_c = 75 \mu\text{s}$ (17) and the coherence time of the entangled atom-atom state, which we expect to be at least $\tau_c/2$, and thus does not limit the quality of our experiment (agreeably, the atom-atom entanglement rate and τ_c need substantial improvement for future quantum repeater scenarios).

To evaluate the atom-atom entanglement we perform measurements of the atomic spins in two bases. We have chosen analysis angles $\alpha = 90^\circ$ and $\alpha = 135^\circ$, while β is varied in steps of 22.5° between 90° and 180° , or between 45° and 135° , respectively. The obtained correlations are shown for the detection of the photonic $|\Psi^-\rangle_{Ph}$ state (Figs. 3A, B) and for the $|\Psi^+\rangle_{Ph}$ state (Figs. 3C, D). By fitting sinusoidal functions to the data points we obtain visibilities $V^{(\alpha)}$ of $V_{\Psi^-}^{(90^\circ)} = 0.788 \pm 0.031$, $V_{\Psi^-}^{(135^\circ)} = 0.728 \pm 0.032$ for the $|\Psi^-\rangle_{AA}$ state and $V_{\Psi^+}^{(90^\circ)} = 0.813 \pm 0.030$, $V_{\Psi^+}^{(135^\circ)} = 0.723 \pm 0.034$ for the $|\Psi^+\rangle_{AA}$ state, respectively. For estimation of the fidelity we assume that the visibility in the third (unmeasured) conjugate basis is equal to the lower of the two measured ones, arriving at $F_{\Psi^-} = 0.811 \pm 0.028$ and $F_{\Psi^+} = 0.815 \pm 0.028$. These numbers prove that in both cases an entangled state of the two atoms is generated. Moreover, the average visibilities $\bar{V}_{\Psi^\pm} = \frac{1}{2}(V_{\Psi^\pm}^{(90^\circ)} + V_{\Psi^\pm}^{(135^\circ)})$ of $\bar{V}_{\Psi^-} = 0.768 \pm 0.023$ and $\bar{V}_{\Psi^+} = 0.758 \pm 0.023$, respectively, are well above the threshold of 0.707 necessary to violate

Figure 3: Atom-atom correlations obtained after Bell-state projection of the photons onto state $|\Psi^-\rangle_{Ph}$ (A,B) and $|\Psi^+\rangle_{Ph}$ (C,D), respectively. The measured correlation probabilities $\frac{1}{N}(N_{\uparrow\uparrow}^{(\alpha,\beta)} + N_{\downarrow\downarrow}^{(\alpha,\beta)})$ (red \blacktriangle with solid lines), and the anti-correlation probabilities $\frac{1}{N}(N_{\uparrow\downarrow}^{(\alpha,\beta)} + N_{\downarrow\uparrow}^{(\alpha,\beta)})$ (blue \blacktriangledown with dashed lines) are shown for two complementary measurement bases. Each point is deduced from $N = 170 - 190$ atom-atom events. The overall number of events in this measurement is 3637, acquired within about 107 hours.

Bell's inequality.

One of our main goals is to enable a future loophole-free test of Bell's inequality (3). Inserting the data from the above measurements into $\langle\sigma_\alpha\sigma_\beta\rangle = \frac{1}{N}(N_{\uparrow\uparrow}^{(\alpha,\beta)} + N_{\downarrow\downarrow}^{(\alpha,\beta)} - N_{\uparrow\downarrow}^{(\alpha,\beta)} - N_{\downarrow\uparrow}^{(\alpha,\beta)})$ we evaluated the parameter $S = |\langle\sigma_\alpha\sigma_\beta\rangle + \langle\sigma_{\alpha'}\sigma_\beta\rangle| + |\langle\sigma_\alpha\sigma_{\beta'}\rangle - \langle\sigma_{\alpha'}\sigma_{\beta'}\rangle|$ from the Clauser-Horne-Shimony-Holt-inequality $S \leq 2$, which holds for local-realistic theories (33). For the data from Fig. 3, using the settings $\alpha = 135^\circ$, $\beta = 67.5^\circ$; $\alpha = 135^\circ$, $\beta' = 112.5^\circ$; $\alpha' = 90^\circ$, $\beta' = 112.5^\circ$ together with $\alpha' = 90^\circ$, $\beta'' = 157.5^\circ$ (replacing $\beta = 67.5^\circ$), for all four heralding signals we obtain an S -value exceeding the limit of 2. Since a measurement result is obtained for each and every heralding signal, the average value of $S = 2.19 \pm 0.09$ for the first time yields definite violation without relying on the fair sampling assumption for a macroscopic distance.

Summarizing, in this experiment we demonstrated heralded entanglement between two atoms 20 m apart. It was high enough to violate a Bell-inequality, showing its suitability for quantum information applications such as device-independent quantum cryptography (34). The design of trap 2 allows rather straightforward extension of the distance between the two traps

to at least several hundred meters, limited only by transmission of photons in the optical fiber connection. Two distant entangled atoms form the elementary link of the quantum repeater, enabling efficient long-distance quantum communication. Together with efficient and fast atomic state detection (18), this experiment forms the basis for the first loophole-free Bell-experiment answering the longstanding question on whether a local realistic extension of quantum mechanics can be a valid description of nature.

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4 Remote preparation of an atomic quantum memory

Figure 4.1: Principle of Remote-State-Preparation.

Many new concepts in quantum communication like the quantum repeater [7, 12] or quantum networks [92] for distributed quantum computing require the faithful mapping of quantum information between photonic quantum channels and matter-based quantum memories and processors. Entanglement between matter and light is crucial for achieving this task. In the following work we experimentally prove the suitability of atom-photon entanglement as the interface between a memory device and the quantum communication channel. For this purpose we perform the full remote preparation of an atomic quantum memory via teleportation of an arbitrarily prepared quantum state of a single photon.

Similar to quantum teleportation [9, 93, 94, 39, 40], remote state preparation (RSP) [95, 96] starts with entanglement between two quantum systems (in our case atom-photon). Whereas in quantum teleportation the qubit to be transferred is carried by a third particle, in RSP it is encoded in an additional degree of freedom of the particle given to the sender, usually called Alice. The other one of the two particles of the entangled pair is sent to the receiver, called Bob, and will carry the qubit after the

successful termination of the protocol. This consists of two steps, first, a complete Bell-state measurement between the qubit encoding the quantum state to be sent and the entangled qubit of the sender. Second, the result obtained in this measurement (2 bits of classical information) is communicated to the receiver. Bob uses this information to perform one out of four well-defined, state independent transformations, thereby reconstructing or preparing the original state.

In the following contribution “*Remote Preparation of an Atomic Quantum Memory*” (W. Rosenfeld et al., *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 98, 050504 (2007)) we report the faithful remote preparation of the quantum state of a single-atom quantum memory applying the RSP teleportation protocol. We evaluated the performance of the scheme by the full tomography of the prepared atomic state, reaching an average fidelity of 82%. In contrast to many well-established experimental techniques in laser cooling and trapping of atoms, like optical pumping and coherent-population-trapping, the demonstrated quantum optical experiment does not introduce state dependency of the method. In fact it represents a universal tool to initialize any desired quantum state of a single trapped atom without the need of direct interaction between flying and stationary qubit.

Remote Preparation of an Atomic Quantum Memory

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Storage and distribution of quantum information are key elements of quantum information processing and future quantum communication networks. Here, using atom-photon entanglement as the main physical resource, we experimentally demonstrate the preparation of a distant atomic quantum memory. Applying a quantum teleportation protocol on a locally prepared state of a photonic qubit, we realized this so-called remote state preparation on a single, optically trapped ⁸⁷Rb atom. We evaluated the performance of this scheme by the full tomography of the prepared atomic state, reaching an average fidelity of 82%.

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Quantum information science has already shown many new possibilities for information processing and communication, most prominently, secure communication [1] and the efficient solution of certain computational problems which cannot be efficiently treated on a classical computer [2]. For future applications, such as links between quantum computers or long distance quantum communication, new devices are required. While photons are ideal for the transfer of qubits (as the generalization of the classical bit the basic entity of quantum information), matter carriers of the qubits, e.g., atoms, ions, superconducting circuits, or quantum dots are well suited for storage and processing. Many new concepts, for example, the quantum repeater [3] or quantum networks for distributed quantum computing thus require the faithful mapping of quantum information between photonic quantum channels and matter-based quantum memories and processors. Entanglement between matter and light is crucial for achieving this task.

So far, there are two methods experimentally investigated. The first employs atomic ensembles of about 10^6 – 10^{12} atoms to momentarily store quantum states of light. Recently, qubits encoded on single photons or qunits encoded in the quantum state of an electromagnetic field have been transferred to the collective state of atoms and vice versa [4,5]. An impressive experimental demonstration of a first quantum communication protocol, the quantum teleportation of coherent states of light onto an atomic ensemble, was reported very recently [6].

The second method is based on the recently achieved entanglement between a single atom and a single photon [7,8]. It applies directly to well-studied single quantum systems like trapped neutral atoms or ions, where various methods of quantum information storage and processing were already demonstrated, e.g., entanglement of up to 8 ions [9,10], creation of a cluster state involving tens of neutral atoms [11], or manipulations on a neutral atom quantum shift register [12]. Furthermore, this interface concept can be adopted to other qubit systems, like optically addressed quantum dots [13–15] or superconducting QED systems [16], stimulating novel applications in these areas as well.

Here we experimentally prove the suitability of atom-photon entanglement as the interface between a memory device and the quantum communication channel. For this purpose we perform the full remote preparation of an atomic quantum memory via teleportation of an arbitrarily prepared quantum state of a single photon.

Similar to quantum teleportation [17], remote state preparation (RSP) [18,19] starts with entanglement between two quantum systems (in our case atom-photon). Whereas in quantum teleportation the qubit to be transferred is carried by a third particle, in RSP it is encoded in an additional degree of freedom of the particle given to the sender, usually called Alice. The other one of the two particles of the entangled pair is sent to the receiver, called Bob, and will carry the qubit after the successful termination of the protocol. This consists of two steps, first, a complete Bell-state measurement between the qubit encoding the quantum state to be sent and the entangled qubit of the sender. Second, the result obtained in this measurement (2 bits of classical information) is communicated to the receiver. He uses this information to perform one out of four well-defined, state independent transformations, thereby reconstructing or preparing the original state. Recently, various approaches towards remote state preparation were studied experimentally with entangled photons [20], light beams [21], and nuclear magnetic spins [22]. However without expansion of the Hilbert space, and thus without the possibility of complete Bell-state analysis, such experiments are limited to a maximum efficiency of 50% and/or are introducing state dependency of the method.

To demonstrate the full RSP protocol, our experiment includes four steps: (i) Entanglement is generated between the spin of a single trapped ⁸⁷Rb atom and the polarization of a single spontaneously emitted photon [8]. (ii) An additional degree of freedom of the photon is used to encode the quantum state we wish to transfer [18]. (iii) The photon is subject to a complete Bell-state measurement [19,23], projecting the atom into one of four well-defined states. (iv) The success of the transfer is shown with full quantum state tomography of the atomic qubit.

In more detail, we first establish entanglement between a photon and a single neutral ^{87}Rb atom stored in an optical dipole trap [24]. Therefore the atom is optically excited to the $5^2P_{3/2}$, $|F' = 0, m_{F'} = 0\rangle$ state [see Fig. 1(a)]. In the following spontaneous decay the polarization of the emitted photon is entangled with the spin state of the atom [8], resulting in the maximally entangled state

$$|\Psi^+\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\downarrow\rangle_z|\sigma^+\rangle + |\uparrow\rangle_z|\sigma^-\rangle), \quad (1)$$

where $|\sigma^\pm\rangle$ are the right- and left-circular polarization states of the emitted photon. The two states $|\uparrow\rangle_z$ and $|\downarrow\rangle_z$, defining the atomic qubit, correspond to the $|F = 1, m_F = \pm 1\rangle$ Zeeman sublevels of the $5^2S_{1/2}$, $F = 1$ hyperfine ground level.

For the next step, the emitted photon is coupled into a single-mode optical fiber [Fig. 1(b)] and guided to the setup shown in Fig. 2, where the state we wish to transfer is imprinted onto the photon. For this purpose we extend the Hilbert space of the photon by using two spatial modes as an additional degree of freedom. The photon is coherently split into the two spatial modes $|a\rangle$ and $|b\rangle$ by means of a polarization independent Mach-Zehnder interferometer, resulting in the spatial state $\cos(\frac{\alpha}{2})|a\rangle + \sin(\frac{\alpha}{2})|b\rangle$. The phase α is determined by the optical path-length difference between the two interferometer arms. Next, the two spatial modes acquire an additional phase difference ϕ , resulting in the state

$$e^{i\phi} \cos\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)|a\rangle + \sin\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)|b\rangle \quad (2)$$

of the photonic qubit. In order to prepare a well-defined state, precise control over the interferometric phases (α , ϕ) is necessary. Therefore the optical path-length differences in the interferometric setup are actively stabilized with the help of an additional stabilization laser and an electronic feedback loop, allowing measurement times of up to 24 h. By inserting a rotatable glass plate into the stabilization beam we can change these path-length differences and thus precisely control the phase setting.

FIG. 1 (color online). Schematic of atom-photon entanglement generation in a spontaneous decay of a single optically trapped ^{87}Rb atom. (a) After optical excitation to $F' = 0$, the atom decays into the ground state manifold $|\uparrow\rangle_z$, $|\downarrow\rangle_z$ forming an entangled state between the atomic spin and the polarization of the emitted photon. (b) The emitted photon is collected with a microscope objective, coupled into a 5 m long single-mode optical fiber and guided to the preparation setup shown in Fig. 2. The overall detection efficiency for the photon is about 3×10^{-4} .

Next, to transfer the state given by Eq. (2) onto the spin state of the atom, a Bell-state measurement in the joint polarization–spatial-mode Hilbert space of the photon is performed. This is done by combining the two modes $|a\rangle$ and $|b\rangle$ on a polarizing beam splitter (PBS) and analyzing the photon polarization in each output port (see Fig. 2). The polarization analyzer detects $|\pm 45^\circ\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|H\rangle \pm |V\rangle)$ polarized photons by means of four single photon counting Si avalanche photo diodes (APD1-4). Since the PBS transmits horizontal $|H\rangle$ and reflects vertical $|V\rangle$ polarization, a coherent superposition of orthogonal polarizations from both modes is necessary to obtain $|\pm 45^\circ\rangle$ in the output of the PBS. For example, to get $|+45^\circ\rangle$ in the PBS output with detectors 1 and 2, $|H\rangle$ polarization has to be transmitted from mode $|b\rangle$ and coherently added to $|V\rangle$ polarization reflected from mode $|a\rangle$. This corresponds to the Bell state $|\Psi^+\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|V\rangle|a\rangle + |H\rangle|b\rangle)$. Accordingly, the $| - 45^\circ\rangle$ polarization corresponds to the $|\Psi^-\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|V\rangle|a\rangle - |H\rangle|b\rangle)$ state, while in the other output of the PBS the states $|\Phi^\pm\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|H\rangle|a\rangle \pm |V\rangle|b\rangle)$ are detected.

The Bell-state detection projects the atomic qubit onto one of the four states

$$\begin{aligned} |\Phi_1\rangle &= e^{i\phi} \cos\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)|\uparrow\rangle_x + \sin\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)|\downarrow\rangle_x, \\ |\Phi_2\rangle &= e^{i\phi} \cos\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)|\uparrow\rangle_x - \sin\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)|\downarrow\rangle_x, \\ |\Phi_3\rangle &= e^{i\phi} \cos\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)|\downarrow\rangle_x - \sin\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)|\uparrow\rangle_x, \\ |\Phi_4\rangle &= e^{i\phi} \cos\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)|\downarrow\rangle_x + \sin\left(\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)|\uparrow\rangle_x, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

FIG. 2 (color online). Schematic setup for preparing the state from Eq. (2) on the spatial degree of freedom of the photon and for the subsequent Bell-state measurement. The interferometric phase setting (α , ϕ) allows to prepare any desired superposition of the spatial modes $|a\rangle$ and $|b\rangle$ without affecting the polarization degree of freedom. The following PBS, together with the polarization measurement in $|\pm 45^\circ\rangle$, basis enable a complete Bell-state analysis in the combined polarization–spatial-mode Hilbert space of the photon.

where $|\uparrow\rangle_x, |\downarrow\rangle_x = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow\rangle_z \pm |\downarrow\rangle_z)$. State $|\Phi_1\rangle$ is already equivalent to the photonic state from Eq. (2). The states $|\Phi_2\rangle, |\Phi_3\rangle,$ and $|\Phi_4\rangle$ can be transformed into $|\Phi_1\rangle$ by applying the operation $\hat{\sigma}_x, \hat{\sigma}_y,$ or $\hat{\sigma}_z,$ respectively, on the atom.

After completion of the transfer of the state from the photon to the atom we perform the analysis of the atomic state [8]. First, a certain superposition of $|\uparrow\rangle_z$ and $|\downarrow\rangle_z$ is transferred to the $5^2S_{1/2}, F = 2$ hyperfine ground level by means of a state-selective STIRAP process. The polarization of the transfer pulse defines which superposition is transferred and thus allows the choice of the measurement basis. The following hyperfine-state analysis measures the fraction of population which was transferred from the $|F = 1\rangle$ to the $|F = 2\rangle$ ground level. This method allows to analyze the state of the atom in any desired basis and thus to reconstruct the density matrix of the state by combining measurements in 3 complementary bases. The characterization of the entangled atom-photon state with this method yields a fidelity of 87%.

In order to evaluate the performance of our preparation scheme, we prepared different states of the atom by varying the phase settings (α, ϕ) . Then we performed a full quantum state tomography of the atomic qubit for each of the four detected Bell states separately. Figure 3 exemplarily shows a measurement where we set $\alpha = 90^\circ$ while rotating ϕ from 0° to 330° in steps of 30° . Let us consider, e.g., the state which is prepared when the photon is registered in detector APD1. This state can be decomposed as

$$\begin{aligned} |\Phi_1\rangle &= \cos\left(\frac{1}{2}\left(\phi + \frac{\pi}{2}\right)\right)|\uparrow\rangle_z + i \sin\left(\frac{1}{2}\left(\phi + \frac{\pi}{2}\right)\right)|\downarrow\rangle_z \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(e^{i\phi}|\uparrow\rangle_x + |\downarrow\rangle_x) = \cos\left(\frac{1}{2}\phi\right)|\uparrow\rangle_y + i \sin\left(\frac{1}{2}\phi\right)|\downarrow\rangle_y. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

While the projections of $|\Phi_1\rangle$ onto $|\uparrow\rangle_x$ and $|\downarrow\rangle_x$ are equal and constant, we observe a dependence on ϕ for the projection onto $|\uparrow\rangle_z, |\downarrow\rangle_z,$ and $|\uparrow\rangle_y, |\downarrow\rangle_y$. By combining all three measurements we determined the density matrix of each prepared atomic state. From this we derived the fidelity [which is the probability to find the atom in the state expected from Eq. (3)] for each detector and every setting of (α, ϕ) . The mean fidelity over all points and all four analyzed Bell states in this measurement is 82.6%. We performed 4 sets of measurements of this kind preparing various states on different circles on the Bloch sphere (see Fig. 4). Altogether, 42 different states were prepared with a mean fidelity of 82.2% (see Table I).

There are several sources of imperfections which affect the achieved preparation fidelity. The most important factors are the limited purity of the generated entangled atom-photon state and imperfections in the atomic state detection, yielding together a reduced entanglement fidelity of 87%. Taking into account this error source we get a corrected fidelity of $\frac{0.82}{0.87} \approx 94\%$ for the preparation and

FIG. 3 (color online). Tomographic data set of the prepared atomic states for $\alpha = 90^\circ, \phi = 0-330^\circ$. The figures show the probability p to find the atom in the state $|\uparrow\rangle_z$ (left), $|\downarrow\rangle_x = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \times (|\uparrow\rangle_z - |\downarrow\rangle_z)$ (middle), and $|\uparrow\rangle_y = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow\rangle_z + i|\downarrow\rangle_z)$ (right), respectively, after a photon detection in detector 1 (red, filled) and 2 (blue, hollow) (upper row), 3 (green, filled) and 4 (magenta, hollow) (lower row). Each data point is evaluated from 150–350 measurement processes from which we calculate the depicted statistical errors (1 standard deviation). The mean fidelity of the 12 states prepared in this measurement is 82.6%. The acquisition of the full data set was realized within approximately three days at an event rate of 10–20 per min.

teleportation process alone. This value is limited by the finite visibility of the interferometer and Bell-state analyzer (about 96%), the mechanical instability of the interferometer and the residual birefringence of its components. The coherence of the prepared states decays on a time scale of about $10 \mu\text{s}$ and does not influence the current measurement. This decay is caused solely by dephasing due to magnetic stray fields, resulting from instabilities of the magnetic environment. Longer coherence times will be achieved by using an improved compensation method.

The principles enabling the successful remote state preparation now also can be applied to further quantum communication protocols, e.g., the quantum repeater. High- Q cavities can enhance the emission probability of the photon into a particular mode, and thus also the rates, by more than 2 orders of magnitude [25]. These cavities should host several atoms [12], which are first entangled with atoms in one of two neighboring cavities via individual entanglement swapping [26]. Second, the entanglement of the atoms with the ones in the other cavities is purified in order to correct for noise and imperfections. One thereby obtains two entangled atoms in each cavity (except for the outermost ones), where always one of them is highly entangled with one in the two neighboring cavities. A Bell-state measurement on such two atoms swaps the entanglement to the atoms in the neighboring cavities. After similar sequences of purification and entanglement swapping over longer and longer links one finally obtains entanglement between the outermost atoms of this chain. Because of the event-ready signal from the entanglement

FIG. 4 (color online). Bloch-sphere representation of the states prepared on the atomic qubit. The basis states in the equatorial plane are defined as $|\uparrow\rangle_x, |\downarrow\rangle_x := \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow\rangle_z \pm |\downarrow\rangle_z)$ and $|\uparrow\rangle_y, |\downarrow\rangle_y := \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow\rangle_z \pm i|\downarrow\rangle_z)$. The angles (α, ϕ) can be interpreted as usual polar coordinates with respect to the x axis. The numbers 1–4 depict the corresponding measurements from Table I. The insets exemplarily show measured density matrices of the atomic qubit (real part) for four selected states.

swapping to the atoms, the number of steps scales polynomially and enables efficient long distance communication [3]. This way one profits from both the high fidelity and flexibility of quantum logic operations on atoms or ions and the efficient transmission of photonic qubits that are ideally suited for long distance distribution of quantum information.

In conclusion, the presented experiment demonstrates the faithful remote preparation of arbitrary quantum states of a single atom without the need of a direct interaction between the information carrier (photon) and the quantum memory (atom). Our implementation uses a quantum teleportation protocol to transfer the state of a photonic qubit onto the atom with an average preparation fidelity as high

TABLE I. Summary of the experimental results. The table shows the fidelity F , i.e., the probability of a successful state transfer for different phase settings (α, ϕ) , averaged over the 4 detected Bell states and all 12 points within one measurement set.

#	α	ϕ	F
1	90°	$0^\circ - 330^\circ$	$82.6\% \pm 0.40\%$
2	$0^\circ - 330^\circ$	0°	$79.7\% \pm 0.65\%$
3	$0^\circ - 330^\circ$	90°	$84.2\% \pm 0.45\%$
4	109.5°	$0^\circ - 330^\circ$	$82.2\% \pm 0.46\%$

as 82%. Together with the long coherence time of atomic ground states [27] such a system is well suited for future applications and makes the quantum repeater—almost—state of the art.

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5 Conclusion and Outlook

The presented experimental research towards long-distance quantum communication with single atom quantum memories, single photons, and entangled light-matter interfaces culminated quite recently in the observation of heralded entanglement between two independently trapped atoms at a distance of 20 m. For that purpose two single photons, each entangled with one of the atoms, were subjected to an interferometric Bell state analysis thereby swapping the entanglement onto the atoms. The observed entanglement fidelity between the remote atoms was high enough to violate a Bell-inequality. This achievement marks an important milestone, demonstrating its suitability for future quantum information applications, like device independent quantum cryptography [97], quantum networks [98], and quantum repeaters [7, 12, 99].

The design of our experimental setup allows rather straightforward extension of the optical communication link to a distance of about one kilometer, limited only by transmission of the flying qubits (photons) in optical fibers. In contrast to experimental implementations of quantum repeater links on basis of the DLCZ-protocol [12, 14] our two-photon detection scheme neither requires interferometric stability of the optical path length of the communication link on the wavelength-scale nor need the trapped atoms be confined within an optical wavelength (Lamb-Dicke regime). However, the overall success probability for the generation of an entangled pair of atoms at remote locations is only 2×10^{-7} , limited by the collection and coupling efficiency of single spontaneously emitted photons into optical fibers. Taking into account our experimental repetition rate of 50 kHz this translates into the preparation of one entangled pair of atoms every 100 seconds. This numbers already point to the major problem of our current experimental implementation of the probabilistic entangling scheme. For entanglement purification as well as the connection of successive repeater segments one would have to store on average one entangled pair of widely separated atoms for 100 seconds until a second pair is available. Based on coherence time measurements of our atomic Zeeman qubit [46] we currently estimate a maximum coherence time of long-distance atom-atom entanglement of $75 \mu\text{s}$. This time is by far too short for the successful establishment of two entangled pairs of atoms, required, e.g., for the connection of two intermediate repeater links. Obviously the next steps towards a scalable quantum repeater with single optically trapped neutral atoms are: (i) Increase the photon collection and coupling efficiency with an optical cavity [100, 101, 102], such that the success probability for the heralded preparation of entanglement between widely separated atoms reaches values of 10^{-2} . (ii) Boost the atomic quantum storage time with the help of clock-state hyperfine

Figure 5.1: Schematic realization of quantum repeaters with trapped neutral atoms based on probabilistic long-distance atom-atom entanglement and deterministic local controlled-NOT quantum gates using the Rydberg blockade.

qubits [103, 16, 17, 104] into the millisecond domain.

For the implementation of an efficient and scalable quantum repeater (especially for entanglement connection and entanglement purification) with optically trapped neutral atoms one additional important element is required, i.e. deterministic local controlled-NOT (CNOT) quantum gates between nearby trapped atoms forming a repeater node (see Fig. 5.1). In the last two years significant progress in this direction has been reported. Several experiments have demonstrated Rydberg state mediated quantum gates [105] and deterministic entanglement between pairs of trapped neutral atoms at a distance of several μm [37, 36, 106]. Alternatively controlled cold collisions can be used to entangle many atoms in optical lattices [107, 108]. At this point I would like to emphasize that all relevant core techniques for the implementation of a quantum repeater based on individually trapped neutral atoms have been demonstrated in the last ten years:

- The highly efficient state-selective sub- μs detection of single atoms [55]*.
- Long-term storage of quantum information in hyperfine qubits [103].
- Entanglement between flying and stationary qubits in free space [43]* and optical cavities [44].
- Long-distance distribution of atom-photon entanglement [46]*.
- Local quantum gates between nearby trapped atoms based on the Rydberg blockade [36, 37].
- Heralded [this work]* and non-heralded [101] entanglement between two atoms at a distance of 20 m.

Combining and integrating these elements into a single experimental setup is a big challenge. Personally, I believe that the combination of the mentioned core techniques with an emphasis on improving efficiencies, gate fidelities, and quantum storage times as well as applying suitable architectures for many-qubit addressing [83, 84, 85] will pave the way for a first demonstration of a sophisticated quantum network and a quantum repeater. Certainly, this scenario is not only the exclusive avenue of future reserach activities. In fact, it is the starting point to tackle so far unanswered fundamental problems of physics.

Is quantum physics a complete theory, or does the description of nature's laws require local-hidden variable theories? The answer to this question, which was asked by Einstein, Podolsky, and Rosen in 1935 [109], can be found by experimentally testing a so-called Bell inequality [110]. So-far performed Bell experiments with entangled particles [111, 112, 113, 114, 35, 49] left open either the detection [115, 116] or the locality loophole [117, 118]. To constitute a definite answer, it is necessary to close both loopholes in the same Bell experiment, i.e. to perform a Bell test both at a large distance and with high detection efficiencies. Within this context in collaboration with the theoretical groups around Marek Zukowski and Nicolas Gisin we recently proposed two different loophole-free Bell experiments [88, 89]*. Both proposals require application of central experimental techniques developed in our group, i.e. the reliable generation of atom-photon entanglement over large distances [43, 46]*, the heralded entanglement between widely separated atoms (this work) and the deterministic sub- μ s readout of atomic spin-states [55]*. Although both proposals are experimentally challenging the so-far developed techniques open the first time the door for a loophole-free test of Bell's inequality.

Loophole-free Bell test with one atom and less than one photon on averageN. Sangouard,¹ J.-D. Bancal,¹ N. Gisin,¹ W. Rosenfeld,² P. Sekatski,¹ M. Weber,² and H. Weinfurter²¹*Group of Applied Physics, University of Geneva, CH-1211 Geneva 4, Switzerland*²*Fakultat für Physik, Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München, DE-80799 München, Germany*

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We consider the entanglement between two internal states of a single atom and two photon number states describing either the vacuum or a single photon and thus containing, on average, less than one photon. We show that this intriguing entanglement can be characterized through substantial violations of a Bell inequality by performing homodyne detections on the optical mode. We present the experimental challenges that need to be overcome to pave the way toward a loophole-free Bell test.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Is quantum physics a complete theory, or does the description of nature's laws require local-hidden-variable theories? The answer to this question, which was asked by Einstein, Podolsky, and Rosen in 1935, can be found by realizing a Bell test [1]. On the one hand, two distant observers, who have performed appropriate measurements on entangled photon pairs, have observed correlated results violating a Bell inequality even though the measurement choices were made long after the pair creation [2] and even though the photons were too far from each other to agree on the results once they knew the measurement basis [3]. On the other hand, two ions close to each other have also exhibited the violation of a Bell inequality even though they were forced to give a result at each trial [4]. But to constitute a definitive answer, it would be necessary to close all the loopholes in the same Bell experiment, i.e., to perform a Bell test both at a distance and with high detection efficiencies.

Closing the detection loophole for the Clauser-Horne-Shimony-Holt (CHSH) inequality [5] requires overall detection efficiencies larger than 82.8% for a maximally entangled state and larger than 66.7% using partially entangled states [6] in the absence of other imperfections. This threshold detection efficiency can further be lowered using states with a dimension higher than qubits. For example, in Ref. [7], it has been shown that a detection efficiency of 61.8% can be tolerated using four-dimensional states and a four-setting Bell inequality. However, considering realistic noise, achievable coupling into the quantum channel (usually an optical fiber), and detection efficiencies, one rapidly becomes aware that closing the detection loophole in an optical Bell test is extremely challenging.

The problem of the single-photon detection efficiency might be circumvented by using homodyne measurements, which are known to be very efficient [8–10]. In this framework, theoretical proposals leading to substantial violations of Bell's inequalities and combining feasible states and measurements have been put forth recently [11].

An attractive alternative is to use an asymmetric configuration involving, e.g., atom-photon entanglement. Since the atom can be detected with an efficiency close to 1, the detection efficiency on the photon side is lower than the case wherein the detections at both sides are inefficient [12,13]—as low as 50% for the CHSH inequality and 43% for a

three-setting inequality. Furthermore, the photon is naturally used to distribute entanglement over long distances so that the choice of the measurement on one side and the measurement result on the other side can easily be spacelike separated. Note that the entanglement between internal states of an atom and the polarization degree of freedom of a photon have already been observed experimentally [14–16]. Such entanglement has further been used to entangle remote atoms from an entanglement-swapping operation [17]. We focus on the entanglement between internal states of an atom and a partially filled optical mode, containing on average less than one photon, as described in detail in Sec. II. We propose Bell-type scenarios either combining a homodyne detection and a photon counting on the optical mode or using homodyne detections only to characterize this special entanglement. Although homodyne detections are used, we show in Sec. III that unexpectedly large violations of the CHSH inequality can be observed. We also present a feasibility study in Sec. IV. We provide the minimal entanglement generation and photon-counting efficiencies that are required to close the detection loophole. We then give the typical distance that is necessary to close the locality loophole. We also take the branching ratios into account, we analyze the effect of the atomic motion, and we present the requirement on the optical-path-length stability. The last section is devoted to the conclusion.

II. ENTANGLEMENT CREATION BETWEEN ONE ATOM AND LESS THAN ONE PHOTON

Let us start with a description of the methods enabling the creation of entanglement between two atomic states and a single optical mode containing on average less than one photon. Consider an atom with a lambda-type level configuration (as depicted in Fig. 1), initially prepared in the state g . A pump-laser pulse with the Rabi frequency Ω partially excites the atom in such a way that it can spontaneously decay to the level s by emitting a photon [18]. Long after the decay time of the atom, the atom-photon state is given by

$$\psi^\phi = \cos\theta|g,0\rangle + e^{i\phi}\sin\theta|s,1\rangle, \quad (1)$$

where $\theta = \frac{1}{2} \int ds \Omega(s)$ refers to the area of the pump pulse. The phase term is defined by $\phi = k_p r_p - k_s r_s$, where k_p (and k_s) correspond to the wave vector of the pump (and the

FIG. 1. Basic level scheme for the creation of entanglement between one atom and one optical mode containing on average less than one photon. The branching ratio is such that when the atom is excited, it decays preferentially in s .

spontaneous photon) and r_p (and r_s) are the atom position when the pump photon is absorbed (and the spontaneous photon is emitted). Note that ϕ may vary in practice, e.g., due to atom-position variations. The requirements for the phase stability are studied in detail below, but we first answer this question: can the entanglement between an atom and a partially filled optical mode be measured from the violation of a Bell inequality?

III. HOMODYNE DETECTIONS IN AN ASYMMETRIC BELL TEST

A. Principle of the Bell test

First, let us recall the principle of a Bell-CHSH test. Two distant observers, usually named Alice and Bob, share a quantum state. Each of them randomly chooses a measurement among two projectors, $\{X_i\}$ for Alice and $\{Y_j\}$ for Bob, where $i, j \in [1, 2]$, and each obtains a binary result, $\{a_i\}$ and $\{b_j\}$ for Alice and Bob, respectively. By repeating the experiment several times, Alice and Bob can compute the conditional probabilities $p(a_i b_j | X_i Y_j)$. They can then easily deduce the value of the CHSH parameter

$$S = E_{X_1 Y_1} + E_{X_1 Y_2} + E_{X_2 Y_1} - E_{X_2 Y_2}, \quad (2)$$

where $E(X_i Y_j) = p(a_i = b_j | X_i Y_j) - p(a_i \neq b_j | X_i Y_j)$. Alice and Bob will conclude that the observed correlations cannot be described by local-hidden-variable theories if they find measurement settings such that $S > 2$. Note that all possible states leading to a violation of a Bell inequality are entangled. Therefore, a Bell test can be seen not only as a test of the laws of nature but also as a witness of entanglement.

B. Bell test with one atom and less than one photon

Now, consider the specific case in which Alice and Bob share a state of the form (1). Alice applies projective measurements on the atomic states and can freely choose projections on arbitrary vectors $\vec{v}_j^A = \cos \frac{\alpha_j}{2} |g\rangle + e^{i\phi_j} \sin \frac{\alpha_j}{2} |s\rangle$ of the Bloch sphere. For each measurement X_j , $j = 1, 2$, and Alice sets $a_j = +1$ if she gets a result along \vec{v}_j^A and $a_j = -1$ if the result is directed along $\vec{v}_j^{A\perp}$. Bob applies measurements on the optical mode and chooses either to count the photon number $Y_1 = n$ or to measure the quadrature $Y_2 = \cos \zeta \hat{X} + \sin \zeta \hat{P}$. When he measures n , he naturally sets $b_1 = +1$ if the result is

positive and $b_1 = -1$ if there is no photon. When he performs the quadrature measurement, he gets a real number x . He then has to process this result to get binary outcomes. He decides to attribute the results $b_2 = -1$ if the result is negative ($x \leq 0$) and $b_2 = +1$ otherwise.

We now show that Alice and Bob can obtain a substantial violation of the CHSH inequality for appropriate settings. But let us first detail the calculation of probability distributions $p(a_i b_j | X_i Y_j)$ for the four pairs of measurements separately. When Bob measures n , he gets $b_1 = -1$ with the probability $\cos^2 \theta$, and Alice's qubit is projected into $|g\rangle$. Therefore,

$$p(+1, -1 | X_j Y_1) = \cos^2 \theta |\langle \vec{v}_j^A | g \rangle|^2 = \cos^2 \theta \left(\frac{1 + \cos \alpha_j}{2} \right).$$

Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned} p(-1, -1 | X_j Y_1) &= \cos^2 \theta |\langle \vec{v}_j^{A\perp} | g \rangle|^2 \\ &= \cos^2 \theta \left(\frac{1 - \cos \alpha_j}{2} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Following similar lines for $b_1 = +1$, one finds

$$p(a_j, +1 | X_j Y_1) = \sin^2 \theta \left(\frac{1 - a_j \cos \alpha_j}{2} \right),$$

leading to

$$E_{X_j Y_1} = -\cos \alpha_j. \quad (3)$$

When Bob measures Y_2 and obtains $b_2 = -1$, Alice's state is projected into

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{b_2=-1}^A &= \cos^2 \theta \int_{-\infty}^0 dx |\Phi_0(x)|^2 |g\rangle\langle g| \\ &+ \frac{1}{2} \sin 2\theta e^{-i\phi} e^{i\zeta} \int_{-\infty}^0 dx \Phi_1^*(x) \Phi_0(x) |g\rangle\langle s| \\ &+ \frac{1}{2} \sin 2\theta e^{i\phi} e^{-i\zeta} \int_{-\infty}^0 dx \Phi_0^*(x) \Phi_1(x) |s\rangle\langle g| \\ &+ \sin^2 \theta \int_{-\infty}^0 dx |\Phi_1(x)|^2 |s\rangle\langle s|, \end{aligned}$$

where $\Phi_0(x) = \langle x|0\rangle$ and $\Phi_1(x) = \langle x|1\rangle$ are the probability-amplitude distributions for the vacuum and single-photon Fock states, respectively [$\Phi_n(x) = \frac{1}{(2^n n! \sqrt{\pi})^{1/2}} H_n(x) e^{-x^2/2}$, where $H_n(x)$ is the Hermite polynomial]. $p(+1, -1 | X_j Y_2)$ is merely deduced from $\langle \vec{v}_j^A | \rho_{b_2=-1}^A | \vec{v}_j^A \rangle$ and $p(-1, -1 | X_j Y_2)$ from $\langle \vec{v}_j^{A\perp} | \rho_{b_2=-1}^A | \vec{v}_j^{A\perp} \rangle$. One can check that $p(a_j, +1 | X_j Y_2)$ has the same expression as $p(a_j, -1 | X_j Y_2)$, but where the integration over dx runs from 0 to $+\infty$, one finds

$$E_{X_j Y_2} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \sin \alpha_j \sin 2\theta \cos(\varphi_j - \phi + \zeta).$$

Interestingly, this expression is the same, up to a factor of $\sqrt{2/\pi}$, as the expression of the correlator when Bob applies a perfect qubit measurement along $\cos \zeta \sigma_x + \sin \zeta \sigma_y$. This invites us to interpret the homodyne measurement above (with the binning $x \leq 0 \rightarrow b_2 = -1$ and $x > 0 \rightarrow b_2 = +1$ in the $\{|0\rangle, |1\rangle\}$ subspace) as a noisy qubit measurement in the xy plane of the Bloch sphere with visibility $\sqrt{2/\pi}$ as was also noticed in Ref. [19].

Substituting the correlators by their expressions into Eq. (2), one obtains a value of the CHSH polynomial for any state of the form (1) and for any measurement of Alice. We found the maximal violation $S = -2 \cos \alpha_1 + 2\sqrt{2/\pi} \sin \alpha_1 \approx 2.56$ for $\theta = \pi/4$ and $\phi = 0$, i.e., the ϕ_+ state and for $\varphi_1 = \varphi_2 = \zeta = 0$, and $\alpha_1 = -\alpha_2 = 2 \arctan(\frac{\sqrt{\pi+\sqrt{2+\pi}}}{\sqrt{2}})$. This violation is the largest that we know in a scenario involving a homodyne detection in which both the measurements and the state can be realized experimentally (see Ref. [11] and the references therein).

C. Bell test with homodyne detections only on the optical mode

A natural question is whether a violation of the CHSH inequality can also be observed by measuring the optical mode with homodyne detections only. It turns out that a violation $S = 4/\sqrt{\pi} \approx 2.26$ can indeed be obtained if Alice and Bob share a maximally entangled state of the form (1) with $\theta = \pi/4$ and $\phi = 0$, provided that Bob's measurements are performed in complementary quadratures $Y_1 = \hat{X}$ and $Y_2 = \hat{P}$ and that Alice's measurements correspond to projections along vectors spanning the (xy) plane with angles $\pm 45^\circ$ between them. This result can easily be understood using the analogy previously mentioned. If Bob uses either σ_x or σ_y , the CHSH parameter would be saturated ($S = 2\sqrt{2}$). Since \hat{X} and \hat{P} correspond to such measurements but with the reduced visibility $\sqrt{2/\pi}$, S is reduced by the corresponding factor.

IV. IMPERFECTIONS

So far, we have shown that an ideal realization would lead to significant violations of the CHSH inequality. However, the story would not be complete without a discussion taking experimental imperfections into account.

A. Transmission inefficiency

Let η_t be the transmission efficiency which accounts for all the coupling inefficiencies from the atom to Bob's location. The probability amplitude associated with $|s, 1\rangle$ is now multiplied by $\sqrt{\eta_t}$, and Alice and Bob can share the state $\psi_{\eta_t}^\phi = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}}(\cos \theta |g, 0\rangle + e^{i\phi} \sin \theta \sqrt{\eta_t} |s, 1\rangle)$ with the probability $N = \cos^2 \theta + \sin^2 \theta \eta_t$. Alternatively, the photon can be lost. Tracing out the lost photon, the resulting state is $|s, 0\rangle$, and it contributes to the global state with a weight $\sin^2 \theta (1 - \eta_t)$. To know the sensitivity of the CHSH inequality with respect to the transmission inefficiency, we thus have to compute S from the overall state

$$\rho_{\eta_t} = N |\psi_{\eta_t}^\phi\rangle\langle\psi_{\eta_t}^\phi| + \sin^2 \theta (1 - \eta_t) |s, 0\rangle\langle s, 0| \quad (4)$$

for all possible values of $\theta, \phi, \varphi_1, \varphi_2, \zeta, \alpha_1$, and α_2 as a function of η_t . The result is shown in Fig. 2. In the scenario in which Bob uses a photon counter and a homodyne detection with unit efficiencies, a transmission efficiency of $\eta_t = 61\%$ can be tolerated [see the solid (blue) curve of Fig. 2]. Although this is certainly demanding, recent results suggest that this might soon be within reach of experiments [20]. It is also interesting to study the sensitivity of the violation with respect to the detection inefficiency. The homodyne measurements can fairly be considered to have unit efficiencies, but most

FIG. 2. (Color online) Robustness of the CHSH violation with respect to the transmission efficiency η_t . The dashed-dotted (purple) line is associated with the case in which Bob uses two homodyne detections (with unit efficiencies). The other lines correspond to the cases in which Bob chooses either a photon counter or a measurement of a field quadrature. The upper, solid (blue) curve is associated with a photon detector with unit efficiency $\eta_d = 1$. The three dashed lines are associated with inefficient counting (from $\eta_d = 0.8$ to 0.4).

of the single-photon detectors are inefficient. Let η_d be the efficiency of the photon-counting detector. From an optimization similar to the previous one, we find that a threshold detection of $\eta_d = 39\%$ can be tolerated for a transmission with unit efficiency. Our scheme is less sensitive to counting inefficiency than transmission inefficiency since the former affects only one of Bob's measurements. The two previous efficiency thresholds can be compared with a scheme that exhibits the same asymmetry but uses the entanglement with the polarization mode [13] and for which the violation of the CHSH inequality requires $\eta_t \eta_d \geq 50\%$. (The effects of detection and transmission imperfections are the same in this case since Bob uses two photon-counting detectors.) The latter is less sensitive to inefficiency in the transmission (for ideal detectors with $\eta_d = 1$) while the scheme we propose is less sensitive to the detector inefficiency (for transmission with $\eta_t = 1$.) Note also that regarding the results presented in Refs. [7,13] wherein the threshold efficiency has been lowered using inequalities with more settings, one could have possible improvements using inequalities different from the CHSH inequality. However, we could not find better resistances with additional binnings for Bob's results and for more (up to three) inputs.

In the case in which Bob uses only quadrature measurements, the CHSH inequality can be violated provided that the transmission efficiency is larger than 79%. This scenario is thus more robust to the transmission inefficiency than the proposals of Refs. [7,13] if the single-photon detectors required in the latter have an efficiency smaller than 63%.

B. Required distance between Alice and Bob

In the previous section, we addressed efficiency issues related to the photon detection and to the transmission. If we

intend to close the locality loophole too, we have to determine how long the state detection takes. It is likely reasonable to believe that the detection time is limited by the atom [21]. If the atomic states are read out on the basis of stimulated Raman adiabatic passage, ultrafast laser ionization, and registration of the correlated electron-ion pairs with coincident counting via two opposing-channel electron multipliers [22], we can reach a measurement time of less than 1 μ s. Therefore, the locality loophole can be closed if Alice and Bob are separated by 300 m. For 800-nm photons, the losses are of 2 dB/km. This translates into a transmission of 93%.

C. Branching ratio

So far, we have considered that once the atom is excited, it decays into the state s . Consider the more realistic case in which the decay from e to s occurs with the probability f_s . Let f_g be the probability of a decay into g and f_{aux} the decay probability into other auxiliary states such that $f_s + f_g + f_{\text{aux}} = 1$. Taking these branching ratios into account, the state long after the interaction with the pump pulse is

$$\rho_f = N' |\psi_{f_s}^\phi\rangle \langle \psi_{f_s}^\phi| + \sin^2 \theta f_g |g, 0\rangle \langle g, 0| + \sin^2 \theta f_{\text{aux}} |\text{aux}, 0\rangle \langle \text{aux}, 0|.$$

$\psi_{f_s}^\phi$ is defined from $\psi_{\eta_t}^\phi$, where η_t is replaced by f_s and $N' = \cos^2 \theta + \sin^2 \theta f_s$. We now present a strategy to make $S > 2$ (calculated from this state) as soon as $f_s \neq 0$. If Alice chooses to attribute the result $a_j = -1$ when she measures the atom in the state aux , the correlators calculated from $|\text{aux}, 0\rangle$ are $E_{X_j Y_1} = 1, E_{X_j Y_2} = 0 \forall j \in \{1, 2\}$, and the resulting S value is equal to 2 in this case. Moreover, if she chooses two measurements very close to σ_z , i.e., ($\alpha_1 = \pi - \epsilon, \varphi_1 = 0$) and ($\alpha_2 = -\pi + \epsilon, \varphi_2 = 0$), one can check that the S value computed from the component $|g, 0\rangle$ is $2 - \epsilon^2$. If she further excites the atom so that $\theta = \pi/4$ and $\phi = 0$ and if Bob chooses $\zeta = 0$, the S value from $\psi_{f_s}^\phi$ is roughly $2 + 4 \frac{\epsilon}{1+f_s} \frac{\sqrt{2f_s}}{\sqrt{\pi}}$. The overall CHSH value is thus given by

$$S \approx 2 + 4 \frac{\sqrt{f_s}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \epsilon + o(\epsilon^2). \quad (5)$$

Therefore, in the absence of errors, the only requirement on the branching ratios to observe a violation of the CHSH inequality is that once the atom is excited, the probability that it decays into s has to be nonzero. This Bell test can thus be applied to a large number of atomic species since it is very resistant to branching-ratio variations. However, the larger the decay into s is, the larger the violation.

D. Stability requirements

Let us now focus on the phase-stability constraints. The phase term of the state (1) has to remain stable from trial to trial. In practice, however, ϕ may vary, e.g., due to atom-position variations. For wave vectors with the same norm $\|\vec{k}\| = \|\vec{k}_p\| = \|\vec{k}_s\|$, the fidelity of the resulting entanglement

$$\rho = F |\psi^\phi\rangle \langle \psi^\phi| + (1 - F) |\psi^{\phi+\pi}\rangle \langle \psi^{\phi+\pi}| \quad (6)$$

is found to be

$$F = \frac{1}{2} [1 + e^{-2a^2(\bar{n}+1/2)\Delta k}] \quad (7)$$

in the weak-confinement regime [23,24]. $a = \sqrt{\hbar/(2m\omega)}$ is the size of the harmonic-trapping-potential ground state for an atom of mass m within a trap of frequency ω . \bar{n} is the average number of thermal quanta of motion, and $\Delta k = \|\vec{k}\| (1 - \cos \theta)$, where θ is the angle between the pump beam and the emission direction. Hence, the problem of the atomic motion can not only be overcome by cooling the ions deeply within the Lamb-Dicke limit (where \bar{n} is small) but more simply by collecting the photons scattered in the forward direction where $\theta = 0$.

Let us also comment on the stability requirement on the optical path lengths. The local oscillator that is required to perform the homodyne detections at Bob's location can be obtained by removing a fraction of the pump beam with a beam splitter. In this case, the setup is made of a large Mach-Zehnder interferometer, and the path-length difference between the two arms of the interferometer ΔL has to be stable so that $\|\vec{k}\| \Delta L \ll 1$. Note that temperature variations change both the refraction index (and thus $\|\vec{k}\|$) and the length of the fibers ΔL . For commercial fibers, several tens of kilometers long, installed in an urban environment, the typical time needed for a mean-phase change of 0.1 rad (corresponding to a fidelity of 0.9) is of the order of 100 μ s [25]. This lets us believe that an active stabilization of the phase should be possible even for very long interferometers using available technologies. This is well confirmed by recent experimental results [26].

V. CONCLUSION

We proposed different scenarios to measure the entanglement between the internal state of an atom and an optical mode containing, on average, less than one photon. We reported large violations of a CHSH inequality for both the case in which one homodyne detection and one-photon counting are performed on the optical mode and for that involving two homodyne detections. With homodyne detections only, a minimal entanglement-generation efficiency of 79% can be tolerated. This efficiency goes down to 61% if homodyne detections are combined with unit-efficiency photon counting. We have also shown that in principle, a violation of the CHSH inequality can be obtained even for branching ratios favoring photon emission in undesired modes. There is no need to cool the atom deeply within the Lamb-Dicke regime if the scattered photons are collected close to the forward direction with respect to the pump propagation. Finally, the stability requirements for the optical path lengths are within reach of experiments.

We believe that our work could provide motivations for several research groups. Much effort has already been devoted to the characterization of single-photon Fock states with homodyne detections [27]. Moreover, although the setup recently developed by the Remppe group has been used to address squeezed light [28], it is of particular interest for our proposal as it combines a single atom embedded in a

high-finesse cavity with a homodyne detection. Note also that beyond its fundamental interest, our proposal might find exciting applications in the framework of quantum-information sciences, e.g., for device-independent quantum cryptography [29].

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6 Publication List

The papers reprinted in this habilitation are indicated by bold title print in the following list. Citations of these papers in the main text of this work are indicated by *.

- *Ascertaining the values of σ_x , σ_y , and σ_z of a polarization qubit*, Oliver Schulz, Ruprecht Steinhübel, Markus Weber, Berthold-Georg Englert, Christian Kurtsiefer and Harald Weinfurter, Phys. Rev. Lett. 90, 177901 (2003).
- *Quantum optical experiments towards atom-photon entanglement*, Markus Weber, PhD thesis under the direction of Prof. Harald Weinfurter. Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München, June 17th, 2005.
- *Analysis of a single-atom dipole trap*, Markus Weber, Jürgen Volz, Karen Saucke, Christian Kurtsiefer, and Harald Weinfurter, Phys. Rev. A 73, 043406 (2006).
- (*) **Observation of Entanglement between a single photon and a single trapped atom**, Jürgen Volz, Markus Weber, Daniel Schlenk, Wenjamin Rosenfeld, Johannes Vrana, Karen Saucke, Christian Kurtsiefer and Harald Weinfurter, Phys. Rev. Lett. **96**, 030404 (2006).
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- Coherence of a qubit stored in Zeeman levels of a single optically trapped atom, W. Rosenfeld, J. Volz, M. Weber, and H. Weinfurter, *Phys. Rev. A* **84**, 022343 (2011).
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- (*) **Loophole-free Bell test with one atom and less than one photon on average**, N. Sangouard, J.-D. Bancal, N. Gisin, W. Rosenfeld, P. Sekatski, M. Weber, and H. Weinfurter, *Phys. Rev. A* **84**, 052122 (2011).
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